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**Fourth periodic report on
PhD Projects**

Responsible Partner: UoS

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INTRODUCTION

To complement the One Health EJP's (OHEJP) research and integrative activities, between 2018 and 2019, 16 PhDs were co-funded by Work Package 6 (each funded 44% by the EU). The research focus of the individual PhD projects falls within at least one of the three research domains of the OHEJP: foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats, and all align with the [Strategic Research Agenda](#). Each PhD project has at least two One Health EJP consortium partners collaborating on the project.

An additional PhD funded through Work Package 7 (WP7, Sustainability) also commenced in 2019. This PhD lies in the field of social sciences and public health. The progress of this PhD is monitored and assessed differently, and further details can be found in the report.

The PhD projects provide opportunities to explore and share skills, expertise and knowledge from the OHEJP consortium, therefore accelerating both the rate and quality of research in addition to developing the One Health scientific leaders of the future.

There is significant scope for inter-disciplinary networking among One Health EJP partners in addition to the interaction with the Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs). The JRPs and JIPs have expertise that can support the PhD students, and provide opportunities to explore and share skills and knowledge, accelerating both the rate and quality of the research. These interactions help to bring the physical, biological, and social sciences together, and allow greater flexibility in the PhD projects to ensure innovative hypothesis driven research. The multi-country and inter-disciplinary approaches help inform decisions on market viability and EU policy relevance of project outputs.

The PhD projects provide excellent added value to the OHEJP, including improved integration (both geographical and interdisciplinary), and an opportunity to develop the next generation of scientists in One Health contributing to the sustainability of the One Health approach.

Each year, the PhD projects report on the research activities, progress, results, risks, ethics, and impact for the previous 12-month reporting period. A record of the dissemination activities and soft skills training that took place during this period is also reported. This deliverable report contains the 12-month reports for each PhD project for months 37 to 48 (Jan-Dec 2021) of the One Health EJP. The purpose of this deliverable is to monitor, report and disseminate the progress and results that can be shared publicly.

1. Summary of the PhD projects performance

In 2021, 15 of the 17 projects incurred delays caused by the COVID-19 global pandemic which impacted the feasibility of meeting the deadlines of the planned deliverables and milestones. The impact of the pandemic on the planned deliverables and milestones is described in further detail in each PhD report in this deliverable. Deliverables or milestones that had not been met on time were assigned new delivery dates within the timeline of the project.

1.1. Overview of project deliverables and milestones

Deliverables in 2021	Total	Finalised	Delayed to 2022
Number	44	24	20
Percentage	100%	56%	45%

Deliverables in 2021	Due	Finalised	Delayed to 2022
ECO-HEN	4	2	2
LIN-RES	4	4	0
HME-AMR	1	0	1
KENTUCKY	3	2	1
METAPRO	1	1	0
PEMbO	3	2	1
MACE	4	1	3
DESIRE	2	0	2
UDoFRIC	4	2	2
WILBR	2	2	0
EnvDis	1	1	0
AptaTrich	1	1	0
VIMOGUT	2	0	2
ToxSauQMRA	2	1	1
TRACE	2	0	2
Codes4Strains	8	5	3
SUSTAIN (WP7 PhD)	Deliverables are not linked to specific tasks, and instead are defined and assessed by Roskilde University. See 12M report for further details.		

39% of the milestones (19/48) planned for months 37 to 48 were finalised. As with the deliverables, many of these milestones were impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. A new delivery date has been assigned within the project timeline.

The activities, deliverables and milestones reported in the 12M reports are those for the reporting period of Month 37- Month 48 of the One Health EJP (January – December 2021).

1.2. PhD project timelines and research domains – an overview

The planned timelines for the One Health EJP PhD projects are shown below.

Please note, the delays reported in this deliverable are associated with intermediate deliverables and milestones during the project. These delays have not had an impact on the expected end date, unless otherwise indicated. At this stage, it is premature to determine the impact on the expected end date, and a number of actions have been taken to alleviate the impact of these delays.

12M REPORTS OF PhD PROJECTS FOR MONTHS 37-48

2. PhD01 ECO-HEN

2.1. Summary

During these 12 months, from January 2021 to December 2021, the student has carried out the following activities.

She joined the annual scientific meeting that took place online (June). During the congress, the student had the opportunity both to share part of her work and to listen to the work of other colleges. In addition, she presented a poster. During the same congress, the student also participated in the "3 minutes thesis" competition, in which she was able to summarise her project and present it to her colleagues. This contributed to the development of her oral and written dissemination skills. Her writing abilities were further developed during the preparation of a manuscript as well as the preparation of an abstract for the oral presentation of an upcoming congress that took place in July. The student participated during these months in the university activity called: doctoral seminars. Through the preparation and presentation of the seminar, the following competencies were developed: summarizing, processing and critical analysis of the data produced and, the public presentation of her activity. By attending other seminars, the student acquired competencies and skills in critical analysis and public questioning and came to be more familiar with the methodologies and objectives of other topics of research.

In February, the student participated in Digital innovations for One Health practitioners' workshop, training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability. She had the opportunity to familiarise herself with other One Health EJP projects as ORION, COHESIVE and RADAR and she was introduced to open-source software tools focused on different disciplines. The student also participated as an assistant in the laboratory activities of the Microbiology and Immunology subject belonging to the Veterinary degree, acquiring teaching skills.

In July, the student presented part of his work in the form of an oral communication in the XXVIII National Microbiology Congress organised by the Spanish Society of Microbiology. During the conference, the student got to know the work of some of her colleagues in the subject and developed her oral skills. Between the end of July and the beginning of August, the student took part in the summer school, organised by OHEJP and Istituto Superiore di Sanità of Italy. The student learned not only about the One Health concept in the environment, but also how to develop (as a group) a national surveillance plan focused on a real pathogen. This plan had to include the three pillars of One Health, so the student went deeper into the concept, as for the plan, actions had to be thought of for animal health, human health and the environment.

In October, the student was part of the organising committee of a congress held at the veterinary faculty. The student had the opportunity to see a congress from the other side, organising the abstracts, the talks, the posters, the timetable, and the breaks. In addition, the webinar "AMR Surveillance in The Netherlands (and beyond) from a One Health perspective" took place on 18 and 22 October, where the student could learn about AMR surveillance in different fields, such as hospitals, livestock, or the environment.

During the 12 months, from February 2020 to January 2021, the student carried out many activities. At the beginning of the year the student participated in a research meetings programme called VISAVET JOURNAL CLUB, organized by the research institute itself. This activity consists of seminars in which a scientific article is presented and discussed among colleagues. It allows not only to learn to critically analyse an article, but also to expose your own opinion and argue with co-workers. She also joined in May the annual scientific meeting that took place online. During this congress, the student had the opportunity both to share part of her work and to listen to the work of other colleagues. During the

congress, a poster with the title “First report of trimethoprim resistance gene *dfrA36* on an *IncF*-plasmid in *Escherichia coli* isolated from day-old chicks” in which a work was presented that covered both laboratory analysis and computer one. During this congress, the student also participated in the thesis contest in 3 minutes, in which she was able to make a summary of her thesis and listen to the projects of her colleagues. Both when writing a poster and in the contest, the student was trained in writing scientific articles and in disseminating a work orally.

During this year, several training courses and activities have also been held. In March the student participated in a course on epidemiological aspects and statistical studies of a research work, in which she learned what type of study to use for each type of data, as well as using software for statistical analysis. In May, the 9-month online specialization diploma in bioinformatics analysis was completed. In these postgraduate studies, the student was able to train in the bioinformatic analysis of massive biological data, interpretation of the data from an omic experiment and plan their subsequent analysis by means of bioinformatics tools, etc. In June, the student successfully completed a spreadsheet training course with EXCEL in which she was able to learn how to create attractive formatted spreadsheets, do automatic calculations using formulas and functions, and make graphs that allow you to visualize data effectively. In addition, another online course ended in December, the objective of which was to introduce the student to data visualization and the development of our own visualizations in Python in which the aspects to consider creating effective data visualizations and how to select the type of graph that best suits the data we want to show were discussed. Later it will be detailed how to create data visualizations in Python using different libraries. In October, the student participated in a workshop organized by OHEJP "Communications and Media Workshop" in which he had the opportunity to discuss with his colleagues how science achievements reach people and contribute to a better life, as well as listening to professionals talking about the importance of communication in science, among other things. Finally, the student has attended both seminars and presentations of doctoral thesis of colleagues within the University, thus being able to listen to other ideas and other works that can enrich hers.

2.2. Overview of project progress

WP1-WP4 and WP6-WP7 have already been achieved.

In October, the egg isolates in the database that had not yet been sequenced (WP7) were checked and sequenced. Now the writing of the thesis (WP9) is in progress and in parallel, the tasks of WP5 and WP8, related to the egg sequences, are being finalised. The writing of the thesis, planned to start in July 2021, was delayed until October due to delays arising from the COVID-19 pandemic, so WP9 will be delayed until May 2022.

2.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

During the nine-month reporting period (January 2021 to September 2021) the PhD work was focused on the in-depth analysis of cefotaxime-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from the studied farm. After this, to December 2021, the work has focused on finishing the unfinished tasks and starting to write the thesis.

WP5. Reconstruction of plasmids spreading AMR genes from animal to egg shell isolates

By studying cefotaxime-resistant isolates, we identified different plasmids harboring genes responsible for cephalosporin resistance: (i) IncI1/ST3 plasmids were found harboring *bla_{CTX-M-1}* gene in *E. coli* isolates from day-old chicks, pullets and laying hens. These IncI1/ST3 plasmids also harbored the sulfonamides resistance gene *sul2* and tetracycline resistance gene *tet(A)*. *Bla_{CTX-M-1}* has also been found in the chromosomal DNA in some isolates, together with an IncX1 plasmid harboring beta lactam resistance gene *bla_{TEM-1B}* and tetracycline resistance one *tet(A)*. both *bla_{CTX-M-1}* genes, the one identified in plasmid and the one identified in chromosome, have been identified close to an insertion sequence

ISECp1. (ii) Inc1/ST26 plasmids have been identified harboring the ESBL *bla_{SHV-12}* gene. These plasmids have been identified harboring also the *tet(A)* gene and a class 1 integron with streptomycin/spectinomycin resistance genes *aadA1* and *aadA2*, chloramphenicol resistance gene *cmIA1* and sulfonamides resistance gene *sul3*. Isolates with these plasmids have been identified in the farm in isolates from pullets and laying hens. Moreover, this isolates also had IncX1 plasmids with *bla_{TEM-1B}* and quinolones resistance gene *qnrS1*. (iii) The ampC resistance gene *bla_{CMY-2}* has been identified in two different plasmids in the farm. Inc1/ST plasmids have been identified in laying hens harboring this gene, presenting these isolates also a class 1 integron in a non-typable plasmid. In addition, *bla_{CMY-2}* gene has been main identified in a IncK2 plasmids in isolates from all the growing phases in the farm (from day-old chicks to laying hens). Gene in both plasmids has been identified downstream of an insertion sequence *ISECp1*, which can facilitate gene insertion in mobile genetic elements.

Plasmid stability experiments. We studied the stability of a large plasmid harboring the gene of interest *dfra36*. This experiment was conducted for up to 100 generations in the absence of antibiotic selective pressure. After 100 generations, more than 80% of the cells lost the plasmid. The stability of this plasmid in the presence of antibiotic was also studied up to generation 20, with 20% of the cells lost the plasmid up to this generation, compared to 50% lost after 20 generations in the absence of selective pressure. This means that this large plasmid is lost over generations even with antibiotic pressure, although less abruptly in the presence of antibiotic in the medium.

In addition, a conjugation experiment was performed with the same plasmid. A rifampicin-resistant strain of *E. coli* was used as receptor, and the isolates with the plasmid of interest as a donor. Conjugation efficiency was calculated by counting donor colonies (ampicillin-resistant), receptor colonies (rifampicin-resistant) and transconjugants (ampicillin and rifampicin resistant) with the formula:

$$\text{Conjugacion efficiency (CE)} = \log \left(\frac{\text{Transconjugants (T)}}{\sqrt{\text{Donor (D)} \times \text{Receptor (R)}}} \right)$$

A result of 6.4% conjugation efficiency was obtained.

WP6. Flow of AMR isolates between animals.

The objective of this WP is to follow the dynamics of AMR, both, isolates and associated platforms, from day-old chicks to pullets and laying hens. M28-M33 (April / Sept 2020).

The database was analyzed to sequence egg isolates with a phenotypic resistance profile of interest. The isolates were sequenced, and the resulting complete sequences were analyzed. A phylogenetic analysis of all sequenced isolates was carried out, and a total of 51 clones were identified on the farm. Within these clones, we kept isolates that belonged to different batches and samplings to understand the transmission dynamics of clonal strains on the farm. In addition, the phylogroup of each isolate was identified, observing a correlation between phylogroups and MLST. Based on phylogenetic distances and clones, mobile genetic elements have been studied for their transmission dynamics. Clonal transmission of resistance genes has been identified, in addition to transmission due to mobile genetic elements.

WP7. Flow of AMR isolates from animals to egg shells

The egg isolates of interest have already been sequenced. By studying phylogenetic distances, 13 of the egg isolates have been found to be clones of *E. coli* isolates isolated from laying hens or pullets. Therefore, clonal transmission also includes eggs. The study of the transmission of resistance genes and mobile genetic elements is not finished, it is being carried out in parallel with the writing of the thesis.

Wp8. Writing of PhD thesis.

In October 2021 the writing of the thesis started. As mentioned above, the writing is done at the same time as some missing analyses, such as the transmission dynamics of moving elements to the eggs.

2.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD01-AMR2-ECO-HEN	D-E14-6.2.	Manuscript	M33	M43		Waiting for editor review.
	D-E14-7.1.	A list of <i>E. coli</i> from eggs to be sequenced	M37	M36		
	D-E14-8.1.	Manuscript	M42	M48		Delayed because we are missing a DNA sequence to finish it.
	D-E14-9.1.	Doctoral thesis draft	M48	M53		Delayed

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD01-AMR2-ECO-HEN	M-E14-3	New sequenced <i>E. coli</i> isolates from animals	M33	Yes		Achieved April 2021
	M-E14-4	New sequenced <i>E. coli</i> isolates from eggs	M37	Yes		Achieved October 2021

2.5. Soft Skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Congress organisation	Scientific congress	05/10/21	UCM
3-minute thesis	Communication	10/06/21	OHEJP
Oral presentation	Communication	08/7/21	SEIMC
Summer School	Learning	26/07 to 06/08/21	OHEJP & Istituto Superiore di Sanità

- Congress organisation: Skills in problem solving, teamwork and decisiveness have been developed. During the organisation of a congress with other colleagues, problems arise, and it is necessary to act to find the best solution and reach an agreement.
- 3MT Thesis and Oral presentation: During these activities the student presents her work to other peers in the sector, developing communication and synthesis skills.
- As mentioned above, the student worked in a group with unfamiliar colleagues, so she had to share and defend her ideas with others, as well as listen and learn from others. This activity made her develop group work skills.

2.6. Publications and patents

Two communications were presented at two different congresses:

- Dynamics of extended spectrum β -lactamase resistance gene *bla_{SHV-12}* in a laying hen commercial farm (Poster presentation in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 of One Health EJP, Hybrid event, 06/09/2019-06/11/2021)
- *Bla_{CMY-2}* gene dynamics in a commercial egg production farm (Oral presentation in XXVII Microbiology Spanish Society National Congress of Microbiology, Online event, 06/28/2021-07/02/2021)

2.7. Impact and Relevance

As mentioned in previous reports, during this twelve-month period (January-December 2021) the PhD project has not been in direct collaboration with external institutes ; nevertheless, the PhD student is in close contact with VISAVET researchers working in other ongoing OneHealthEJP projects like ADONIS, DISCOVER and MATRIX for improving their bioinformatics skills. In addition, the results of the thesis, presented in posters, the on-going-publications and finally in the thesis, can serve to inform other researchers in partner institutes involved.

2.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p>This project is focusing on laying hens. Further details are needed on the researcher's interaction and 'use' of a legal animals (e.g., the layers hens). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so, please comment on any implications for the animal.</p> <p>Please state the 3Rs aspects of this work.</p> <p>Please describe how the animals' welfare are protected and considered (e.g., if the chicken is affected when taking samples, even if the work is dealing with faeces as these types of study can still include restricting the animals or manipulating diets, etc, all which can have an impact on the animals).</p>	<p>To the present moment, all the work has been performed with isolates stored in our laboratory and neither new farm visits nor new environmental sampling have been performed. Consequently, there are no implications for animals regarding health or welfare.</p>

2.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

The written manuscript had been delayed to February 2022 due to impossibility to access the laboratory for weeks (due to several quarantine periods). The doctoral thesis has been delayed from the deadline (according to AWP 2020) of December 2021 to the new proposed deadline of May 2022. The delay is

due to the delay of other tasks, associated with the impossibility to access the laboratory.

2.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	Yes*
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	Yes**
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

*The DTU supervisor, Dr. Valeria Bortolaia is no longer working at DTU. A new DTU supervisor, Dr. Pimlapas Leekitcharoenph is now in charge.

**The PhD co-supervisor Prof. Dr. Alicia Gibello passed away last May, so some rearrangements are in motion.

2.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Not applicable

2.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021 (presentation of a poster and participation in 3MT competition)		
Date:	9 th – 11 th June 2021		
Place:	Online meeting		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No

Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	Digital Innovations for One Health Practitioners		
Date:	15 th -19 th February 2021		
Place:	Online meeting		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No

Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	XXVII Microbiology Spanish Society National Congress of Microbiology		
Date:	6 th - 8 th July 2021		
Place:	Online meeting		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No

Website	<i>No</i>	Other	<i>No</i>
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	<i>No</i>		<i>No</i>
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50+	Media	<i>0</i>
Industry	<i>0</i>	Investors	<i>0</i>
Civil Society	<i>0</i>	Customers	<i>0</i>
General Public	<i>0</i>	Other	<i>0</i>
Policy Makers	<i>0</i>		<i>0</i>

3. PhD02 LIN-RES

3.1. Summary

Linezolid resistance occurrences among faecal samples of poultry, pigs and veal calves and nasal swab samples from pigs (results viewable in previous PhD reports) were reported in a paper published in open access in the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy (<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkab376>). In this paper, we also reported the presence of mutations or genes conferring resistance to linezolid but also the genetic organisation surrounding these genes and the relatedness between (MLST and cgMLST) the animal isolates isolated during the selective monitoring, the human isolates sent by the collaborators from the National Reference Centre-*Staphylococcus aureus* located in Erasme hospital in Brussels and from public databases. The LIN-RES project results were included in the PhD thesis manuscript of Michaël Timmermans entitled « Etude de la résistance aux antibiotiques : développement d'une technique multiplexée de détection de gènes de résistance chez les bactéries Gram-négatives (AMR-ARRAY) et étude de la résistance au linézolide chez les bactéries gram-positives (LIN-RES) », submitted to the university (Université Libre de Bruxelles) in the beginning of August and defended privately in November 2021. The public defence will take place in 2022. Finally, conjugation experiments were completed and the related results were reported in the deliverable (D-PhD02-3.3).

3.2. Overview of project progress

WGS analysis allowed us to identify insertion sequences close to the linezolid resistant genes or in the same contig carrying the linezolid resistant genes (task 2.3). The task 3.1 is completed (genetic organization of the contigs carrying LIN-RES genes as well as incompatibility groups were investigated). Conjugation experiments are also completed (task 3.2) and the related results were reported in the deliverable (D-PhD02-3.3).

A paper has been published in open access in the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy (<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkab376>).

The epidemiological analysis including investigation of putative risk factors related to antibiotic consumptions is in the process of being finalised (further investigations are underway to extend the risk factor analysis).

The public defence of the thesis will take place in 2022.

3.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

All the linezolid resistant isolates collected during the selective monitoring were sequenced by whole genome sequencing (WGS), assembled and analysed. A cgMLST analysis was conducted to study the relatedness of these isolates and compare with published sequenced of linezolid-resistant isolates. Insertion sequences were identified in contigs carrying the linezolid resistant genes. A paper has been published in open access in the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy (<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkab376>). Conjugation experiments are completed.

A study about antibiotic consumption at farm level is in the process of being finalised to look after a potential correlation between linezolid resistant gene occurrences and antibiotic consumption with a special focus on phenicol consumption (as linezolid resistant genes confer also resistance to phenicols).

3.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
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PhD02-AMR2/3/6-PhD LIN-RES	D-E27-2.3	Genetic resistance profiles and subtypes of strains sequenced until M36	M39	M39		
	D-E27-2.4	Results of in silico analysis of genetic scars of horizontal transfer or recombination events	M48	M48		
	D-E27-3.1	Results of in silico analysis of transferability	M39	M39		
	D-E27-3.3	Results of laboratory experiments to demonstrate transferability of linezolid resistance genes	M48	M48	N/A	
	D-E27-4.1	Summary of the risk factors analysis (epidemiological and consumption data)	M54 (delay to M54 was approved)		M54	A delay was approved to enable additional investigations to extend the risk factor analysis.
	D-E27-5.1	Final synthesis and reporting	M54 (delay to M54 was approved)		M54	

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD02-AMR2/3/6-PhD LIN-RES	M-E27-5	Final synthesis and reporting.	M54 (delay to M54 was approved)	No	M54	

3.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Not applicable.

3.6. Publications and patents

A paper has been published in open access in the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy (<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkab376>).

3.7. Impact and Relevance

This project allowed us to strengthen the links with the National Reference Center of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Belgium. It also, through the different presentations in international meetings, raised the awareness of the other countries and inside Belgium about the resistance to linezolid and gave the opportunity to share the scientific expertise between labs. The different conferences organized by the EJP gave the possibility to have a better visibility among the scientific community. The link with the collaborators (ANSES, Veterinair Microbiologisch Diagnostisch Centrum (VMDC) Utrecht University, Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (BfR) have been reinforced through this project and thanks to the Annual Scientific Meeting's.

3.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p>Satisfactory ethics self-assessment</p> <p><u>Human biological samples</u> The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate authorizations will be sought to collect the Human samples.</p> <p><u>Personal data processing</u> The beneficiary must confirm that no personal data will be collected as part of the project; otherwise the GDPR (EU 2016/679) must be applied and the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained must be provided.</p> <p><u>Animal</u> This project is focusing on laying hens. Further details are needed on the researcher's interaction and 'use' of a legal animals (e.g. the layers hens). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so please comment on any implications for the animals. Please describe how the animals' welfare are protected and considered (e.g. if the chickens are affected when taking samples, even if the work is dealing with faeces as these types of study can, this can still include restricting the animals or manipulating</p>	<p>Since we gather a lot of samples through official sampling campaigns, we will finally not need to sample by ourselves animal or human samples.</p> <p>Then, no more ethical issues are linked to the LIN-RES project.</p>

diets, etc., all which can have an impact on the animals). Please provide a statement on the 3Rs aspects of this work If Ethical Approval is required, please state which Research Ethics Committee this will be sent to	
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3.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Not Applicable

3.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

3.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

We work with the FASFC (Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain) and we work with samples of the nationwide antimicrobial resistance surveillance program.

3.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021 - Presentation of a poster and participation in 3MT competition		
Date:	9 – 11 June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	Yes
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

4. PhD03- HME-AMR

4.1. Summary

This project, which focuses on the impact of the presence of heavy metal (in this case zinc) in soil on the resistome both in the soil and foods produced from the land, commenced in February 2021. As reported previously there were significant delays in student recruitment due to COVID-19 related travel restrictions. Elena started in February and work has been progressing well since then. Initial work focused on the preparation of a scoping literature review on the impact of heavy metals on antimicrobial resistance in primary production. All literature searches have been completed on several databases and relevant literature has been selected, reviewed and analysed. The writing process is ongoing and a first draft of the scoping review is almost complete. In addition to this the student has completed several training modules in relation to health and safety, lab practices, manual handling, statistics, presentation and writing skills, database usage and data protection.

The first experimental trial of the project is nearing completion. Field plots were set up in two geographically distinct regions, with zinc added to some plots and not to others at each site. Soil samples were taken at both sites (22 zinc added, 22 no zinc added) and returned to the lab. Each sample was analysed for the presence of Enterobacterales, ESBL-producing Enterobacterales, carbapenamase producing Enterobacterales and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacterales using culture-based SOPs in place in the lab. Presumptive isolates obtained from this sampling were identified by MALDI-TOF. The ones confirmed as Enterobacterales were then tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility by disc diffusion in accordance with EUCAST criteria and phenotypic profiles will be compared with genotypic profiles obtained from whole genome sequencing. Soil samples from each plot were also stored for later DNA extraction for metagenomics analysis.

4.2. Overview of project progress

There was a substantial delay to the commencement of this project due to recruitment issues and the COVID-19 crisis. Elena commenced the project in February 2021. Initial work focused on the preparation of a scoping literature review on the impact of heavy metals on antimicrobial resistance in primary production. The student has also completed several training modules in relation to health and safety, lab practices, manual handling, statistics, presentation and writing skills, database usage and data protection.

Due to the late start of the project and to align with the seasonality of field trials, the first experimental work to be undertaken is in relation to study 3 (D-PhD03-1.2), focused on the impact of heavy metal amendments on AMR in soil. In the initial project description this deliverable was associated with the application of zinc containing pig slurry. However, this trial is now being undertaken in plots where ready to eat food crops will be grown and therefor slurry was not a suitable amendment. Therefore, the zinc was added directly to the soil. This was also deemed more applicable because high level zinc oxide supplementation of pig diets will no longer be permitted in the EU from 2022 and therefore it is expected that the zinc levels present in pig slurry will decrease.

Work is almost complete on this first experimental trial. Field plots were set up in two geographically distinct regions, with zinc added to some plots and not to others at each site. Soil samples were taken at both sites (22 zinc added, 22 no zinc added) and returned to the lab for analysis. Each sample was analysed for the presence of Enterobacterales, ESBL-producing Enterobacterales, carbapenamase producing Enterobacterales and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacterales using culture-based SOPs in place in the lab. Presumptive isolates obtained from this sampling were identified by MALDI-TOF. The Enterobacterales isolates were then tested for their susceptibility to a panel of 14 antimicrobials by disc diffusion in accordance with EUCAST criteria. Whole genome sequencing of the AMR Enterobacterales will be undertaken to provide a genotypic comparison. Soil samples from each plot were also stored for later DNA extraction for metagenomics analysis.

This document is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This Programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830

Sampling for achievement of D-PhD03-1.1 associated with study 1 will commence in the first half of 2022. Initial meetings have taken place with Geological Survey Ireland to identify suitable locations. The analysis to be undertaken will be analogous to that used for study 3 and therefore all SOPs are in place.

4.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

The task titles below are as outlined in the original project description.

Task 1 (Study 1) Comparison of the resistome in low and high metal containing soils

Initial discussions on site selection have taken place with Geological Survey Ireland. Sampling will commence in early 2022. Analytical SOPs are in place.

Task 2 (Study 2) Comparison of the resistome in bovine milk filters from cattle grazing on grass in low and high metal areas

Sampling for this study will follow from site selection for Study 1 and will take place in the summer of 2022. Analytical SOPs are in place. Suitable farms will be selected through consultation with the Teagasc advisory (extension) service.

Task 3 (Study 3) Analysis of the resistome on sites following manure application from pigs with heavy metal included in feed and from pigs with no/minimal heavy metal in feed

As noted above high level zinc oxide supplementation of pig diets will no longer be permitted in the EU from 2022 and therefore it is expected that the zinc levels present in pig slurry will decrease. Due to this and the desire to reduce the variables it was deemed appropriate to focus on the impact of direct zinc amendment and compare soils in paired plots with and without amendment to monitor and changes in the resistome. This also provides the opportunity to monitor changes in AMR organisms present in crops produced in these soils. The deliverable associated with this study is unchanged.

Work on this task is almost finished. Sampling has been completed on two sites (160 samples in total), the presence of Enterobacterales, ESBL-producing Enterobacterales, carbapenamase producing Enterobacterales and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacterales was conducted using culture-based SOPs and confirmed by MALDI-TOF analysis. A total of 23 Enterobacterales were identified and tested for antibiotic susceptibility.

Task 4 (Study 4) Genotypic comparison with antimicrobial resistant Enterobacteriaceae with human, environmental and animal isolates from Irish and EU reference laboratories

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris have suitable banks of isolates from animals and the environment for comparison with isolates obtained as part of this project and will utilise public repositories of sequenced isolates and collaborations with reference laboratories to increase the diversity of isolates for comparison. The selection of strains for comparison will be dependent on the identity of isolates obtained in studies 1, 2 and 3 of this project. This work will commence in late 2022.

4.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD02-AMR2/3/6-PhD LIN-RES	D-PhD03-1.1	Report on AMR bacteria present in soils of differing heavy metal content	M48		M60	Delay in student starting project and rearrangement of study commencement order will delay the first deliverable being achieved.
	D-PhD03-1.2	Report on the impact of the application of heavy metal containing amendments to AMR bacteria in soil	M54		M54	The study linked with this has commenced first and therefore it is currently envisaged that this deliverable will be achieved on time.
	D-PhD03-1.3	Report on AMR bacteria present in milk filters from animals grazing in areas of differing heavy metal content	M59		M66	Delay in student starting project will delay the achievement of this deliverable.

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	1	SOP in place for sampling culture based analysis	M27	Yes	M40	Delayed due to the late recruitment of student but the SOPs for culture based analysis are now in place and have been utilised in the first sampling study undertaken.
	2	Sequences of sufficient quality obtained from metagenomic analysis	M35	No	M48	Delayed due to late recruitment of PhD student

4.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Biosafety Awareness	Health and Safety	23/04/21	Teagasc
Lab risk assessment	Health and Safety	29/04/21	Teagasc
Lab chemical safety awareness	Health and Safety	19/04/21	Teagasc
Lab safety basics	Health and Safety	17/03/21	Teagasc
Manual handling	Health and Safety	08/02/21	Teagasc
Antimicrobial resistance –theory and methods	Relevant to PhD topic	04/02/21	Coursera
Metagenomics applied to surveillance of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance	Relevant to PhD topic	19/02/21	Coursera
Scopus workshop	Database interrogation	24/03/21	NUIG
Present your research with confidence	Presentation skills	24/05/21	Environ 2021
Statistical analysis with R	Statistics	14-17-18/06/21	Teagasc
The Impostor Syndrome	Mental Health	06/07/21	Walsh Scholarships Programme
Health and Safety Briefings	Health and Safety	26/08/21	NUIG
Academic Writing Centre summer workshop	Writing skills	27/08/21	NUIG
Understanding AMR in Water-Webinar	Relevant to PhD topic	28/08/21	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)
General Data Protection Regulation	Data protection online	30/08/21	Teagasc (E-Learning)
Safety Responsibilities for Principal Investigators	Laboratory Safety	30/08/21	NUIG
Safety Responsibilities for Heads of Units	Laboratory Safety	31/08/21	NUIG
Chemical safety training	Laboratory Safety	31/08/21	NUIG
Academic English Writing	Writing skills	21/09 - 23/11 (10 lessons)	NUIG-English Language Centre
Plain English Training	Writing skills	27/09/21	Teagasc-NALA
Mental Health Workshop	Mental Health	28/09/21	Spectrum Life
Gas Cylinders	Health and Safety	15/10/21	Teagasc
AMR Surveillance in The Netherlands (and beyond) from a One Health perspective	Relevant to PhD topic	18/10/21	MetVetNet Association
One Health Annual Conference	Relevant to PhD topic	03-04/10/21	Ryan Institute Centre
Online writing workshop	Writing skills	01/12/21	NUIG-Academic Writing Centre

4.6. Publications and patents

Not applicable yet.

4.7. Impact and Relevance

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris currently collaborate on the Irish EPA funded project AREST which examines antimicrobial resistance in the environment and contribute to One Health orientated AMR research and policy making at a national and international level. This project is highly complementary to those activities and will facilitate an increasing collaborative relationship between the research groups. Dr Burgess has worked previously with Dr Johannessen of the Norwegian Veterinary Institute as part of the HUPLANT Control COST action focusing on microbial food safety issues and this project will further develop this relationship. This project has also led to Dr Burgess forging collaborative linkages with Geological Survey Ireland in relation to heavy metal mapping and with the SFI funded VISTA MILK research centre.

4.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p><u>Biological samples</u> The beneficiary must confirm that no Human and/or Animal samples will be collected for further analysis.</p> <p><u>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects</u> Considering the area of work, the beneficiary must re-confirm that there are no environmental or H&S Aspects.</p>	<p>No human or animal samples will be collected as part of this project.</p> <p>There are no environmental or H&S aspects in relation to this project. All samples and lab work will be undertaken using SOPs in place in the partner institutes and all isolation work will take place in appropriate BSL2 labs.</p>

4.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
All 1	Not given	M69	All	Not given	M66	Recruitment delay	0	133,900

COVID-19 has had a severe impact on recruitment for this project. Prior to the pandemic we reported issues with recruiting a suitable PhD candidate. A suitable candidate was identified in March 2020 and the position offered but failed to secure a visa by October 2020. Another advertising round commenced and another suitable candidate was selected and will start in February 2021. Tighter sampling schedules will be employed to address project delays to date.

4.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No

Other risks (please describe)

No

Additional information:

As outlined there has been a significant delay to the project start and associated delay in work plan execution and reporting. Nonetheless, Dr Burgess and Prof Morris believe the project remains achievable with the right candidate and slightly tighter timelines. This has been made possible through collaboration with other relevant projects as outlined in Section 11.

4.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

An Initial meeting has taken place with Geological Survey Ireland and through collaboration with the Tellus survey (<https://www.gsi.ie/en-ie/programmes-and-projects/tellus/Pages/default.aspx>) this will enable suitable high and low metal content soils across Ireland for resistome analysis as part of study 1 and farms for selection as part of study 2. A follow up meeting is scheduled for February 2022.

As part of Study 3 we have collaborated with a nationally funded project which is focused on the impact of different soil amendments on cadmium uptake in food crops. We focused on plots where zinc has been applied and use the corresponding control (no amendment) plots for comparison.

This project is complementary to the EPA funded AREST project (<https://www.nuigalway.ie/medicine-nursing-and-health-sciences/medicine/disciplines/bacteriology/research/arest/>) which is examining antimicrobial resistance in the environment. Prof Morris is the coordinator of this project and Dr Burgess is a participant. The culture-based methodologies being employed in AREST will be particularly relevant for HME-AMR. The student will have the opportunity to collaborate with these colleagues for methodologies and isolate characterisation.

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris both contribute to Ireland's National Action Plan for Antimicrobial Resistance which has recently been updated and the results of this project will contribute to achieving the objectives of that plan.

HME-AMR is complementary to an ongoing PhD project in Dr Burgess' group focusing on the impact of zinc oxide supplementation on the porcine resistome which will facilitate a smooth transition for the HME-AMR student in relation to methodologies and analysis.

HME-AMR is complementary to a project led by Dr Orla O'Sullivan as part of the SFI funded VistaMilk project (<https://vistamilk.ie/>) which is examining the soil resistome in different sites across Ireland. Dr Burgess and Dr O'Sullivan will collaborate to ensure synergy of the projects and avoid duplication.

4.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021 Presentation of a poster and 3-minute thesis		
Date:	June 9-11 2021		
Place:	Copenhagen/online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

5. PhD04- KENTUCKY

5.1. Summary

Salmonella enterica serovar Kentucky (*S. Kentucky*) is a common causative agent of gastroenteritis in humans. It is one of most notorious *Salmonella* serotypes, as it is strongly associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Ciprofloxacin-resistant *S. Kentucky* is able to gain additional antibiotic resistance determinants through the acquisition of locally circulating plasmid-borne ESBL, AmpC and/or carbapenemase genes. Most recently, the situation has worsened, as ECDC launched an Urgent Inquiry (UI-464) on a CIPR *S. Kentucky* ST198 strain carrying a chromosomally integrated blaCTX-M-14b gene encoding for cephalosporin resistance. The insertion event was traced back to Malta, but the strain has already spread to Belgium, UK and five other EU countries. In this PhD project, we will investigate (i) what explains the evolutionary success of the multidrug resistant *S. Kentucky* ST198 clone, and (ii) what is the mechanisms of the integration (and potential further transfer) of the ESBL gene in its chromosome.

In the second year of the PhD research, we continued the investigation of the IncHI-type, mega-plasmid carrying the ISECP1-blaCTX-M-14B transposition unit. Due to its clinical significance, the plasmid was chosen as a focal point for our fluorescent tagging strategy. Yet, wet-lab experiments backed with *in silico* analysis indicated that the plasmid is non-conjugable, most probably due to truncation in the transfer region. Thus, we reasoned to shift to the prototype IncHI1 plasmid (R27), a self-transmissible plasmid with fully characterized conjugation machinery (Craig et al., 2000) and is capable of transfer between members of the Enterobacteriaceae.

The transposition mechanism of ISECP1 is obscure so we decided to develop fluorescent reporters based on the partitioning system parS/ParB to differentially label the pR27 backbone and the ISEcp1-blaCTX-M-14b unit. parS is a cis-acting centromere-like sequence to which a partitioning protein ParB selectively binds. Two alternative partitioning systems were instigated namely, P1 Phage-derived and *Lactococcus lactis*-derived parS/ParB. The later system has minimal interference with DNA replication. Yet, the system is derived from gram-positive bacteria and needs to be optimized to a gram-negative host.

First, we labeled the pR27 backbone with a P1-parS sequence. Next, we tagged ISECP1-blaCTX-M-14B transposition with *lactis*-parS sequence *in vitro*, followed by cloning the assembled unit into pR27. The construct was confirmed by sequencing. Then we codon-optimized *lactis*-parB protein according to *Salmonella* codon usage and fused the optimized-parB to msf-GFP under an IPTG inducible promoter. We tagged optimized parB at the N- terminus and C- terminus with both flexible and rigid linkers. Yet we failed to obtain localized foci *in vivo*.

We decided to move to alternative fluorescent reports based on P1/ pMT partitioning system (Nielsen et al., 2006). In parallel, the *in vitro*- mating assays of pR27 indicated a conjugation efficiency of 10⁻⁵-10⁻⁶ at 25C which is challenging to study under time-lapse fluorescent microscopy. Thus, we replaced the conjugation repressor htdA with pMT parS sequence to obtain a 2-log increase in the conjugation efficiency (Whelan et al., 1994). Next, we *in vitro*-labeled the ISECP1-blaCTX-M-14B transposition with P1-parS sequence and cloned it into pR27. Currently, we are optimizing the cognate parB proteins.

5.2. Overview of project progress

The PhD is going according to schedule, although the project start suffered from the Covid-19 crisis. Due to direct consequences of the pandemic, the original candidate (Jasper Van der Peet) had to return permanently to The Netherlands in M28. He was replaced by Alaa Albasiony, who will pick up activities in M32. The transition between both candidates was smooth with two of the five deliverables (D-PhD04-1.1 and D-PhD04-1.2) completed. However, a necessary visit to INRAE (MedVet travel grant obtained) is still postponed to 2022. This academic year, Alaa is taking courses in omics and bioinformatics, and supervises a master thesis in bioinformatics (Biancamaria Florenzi, KULeuven), who is perform the database mining described below.

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5.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Insertion of P1-parS and lactis-parS labelled transposition unit into pR27

pKD46, a plasmid with temperature-sensitive replicon, encoding lambda Red recombinases was electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT strain. Next, pR27 was conjugated by filter mating to MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46. In short, cultures of the donor (*E. coli*, pR27) and recipient strains (MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46) were grown in LB supplemented with the required antibiotics at 25°C in static conditions for 16 h. Cells were washed with 0.1M MgSO₄ to eliminate the antibiotics. The recipient strain suspension (0.4 ml) and donor strain suspension (0.1 ml) were mixed on a 0.22 μm membrane and incubated at 25°C for 2 h. Serial dilutions were plated in appropriate media to select for trans-conjugants (MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27).

P1-parS was then PCR amplified as P1-parS- frt-cat-frt fragment and electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27 to be inserted in an intergenic region on pR27 backbone via lambda red recombineering (Datsenko et al; 2000). Next, we flipped the chloramphenicol cassette using pCP20, a plasmid encoding Flp recombinase.

To label the ISEcp1-bla CTX-M-14b unit with *Lactococcus lactis*-derived parS, we PCR amplified the unit as two fragments with the 18bp parS sequence as an overhang (GGGGCTAAATTTAGCCCC). The two fragments were then assembled *in vitro* by gibson assembly and inserted into pR27 backbone by homologous recombination (Datsenko et al; 2000). The 18bp parS sequence was inserted downstream the terminator region of the ISEcp1 gene and upstream the promoter region of bla CTX-M-14b gene. We then confirmed the insertion of P1 and *Lactococcus lactis*-derived parS together with the conservation of the ISEcp1, bla CTX-M-14b genes by sequencing.

Optimizing P1-ParB and Lactis-ParB Proteins

First, we separately inserted by recombineering the two parS sequences into the chromosomes of MA8508ΔpSLT to serve as a positive control for fluorescent microscopy. Next, we transformed the MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with P1-parS and lactis-parS with pALA2705 and pMK17-01 respectively. pALA2705 plasmid encodes P1-parB N-terminally fused to mCherry whereas pMK17-01 encodes lactis-parB C-terminally fused to msfGFP. Time-lapse microscopy experiments showed only localized foci with P1-parB-mCherry, indicating that lactis-parB failed to bind its cognate parS sequence.

Thus, we reasoned to codon optimize the lactis-parB protein to a gram-negative host using the genescriptTM platform. Then the codon-optimized lactis-parB protein was then cloned into a variant of pALA2705 encoding GFP to obtain pALA2706 (lactis-parB N-terminally fused to GFP). pALA2706 was then transformed into MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with lactis-parS. Microscopy experiment showed again diffused fluorescence. We thought to change the fusion type into C-terminal fusion and try different linkers. In short, pALA2706 was PCR linearized to remove GFP- lactis-ParB. Then msfGFP and lactis-ParB were PCR amplified, assembled *in vitro* to produce lactis-parB C-terminally fused to msfGFP with two different linkers (SSSRGSGGEAAKAGS, (SGGGG)₄), and ligated back to PCR-linearized pALA2706 by gibson assembly. The two variants of the plasmid were then separately transformed to MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with lactis-parS. yet we failed to obtain localized foci.

The inability of lactis ParB to bind its cognate parS sequence *in vivo* may be attributed to improper folding in gram-negative host despite being codon-optimized. It is also possible that parB fail to oligomerize upon binding, so we don't observe the localized focus over the background diffused fluorescence. Moreover, in *E. coli*, the integration host factors (IHF) bind specific sequence on P1-parS and facilitate the binding of P1-parB to P1-parS (Barbara Funnel., 1991) and since lactis-parS does not carry an IHF-binding sequence it might have failed to attract the partitioning machinery.

Construction of a reporter plasmid based on P1, pMT parS/ ParB partition system

pMT parS was PCR amplified as pMT-parS- frt-cat-frt fragment and the fragment was electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27 to replace htdA gene. HtdA is involved in the repression of four tra operons and has a pivotal role in the growth phase dependency of R27 conjugation. *In vitro* conjugation assay has shown a 2-log increase in the conjugation efficiency of pR27, htdA mutant as compared to the wild-type. We then labelled the transposition unit with P1-parS as previously described followed by electroporation into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27(pMT-labelled, ΔhtdA). We are currently optimizing the cognate parB proteins and if the system were to be orthogonal as per the literature (Nielsen et al., 2006), we will assemble the P1-parB and pMT-ParB with the fluorescent markers into a chromosomal operon under the control of Ptet inducible promoter to avoid ectopic expression from the plasmid.

Abundance of insertion sequences and AMR genes

A dataset of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* assemblies at the contig level has been downloaded from the public database 'NCBI Assemblies'. To investigate the presence of associations between IS elements and AMR genes in the dataset, detection of antimicrobial resistance has been carried out through ResFinder, detection of IS elements through ISEScan, detection of replicons through PlasmidFinder and prediction of the origin for each contig with the machine learning program RFPlasmid.

By comparing the coordinates on the contigs of the detected elements, distances between IS and AMR genes have been calculated as the number of bp between the end of one element and the start of the other and stored in python data frames. This process has been done by measuring the number of associations that would be present in the dataset for each of the most common IS families when considering different thresholds. The value chosen was 10,000 bp, as it would allow to capture a good number of IS6 associations without overestimating the number of associations for any of the other relevant IS families.

The number of associations in the dataset was thus approximately 30,000 on 4,325 samples, the large majority of which were located on a contig that was predicted to be plasmid-derived. The IS family that presented the highest number of associations with different AMR types was IS6, which was particularly associated with aminoglycosides and beta-lactams, followed by IS91, IS1380 and IS5.

Considering specifically beta-lactamases, the IS family that is most often associated with genes of this class of resistance was IS1182, followed by IS21, IS1380 and IS6. In particular, the genes blaCTX-M-15, blaCTX-M-3, blaKPC.3 seem to be often found close to many of the IS families present in the dataset.

The IS1380 family can be found close to the following beta-lactam resistance genes, blaCTX-M-15, blaCTX-M-132, blaCTX-M-3, blaCTX-M-36, and blaKPC-2. Among these, the CTX-M-15 gene is by far the most relevant in terms of number of associations, most of which are found on plasmid-derived contigs.

The ISEcp1 element belongs to the IS1380 family of insertion sequence and indeed is one of the most important elements that mobilise blaCTX-M-15 genes (Hamamoto et al., 2020). In this context, ISEcp1 is included between a IRL and a IRR sequence and is found upstream of the blaCTX-M-15 gene. It can mobilise its downstream region with variable lengths, creating a transposition unit through the

recognition of the IRL and the IRR, or an alternative IRR (IRRalt) (Hamamoto et al., 2020). This transposition is called a one-ended transposition (Poirel, Decousser and Nordmann, 2005). Interestingly, ISecp1 is known to also provide a promoter sequence to different AMR genes in its right side (Poirel, Decousser and Nordmann, 2003).

These results combined, provide a detailed look into the mobilizing capacity of IS elements and AMR genes. In the next year, we will continue to show this mobilization using the constructed fluorescently marked reporter strains.

5.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
	D-PhD04-1.2	Construction of reporter strain, able to show transfer of ESBL gene between plasmid and chromosome	M42	M47		https://zenodo.org/deposit/5794246 Public.
	D-PhD04-1.3	Peer-reviewed paper on the database search on the abundance of transferable AMR genes in public databases	M48		M52	Literature survey is ongoing
	D-PhD04-1.4	Peer-reviewed paper on the molecular mechanisms behind the hopping of AMR elements	M54			
	D-PhD04-1.5	PhD dissertation finalised	M60			

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD04-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY	M4	Finalization of characterization of MGEs and selection of elements for further study at KULeuven	M46	No	M50	Small delay caused by the pandemic.

5.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
OMICS techniques and data analysis	Lab skills / Bioinformatics	01/02/2021 – 30/06/2021 (ongoing)	KULeuven
Exploitation of research - knowledge & technology transfer	IP skills	Planned for 2021 (Q4)	KULeuven
Academic English: presentation and seminar skills	Language course	Planned for 2022	KULeuven

5.6. Publications and patents

Albasiony, A., Ceysens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2021) Exploring the ISECP-1 mediated chromosomal integration of blaCTX-M-14 in *Salmonella* Kentucky. Annual Scientific Meeting OHEJP, June 9-11th, 2021. Poster presentation.

5.7. Impact and Relevance

The Kentucky project units Sciensano, INRAE and Laboratory of Food Microbiology of KULEUVEN (BEL), which clearly have complementary expertise. Sciensano holds the National Reference laboratory of *Salmonella*, and has experience in short-and long read sequencing. Prof. Abram Aertsen's group uses analytical genetics and live (single-)cell biology approaches to study the spread, establishment and adaptive phenotypic impact of mobile genetic elements. Benoît Doublet and his team have long-term expertise in plasmid biology and will study the transfer dynamics of these elements. It is clear these groups, which have never collaborated before, will greatly learn from each other and will exchange knowledge, strains and experiences along the way. The final goal is to improve our methodologies and understanding of transfer dynamics of these mobile elements, and its impact on antimicrobial resistance.

5.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<u>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects</u> The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.	I confirm that the PhD candidate has followed the necessary training in quality and biosafety to perform his work.

5.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
								See information below

Comments:

1. Due to consequences of the Covid-19 crisis, the original candidate (Jasper Van der Peet) had to return permanently to The Netherlands in M28. He was replaced by Alaa Albasiony who picked up activities in M32. This caused an inevitable delay in lab progress, although all objectives of the Kentucky project remain in reach.
2. The Kentucky project only foresees budget for personnel cost, so the budgetary impact is limited. If the program will be extended with two months to compensate for the lab closures (during Y3), we would need a budgetary injection of €6.000 to pay the salary of the PhD candidate.

5.10. List of critical risk

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	Yes (see above)
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

The planned research visit to INRAE (M32) is still uncertain at this time, although crucial for build-up of expertise in conjugation and plasmid transfer methodology. Hopefully this visit can be planned in 2022.

5.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Long-read sequencing was performed according to methodology derived from the Full Force project (JRP-14). No interactions with OHEJP stakeholders were made in this stage of the project.

5.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021		
Date:	9 -11 th June 2021		
Place:	Online and Copenhagen		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	Yes
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	10	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	10		

6. PhD05- METAPRO

6.1. Summary

During 2021, we managed to overcome a little bit the COVID-19 situation and started making substantial progress on our tasks. We have been able to advance on the sampling process and we also achieved a strong bioinformatic pipeline that renders interesting results. The first part of the year has been mainly focused on the metagenomic analysis of the data from our own database, which offered interesting results that are guiding and shaping the next steps of the project. In addition, sequencing from the samples collected as part of this project has been performed and analysis is currently in process. We have been able to detect the main plazomicin resistant determinants, the 16S rRNA methyltransferases, from samples of very different origins. Furthermore, we also accomplished to determine their genetic surroundings, which is giving us hints of which bacteria may act as reservoir of these important resistance determinants. Therefore, this has led us to make some changes on some of the milestones of this project and in our workflow to be able to isolate these bacterial strains that are being the reservoir of the plazomicin resistance genes. However, there are still a lot of analyses ongoing and more COVID problems to overcome, but we are working hard to keep the track and end the project on the proposed dates.

6.2. Overview of project progress

- Spanish sampling design: since at the beginning we had some difficulties with the pandemic situation we had difficulties accessing sampling points, a metagenomic analysis of the data of previous projects from the lab was performed. In addition, samples from different ecological niches are already collected and we have established contact with other potential sampling points.
- Spanish sampling execution: samples from pig and poultry farms have been obtained and sampling for the rest of the ecological niches are undergoing.
- Metagenome sequencing of the Spanish sampling: sequencing of some of the samples has been performed and from the rest is currently being performed.
- Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling: we are making a slight change in this task. We are no longer looking for just Enterobacteria, but we are aiming to isolate and culture the bacteria that act as a reservoir of the acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases.
- Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the Spanish sampling: we started some of the analysis using metagenomic data obtained in previous projects from the lab. We tested part of our pipeline and we were able to detect already acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferases with our read-based approach. Assembly-based approach is also giving us hints of where are these resistance mechanisms maintained in the different niches. Analysis from the sequence data of poultry and pig farms is being performed.
- Sampling design in the United Kingdom: contact with our UK partners has been established to discuss timeline and sampling possibilities.
- UK Sampling execution: this task is not due to take place until next year.
- Metagenome sequencing of the UK sampling: this task is not due to take place until next year.
- Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the UK sampling: this task is not due to take place until next year.

- Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the UK sampling: this task is not due to take place until next year.
- Writing of a guideline for early detection of plazomicin resistance determinants to preserve plazomicin for human clinical use: this task is not due to take place until June 2022.
- Writing of the Thesis manuscript: this task is not due to take place until June 2022.
- Thesis defence: this task is not due to take place until February 2023.

6.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

During this year we continued with the metagenomic analysis of the data of pig and poultry farms from Spain belonging to previous projects. With a full metagenomic analysis we were able to detect 16S rRNA methyltransferases in a low prevalence in both types of farms using a read based approach. The 16S rRNA methyltransferase-positive samples were analysed as well with an assembly approach to study the potential genetic environment of the methyltransferases. It suggested that the Order Eubacterium may play a role in the maintenance of these resistance determinants. At present, we are extending this analysis to samples from pig and poultry farms across Europe to enlarge our dataset. We are also including human metagenomic data accessible via SRA to compare if we can detect 16S rRNA methyltransferases.

Since our metagenomic analysis suggest that the prevalence of 16S rRNA methyltransferases is low and associated to the Order Eubacterium, it is possible that in many samples we will not obtain enterobacteria via culturing. Therefore, we changed the milestone 4 (“Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling”) to look for all the bacteria that may act as reservoirs of the plazomicin resistance. Currently, we are testing different culture media to isolate potential plazomicin resistant bacteria and proceed with their Whole Genome Sequencing to identify more accurately the genetic environment of the methyltransferases.

In addition, we were able to collect samples from a few different ecological niches. Some of them have been already sequenced and analyses of them will follow.

6.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved : Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD05-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO	D-PhD05-4.1	Sampling questionnaire	Jan 2021	April 2021		https://zenodo.org/record/4662681#.YMxl7JMzb0p

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD05-AMR2/6.1/	M3	Metagenome sequencing of	MAR 2021	Partially	2022	We sequenced

ET5-METAPRO		the first sampling				the first samples collected and sequencing the others that we are still collecting
	M4	Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling	MAR 2021	No	2022	We made an adjustment to this milestone, so we are not longer for enterobacteria but we are looking for the bacteria that act as reservoir of plazomicin resistance determinants
	M5	Design of the second sampling	JUN 2021	No		Ongoing
	M6	Second sampling execution	SEP 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task
	M7	Metagenome sequencing of the second sampling	DEC 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task
	M8	Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the second sampling	DEC 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task
	M9	Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the first sampling	DEC 2021	No		We expect to start in 2022 with this task

6.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
MicroMundo Symposium	AMR	27-28 th /04/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Webinar Series 'Jornadas sobre la Carrera Investigadora'	Scientific Research	14 th /01/2021 – 29 th /04/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Course 'Hojas de Cálculo con Excel I'	Excel	15 th /03/2021 – 30 th /06/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course 'Hojas de Cálculo con Excel II'	Excel	14 th /06/2021 – 29 th /10/2021	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Workshop 'Bioinformatics tools and methods for antimicrobial resistance'	AMR	15 th /10/2021	PH4GE, JPIAMR and CLIMB-BIG-DATA
BioinfoCAM meeting	Bioinformatics	21 st /10/2021	SEBiBC

6.6. Publications and patents

Not applicable.

6.7. Impact and Relevance

This PhD project connects three major laboratories focused on the fight of Antimicrobial Resistance, having all of them participated in other European Projects in the past. This offers a possibility to maintain the great relationship that has been always present between institutes. This fact is highlighted by the various exchanges of students that have had part and how successful they have been. In addition, since the PhD project supervisors study AMR from different perspectives, this new collaboration brings the opportunity to combine them all together to get the most out of it. But it is not only limited to that. Being part of the EJP networks allows to connect the partners and the student with different backgrounds and perspectives that are often needed.

6.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

6.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay

Comments: None.

6.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No

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Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

Due to a late incorporation of the candidate and the COVID-19 crisis the PhD project start date had to be postponed and the work plan has been also compressed. Any other special situation not predicted could cause a major delay in the work plan execution.

6.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

- **FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests** (<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/jrp-farmed/>). Since the objectives and the techniques of both projects are similar, the candidate is taking part actively in the tasks performed at UCM associated to this project.
- **EFFORT: Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission** (<http://www.effort-against-amr.eu/>). The group participated actively in the EFFORT project and its activities and resources are the foundation of the present research project.
- **JPIAMR: Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance**. The lab is part of the NEAR-AMR (<https://www.jpiamr.eu/near-amr/>) and of the GAP-ONE (<https://www.jpiamr.eu/gap-one/>) projects. The candidate can benefit of these networks to extend the search of plazomicin resistance determinants in other parts of Europe and Africa or to estimate the economic burden of plazomicin resistance.
- **AVANT: Alternatives to Veterinary Antimicrobials** (<https://avant-project.eu/>). The student will also be involved in the development and test of alternatives to antimicrobials.
- **DAMR-Una Europa: "Disseminate antimicrobial resistance knowledge and the use of whole genome sequencing on relevant bacterial pathogens during COVID-19 world emergency"** (<https://www.una-europa.eu/>). The student is taking part in this project teaching a webinar on metagenomics and collaborating on the sequencing of bacterial pathogens.

6.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021. Presentation of a poster and participation in 3MT competition.
Date:	9 th - 11 th June 2021
Place:	Online and Copenhagen

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	Seminar presentation 'Identificación y caracterización molecular de mecanismos de resistencia a antibióticos emergentes'
Date:	12 th May 2021
Place:	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories	
	Yes / No
	Yes / No

Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	31 st European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID) - Poster Presentation		
Date:	9 th - 12 th July 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No

Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	14000+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	XXVIII Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Microbiología (SEM) - Poster presentation		
Date:	28 th June - 2 nd July 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No

Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	900+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

7. PhD06- PEMbO

7.1. Summary

WP1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups (M31-M48)

Since the last report, Ciriac has modified the bacterial genomic DNA extraction protocol which has enabled him to obtain DNA of sufficient quantity and quality to perform 3rd generation sequencing of 10 *Mycobacterium bovis* (*M. bovis*) strains with the MinION (Nanopore) technology available in his laboratory. Two of them have also been sequenced with PacBio technology in Genoscreen platform and were used to compare the quality of the genome sequences obtained with these two sequencing techniques. The 10 strains were also sequenced with the Illumina technology in Genoscreen that provide high fidelity DNA sequencing data but on short reads. Using long read -MinION's data- de novo assembly and short reads -Illumina's data- for genome correction, Ciriac tested several assembly strategies and chose the best one to obtain the new complete genomes.

WP2: Genome sequence analysis (M39-M54)

IS6110 is an insertion sequence of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex, to which *M. bovis* belongs, with an important role in genome plasticity and in the bacterium evolution caused by IS6110 transposition.

In the previous report we showed that IS6110 is present in multiple copies in endemic French *M. bovis* groups and could lead to phenotypic changes that explain their epidemiologic success. Since the last report, we have found out that some IS6110 interrupt or could regulate (via its strong promoter) some genes involved in virulence, host persistence or environmental stress resistance. The insertion positions seem stable in French endemic *M. bovis* groups over time and independently of the affected animal species.

Description of these new complete genomes were performed and focus on specific genomic characteristics:

- Annotation and pangenomic study
- Single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) matrix

- List of SNP in virulence genes
- Confirmation of IS6110 copy number and their localisation
- List of interrupted coding sequences
- List of Regions of Difference (RD)

Ciriac currently refines the RD list using a larger panel of *M. bovis* short read sequences which represents the French *M. bovis* diversity. These results will help us to better define the French clonal group.

With these results, Ciriac is currently defining genetic targets explaining differential phenotypical characteristics of the different *M. bovis* groups. These targets will be tested in WP3.

WP3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies (M40-M50)

To perform this WP, strains were selected and cultivated. Given that our biosafety level 3 laboratory (BSL 3) is currently unavailable (From December) until February 2022, this WP will have an alteration to the deadline (begin in M50 instead of M40 and should end in M60).

WP4: Valorisation and dissemination of results (M37-M56)

The draft of the first article on IS6110 results is finished, and currently under modification for very soon submission for publication.

New complete genomes will be published in early 2022. An article about the obtention and description of these genomes is currently ongoing and planned to be submitted at the first semester 2022.

Ciriac did his second thesis project steering committee.

Poster presentation on IS6110 study:

- Annual Scientific Meeting One Health European Joint Program 2021 (ASMOHEJP2021).
- Société Française de Microbiologie 2021 (SFM 2021).
- Journées Scientifiques et Doctorales de l'Anses 2021 (JSDA 2021) → best poster presentation award.

Oral presentation on IS6110 study:

- ABIES doctoral days 2021.

Poster presentation on obtaining reference genomes:

- ASMOHEJP2021.

Oral presentation on obtaining reference genomes:

- Scientific Happy Hours (unit meeting).

Scientific events:

- “Ma these en 180 secondes”. Three Minute Thesis Competition (3MT) organised by student's university.
- 3MT organised during ASMOHEJP2021.
- Doc'Avenir 2021. Speech competition organised by doctoral school→ first prize of the public and second prize of the jury.

7.2. Overview of project progress

WP1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups

Task-1.2: Sequencing and *de novo* assembly (M27-M41)

Strains presenting ten different genotypes were sequenced in MinION (Nanopore) and Illumina technology. Two of these strains were also sequenced at Genoscreen, Lille, with the PacBio technology. We performed a comparison of the results obtained by using different assemblers for a same genotype and selected the most accurate one.

De novo assemblies were performed with the best tools.

Comparison between PacBio and MinION sequencing is ongoing.

This task was delayed because of COVID-19 crisis, lockdown and technical problem in WP1 task 1-1

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(programmed for M37 but being finished in M41). Most of the objectives of this task are accomplished. The comparison between the two sequencing technologies is ongoing but is not crucial for the other WP.

WP2: Genome sequence analysis

Task-2.1: Sequencing of supplementary strains (M38-M41)

This task was finally accomplished given that the totality of strains could be sequenced by the MinION-Nanopore technology.

Strains of 3 important French *M. bovis* genotypes (F7, SB0120-CO and SB0120-DHV genotypes) already sequenced in other studies of our team will be used in other tasks.

This task is done.

Task-2.2: Genomic markers analysis (M33-M44)

IS6110 insertion site in French *M. bovis* diversity described in the last report were manually checked with Integrative Genomics Viewer using the bam file generated by ISMapper and confirmed with new complete genomes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. IS6110 occurrence in *M. bovis* French genetic diversity.

Heatmap showing the presence and genomic position of IS6110 copies in genomes of French strains. The evolutionary tree was inferred on Mega by using the Maximum Likelihood based on 8981 whole genome single nucleotide polymorphism (wgSNP) of 81 genomes (80 genomes of *M. bovis* representing French diversity and Mb3601 reference strains). The tree is drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site. The strains are grouped in 7 clusters which have been previously defined.

Gene ontology analysis was performed on the genes upstream and downstream of IS6110 insertion position.

Evolution of IS6110 insertion positions and number of copies over time and in different host species was investigated in the 3 most important *M. bovis* groups (SB0120-CO, SB0120-DHV and F7) (Figure 2 for SB0120-CO). For these analyses we used genomes previously obtained with the Illumina technology for other research projects of Anses team.

IS6110 position found in SB0120-CO strains can be confirmed and precisely determined (Figure 2) with the use of the reference genome Mb3601. The interruption and possible up or down regulation of important genes were also be analysed.

Figure 2. IS6110 in *M. bovis* SB0120-CO over the time and between different host species.

Heatmap showing the presence or absence of IS6110 in parasymphatric SB0120-CO strains. *M. bovis* strains are presented by year of isolation. Illumina reads are mapped in Mb3601 reference genome which is shown in purple. Black squares show the presence of IS6110 in a specific site. The last line of the figure presents the different host species of these SB0120-CO strains (cattle in green, badger in blue, wildboar in yellow and fox in orange).

Confirmation of IS6110 insertion site in F7 and SB0120-DHV main genomes panel is ongoing.

Whole genome SNP on the new reference genomes and a list of SNP in virulence genes are ongoing. Genome annotation and pangenomic study on these new complete genomes was done. Comparison of complete genome genomic structure was done with Mauve.

The list of interrupted coding sequence in new genomes was done.

Selection of interesting molecular target who could have an important role in bacterial virulence and growth is ongoing.

The list of regions of difference between the complete genomes was done.

In vitro confirmation of some regions of difference was performed to validate our method.

The list of difference regions is being refined by mapping the genome sequenced with Illumina technology onto our new reference genomes. This objective is ongoing.

WP3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies

Task-3.1: Protein profiles determination (M40-M49)

Task-3.2: Lipidomic analyses (M40-M49)

A confirmation of first *in silico* results will be reinforced with *in vitro* studies.

In vitro growth rates in laboratory conditions of the 10 genotypes during WP1 is a trait that we have observed as being differential among the strains. We will perform appropriate growth kinetics analysis to better study this differential phenotypic trait.

Proper biochemical and lipidomic assays are being currently being defined to be performed in the first trimester of 2022.

WP4: Valorisation and dissemination of results (M37-M56)

Task-4.1: Publication of results (M44 and M53)

The first article on IS6110 in French *M. bovis* diversity is well underway.

Writing of the second article has already started, with the objective of submission for publication in the

first semester of 2022. The aim of this article is the description of 10 new *M. bovis* reference genome. These complete genomes are closer to French field strains than the previous reference genome for *M. bovis* (Af2122/97). They are representative of the main French genotypes and allow a better description of these genotypes, especially for the large genetic events that cannot be described in genome sequenced with short read sequencing. A comparison between the new complete genomes will be done in this article and could be useful to explain the success of several *M. bovis* genotypes in France.

A short communication on the diversity of the Direct Repeat region and CRISPR Cas locus of French *M. bovis* is planned. This communication is currently being drafted.

Publication of new complete genomes will be done in the first trimester of 2022.

Task-4.2: Communication (M36-M56)

Ciriac's second thesis project steering committee.

Oral communication at ABIES doctoral days 2021.

Posters presentation at ASMOEHP2021 (2 posters).

Participation in the 6th edition of "ma thèse en 180 secondes".

Oral communication during unit meeting Scientific Happy Hours.

Speech competition at Doc'Avenir event (1st prize of public and 2nd prize of the jury).

Poster presentation at French Society of Microbiology 2021.

Poster presentation at Scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021 (Best poster presentation prize).

Task-4.3: PhD manuscript writing (M36-M56)

This task was started in M28 mainly by writing the thesis' introduction during the first French sanitary containment. Ciriac will continue to write his manuscript and finish it by M51.

7.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups

Task-1.2: Sequencing and de novo assembly (M27-M41)

M. bovis strains were sequenced using MinION sequencing at ANSES.

M. bovis strains were sequenced using PacBio and Illumina sequencing at Genoscreen (Lille France).

Ciriac compared several assembly strategies to obtain new reference genomes by *de novo* assembly.

Ten strains' assembly with *de novo* assembly was performed.

Comparison between PacBio and MinION sequencing is ongoing.

WP2: Genome sequence analysis

Task-2.1: Sequencing of supplementary strains (M38-M41)

Three genomes were added to the initial list of 7 *M. bovis* genomes. These genomes were sequenced with MinION and Illumina sequencing technologies.

Task-2.2: Genomic markers analysis (M33-M44)

Analyses of insertion sites of IS6110 in French *M. bovis* diversity show that more than a third of our sample are IS6110 multi-copy and 10% have more than 6 copy (Figure1).

These strains with the highest IS6110 abundance are those circulating in the most bTB prevalent regions and are defined by a specific node in the phylogenetic tree (Figure1).

IS6110 copy numbers is correlated with clonal group definition (Figure1).

Cluster A/F4 family strains is also an endemic group and their strains are IS6110 multicopy.

A list of gene interrupted or possible up regulated by IS6110 was established.

Gene ontology analysis show that IS6110 insertions sites are often found in the environment of genes implied in "replication, recombination, and repair".

SB0120-CO strains have a strong stability of the IS6110 copy number and high recurrence of their genomic position over the time.

These traits are conserved independently of the affected animal species.
The same stability was shown in two other genotypes named F7 and SB0120-DHV.

IS6110 position of SB0120-CO genomes were confirmed with Mb3601 reference genomes.
Confirmation of IS6110 position of SB0120-DHV and F7 genomes with the new complete genomes is ongoing.

Annotation of new reference genomes was done.

Pangenomic study on them shows a high core genes similarity (3922/4046).

The list of 2213 SNPs has been established between the 10 new genomes and Mb3601. Eighty six percent of them are intragenic and suggest that these SNPs could have phenotypical consequence. The list of SNP in genes playing an essential role in virulence is ongoing.

Mauve analysis showed high genomic structure conservation but also region of differences among the new complete genome.

The list of interrupted coding sequence in new genomes was done. This list is in agreement with the previous results and shows 31 interrupted coding sequences specific to each genome on average and in comparison with Mb3601. However, the selection of interesting molecular targets for phenotypic analyses is ongoing.

The list of regions of difference showed 25 regions of difference with more than 1000 nucleotides, 107 with more than 100 nucleotides and 253 with more than 10 nucleotides.

Some regions were confirmed with *in vitro* studies and allow to validate the method.

Ciriatic currently refines the Region of Difference list using a larger panel of *M. bovis* short read sequences which represents the French *M. bovis* diversity. Some of these Regions of Difference appear to belong to *M. bovis* specific groups and could be used to better describe a group or subgroup of *M. bovis*.

WP3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies

Task-3.1: Protein profiles determination (M40-M49)

Task-3.2: Lipidomic analyses (M40-M49)

Field strains of interest were selected.

A good bacterial concentration in liquid culture of each clone was obtained.

Tasks 3.1 and 3.2 were postponed due to the impossibility to use BSL 3 laboratory until M50. An appropriate *in vitro* test according to the results of the *in silico* analyses are being assessed to be performed in the first trimester of 2022.

Other phenotypic trait studies are also planned when the BSL 3 lab will be available (February 2022).

WP4: Valorisation and dissemination of results

Task-4.1: Publication of results (M36-M56)

Two publications in peer review journals are planned.

One of them will present the number and localization of IS6110 in the diversity of *M. bovis* French strains. This article will show that more than a third of *M. bovis* strains in our sample are IS6110 multicopy, 10% have IS6110 high copy number and these strains are present in the same phylogenetic tree. This work describes that the current epidemiologically most successful strains in France have high number of IS6110.

A focus on SB0120-CO genotype shows a strong stability of the IS6110 copy number and localization independently of the animal species.

These results make us wonder if this success could not be the consequence of phenotypic modifications fitness due to the genetic changes originated by IS6110 transposition.

This article is written and being corrected by the co-authors. It will be submitted shortly.

The second publication will present the new reference genomes with their analysis, the genetic differences between them and the possible consequences in their phenotype. This article currently being written.

Writing of a short communication is also planned. The aim of this communication is to study the high diversity and the unexpected evolutionary patterns of Direct Repeat region and CRISPR Cas locus in the French *M. bovis* diversity.

New complete genomes were obtained and should be submitted in the first trimester of 2022.

Task-4.2: Communication (M36-M56)

In March, Ciriac presented his result to his steering committee during the second thesis project steering committee. The committee appreciated the presentation and validated his enrolment in the third year.

In the same month, Ciriac presented on live his thesis subject during “ma thèse en 180 secondes challenge”. The video is available on YouTube platform: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NDdasDgzt2Y>. The goal of this challenge is to present his thesis subject in 3 minutes.

Ciriac presented his thesis subject at the speech competition in ASMOHEJP2021. Ciriac also presented two posters in the same event (one on the IS6110 work and one on the acquisition of new reference genomes).

Ciriac presented an oral communication on his result on IS6110 during ABIES doctoral days 2021.

Ciriac presented during regular unit meetings (Scientific Happy Hours) his strategy to obtain new reference genomes and his early results.

Ciriac participated to a speech competition in “Doc’Avenir” event which organised by his doctoral school and won the first prize of the public and the second prize of the jury.

The student presented his result on IS6110 with a poster presentation during two congresses (Congress of the French Society of Microbiology 2021 and Scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021) and obtained “the best poster presentation” prize during the scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021.

The *M. bovis* congress scheduled on June 2020 has been postponed to June 2022 because of the COVID-19 crisis. We had been selected for a poster presentation on the 2020 planned session. According to our new results, we hope to be able to present a poster or oral communication in the 2022 session.

Task-4.3: PhD manuscript writing (M36-M56)

Ciriac will start to write the thesis’ introduction in M28.

The rest of the manuscript writing is planned to be finished by M51.

7.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	D-PhD06-6.2	Second steering committee report	M39	M41		This committee was made in M39 and the document translate in English was published in M41.

	D-PhD06-6.3	Oral communication at a congress	M38	M41		Oral communication on IS6110 study in ABIES doctoral days 2021 congress.
	D-PhD06-6.4	first publication in microorganisms MDPI	M40		M51	This deliverable is delay because writing/correction time and result improvement delayed by COVID-19 crisis.
	D-PhD06-6.5	Final steering committee	M50	None		This document is not requested by Ciriac's doctoral school.
	D-PhD06-6.6	Oral communication at a congress	M54			
	D-PhD06-6.7	Publication in an international journal	M54			
	D-PhD06-6.8	PhD manuscript	M56			

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	M-E5-1	PacBio + Illumina sequencing for obtaining reference genomes	M30	Yes	M41	Strains are sequenced in MinION technology and two of them are also sequenced in PacBio technology. As planned, all strains are also sequenced in Illumina technology.
	M-E5-2	Assembly and annotation of reference genome	M38	Yes	M45	
	M-E5-4	Mapped genome	M36	Yes	M47	
	M-E5-5	Strain selection for WP3	M40	Yes	M43	Strains are selected and cultivated to obtain good concentration of them. Moreover the BSL 3 closure put the experiments of WP3 on hold..

	M-E5-6	SNP matrix	M44	No	M50	SNP matrix was obtain. Complete genome allow to study bacterial genomic structure like the region of difference and broken coding sequence in 10 genomes. These events were also listed and described.
	M-E5-7	List of SNP in virulence genes	M44	No	M50	Ongoing

7.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Ma thèse en 180 secondes	To learn how to explain thesis subject quickly and clearly to non-scientific people.	11/02/2021	Paris Est University
MinION sequencing training	Presentation of MinION sequencing and how to run it.	22-26/02/2021	ANSES
Bionumerics training	Presentation of Bionumerics	19/04/2021	ANSES
ABIES doctoral days 2021	Scientific meeting on “transition” organised by Ciriac’s doctoral school.	6-7/05/2021	Doctoral school ABIES AgroParisTech
Webinar on bartonella	Knowledge in the detection and treatment of bartonella.	20/05/2021	SFM
Interdisciplinary Seminar 'City and Health: What is the value of the 'One Health' approach for research and action?	Scientific knowledge and exchange on the integration of the Onehealth concept in research and the health system and the need for it to be taken into account at the interdisciplinary and international level.	09/02/2021	Doctoral school ABIES AgroParisTech
Webinair on legionella	Knowledge in the detection and treatment of legionella.	03/06/2021	SFM
ASMOHEJP2021	Annual scientific meeting of One health European joint programme.	09-10-11/06/2021	One health EJP
Webinair on “useful or useless bacterial serologies “	Webinair on “useful or useless bacterial serologies “.	10/06/2021	SFM

Webinair on measles	Knowledge in the detection and treatment of measles.	24/06/2021	SFM
SARSCoV-2 sequencing with nanopore technology	History of sequencing and bioinformatics analysis. Presentation of the latest tools developed for genome assembly and comparison!	01/07/2021	Doctoral school ABIES AgroParisTech
Bioinformatic training	One week training at INRAE to confirm genome assembly strategy and refines their analysis.	16-20/08/2021	INRAE
Doc'Avenir 2021	To discover the different possibilities of professional orientation after the thesis.	15/09/2021	Doctoral school ABIES AgroParisTech
Meeting on « Impact des technologies de rupture : quel rôle des établissements de l'ESR ? »	Knowing the impact of disruptive technologies: what role for reference healthcare institutions.	22-24/09/2021	Doctoral school ABIES AgroParisTech
Scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021	Scientific meeting on: Epidemiology and Surveillance Exposure and toxicology of chemical contaminants Antibiotic resistance Plant health Food safety Animal health and welfare	13,16,20,28 and 30/09/2021	ANSES
Congress of the French Society of Microbiology (SFM) 2021	French scientific meeting on microbiology fields.	22/10/2021	SFM

7.6. Publications and patents and remarkable outcomes

C.Charles. (2021, May 19). C.Charles second thesis project steering committee report. doi: <https://zenodo.org/record/4772558>

10 new reference genomes of *M. bovis* have been sequenced, assembled and soon published. These complete genomes close to *M. bovis* French diversity will help to better understand their characteristics and will be very useful in epidemiological study.

Ciriac won two prizes (first prize of the public and second prize of the jury) during speech competition organised by his doctoral school (During Doc'Avenir event).

Ciriac won "best poster presentation" prize during the scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021.

7.7. Impact and Relevance

The aim of this thesis project, a collaborative study between ANSES, Animal Health Laboratory (Maisons-Alfort) and INRAE, Infectiology and Public Health laboratory (Nouzilly), two French EJP Partners, is to better understand the complex biology of *M. bovis* through the study of the complete genomes of a large panel of isolates of interest. The first two parts aimed at obtaining reference sequence (WP1) and identifying large genomic events (WP2). This part of the project will be carried out at ANSES and with the support of Genoscreen, Lille, for the strains' Illumina and MinION sequencing. These new genomes will allow to better understand the *M. bovis french* genotypes and will be useful for

epidemiological study. The WP3 of the project will consist of studying phenotypic traits that the genetic events disclosed by the genomic studies through analyses of antigenic variability, lipidomics and proteomics studies. Design of these perspectives will be carried out at INRAE with the support of IPBS laboratory at Toulouse (France) for molecular target selection.

7.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p><u>Biological samples</u> The beneficiary must confirm that no Human and/or Animal samples will be collected for further analysis.</p>	No human or animal samples will be collected for further analyses
<p><u>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects</u> The beneficiary must confirm that authorisations for relevant facilities (e.g., security classification of laboratory) have been obtained, and that safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.</p>	Authorisations for relevant facilities have been obtained, and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.
<p><u>Non EU countries (putative collaboration with Argentina)</u> The beneficiary must provide details on the material which will be imported to/exported from EU and confirm that the adequate authorisations have been obtained.</p> <p>Please provide more information on Nagoya Protocol Compliance</p>	<p>Whether any collaboration was established with one of the potential mycobacterial groups in Argentina, INTA-Castelar, the <i>M. bovis</i> French strains to be sent will be so only if a MTA between the two interested parties (Anses-INTA) was signed beforehand and the <i>ad hoc</i> import licence to send them to Argentina was appropriately established.</p> <p>Concerning the Nagoya Protocol in the French territory, within the Framework of the n° 2016-1087 law of the 8 August 2016 for reconquering biodiversity, nature and landscapes, which is the implementation of Nagoya Protocol, the decree n°2017-848 of the 9 May 2017 fixates the rules to have access to the genetic resources situated in the national territory and to share the advantages resulting in their use. Argentina complies with the Nagoya protocol by the law 2726 of the 26 November 2015.</p>

7.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay

Comments:

The delay observed in the last report has been almost completely made up. Moreover, genomic target is not completely done and our BSL 3 laboratory will not be available until M51. This problem is added to the end of Ciriac's thesis coming up (M57) and the beginning of the manuscript writing. At the moment we are not sure that we will be able to complete all the tasks in WP3.

7.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

7.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Not Applicable

7.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	Ma thèse en 180 secondes		
Date:	09/03/2021		
Place:	YouTube https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NDdasDqzt2Y		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No

Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	160 live event & 174 in the platform	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	ABIES doctoral days 2021. Oral presentation		
Date:	6-7/05/2021		
Place:	Paris France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No

Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	150+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	C. Charles' second thesis project steering committee		
Date:	19/05/2021		
Place:	Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4772558		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Yes	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No

Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	21	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM 2021. Speech event, 2 poster presentations		
Date:	9-11/06/2021		
Place:	Online and Copenhagen		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	900+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	Scientific happy hours. Oral presentation		
Date:	03/09/2021		
Place:	Teams meeting (Maisons-Alfort France)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	20	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	Doc'Avenir 2021. Speech competition		
Date:	15/09/2021		
Place:	Paris, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0

<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	Congress of the French Society of Microbiology (SFM) 2021. Poster presentation.		
Date:	22-24/09/2021		
Place:	Nantes, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	400+	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0

Policy Makers	0		
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Name of the activity:	Scientific and doctoral days of ANSES 2021. Poster presentation.		
Date:	13,16, 20, 28 and 30/09/2021		
Place:	Teams meeting (Maisons-Alfort France)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	170+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

8. PhD07- MACE

8.1. Summary

A review of cystic echinococcosis surveillance and control methods, as well as historical mathematical modelling approaches used, was drafted for an internal report due 15 months after the start of the PhD (Confirmation report). This report is available in Zenodo (relates to D-PhD07-6.1).

Methodology for a new surveillance programme for cystic echinococcosis in dogs for Uruguay has been developed and will be implemented by our colleagues in the National Commission for zoonoses (NCZ). This framework is being extended and adapted to support current planning of a screening programme across the country, in collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture (relates to D-PhD07-6.2). Due to changes in prioritisation since the beginning of the pandemic and a change in leadership in Uruguay, our collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture has been put on hold indefinitely. We have reached out to colleagues in Iran and Italy to set up collaborations and data sharing for the validation of the methodology.

The elicitation questionnaire is currently being planned to be conducted in a representative sample audience of stakeholders in South America. We are currently in communications with partners and are planning to share the questionnaire following a short presentation of the objectives and outcomes of the survey (relates to D-PhD07-6.3).

A stochastic, individual-based transmission model of the dynamics of cystic echinococcosis between dogs and sheep is currently being developed, with significant progress made (relates to D-PhD07-6.4).

A Trip was made to Argentina, with a visit to the Argentine medical research institute under the Argentinean Health Ministry (ANLIS) in Buenos Aires and the regional unit of epidemiology and environmental health in the Andes area (URESA), in Rio Negro, with engagement activities and support of the sheep vaccination programme against CE.

8.2. Overview of project progress

The PhD project has been progressing mostly as originally planned. A draft of review of surveillance and control tools for CE (D-PhD07-6.1) was written for the confirmation process and uploaded to Zenodo. An initial spatio-temporal model of CE was fitted to data in Uruguay (D-PhD07-6.2). For the spatial analysis, the student's current focus country has shifted from Uruguay to Iran and Italy. We are currently collaborating with colleagues within the latter two countries mentioned, and we have received data which can be used to validate the methodology. The elicitation questionnaire (D-PhD07-6.3) that was originally moved forward was developed, but it was not possible to deploy yet due to COVID19, we are currently engaging stakeholders to deploy it in South America. Significant progress has been made coding the mathematical model to simulate different control scenarios (D-PhD07-6.4).

8.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

The relevant literature has been flagged (MACE.Y2.A), with a draft finalised for the student's confirmation report (due in M39), this output relates to deliverable (D-PhD07-6.1), which is available in Zenodo.

An initial pilot version of the spatial model was developed based off data from Uruguay between the years of 2008 – 2015 (D-PhD07-6.2), however due to concerns regarding the spatial coverage of the data used, it was decided not to make the analysis public yet. Instead, we are adapting and extending the framework to support a screening programme that Uruguay is currently planning, so that the model can be revisited with better data. Currently, to be best of our knowledge, Uruguay's screening programme for CE is on hold due to COVID-19. We have received data from colleagues in Italy from a recent survey for CE in sheep and goat farms. Furthermore, we have received data from Iran from another recent survey which investigated the prevalence of CE in dogs within farms near Kerman. We plan to utilize this data for the validation of the geostatistical methods developed.

The main focus of the student during the last year has been to conduct an elicitation with surveillance and One Health experts at an international conference. This exercise will allow to capture in the mathematical model developed in this project more realistic considerations regarding “willingness to pay” and “willingness to accept” of different control and surveillance strategies. This task relates to MACE.Y5.3; and was originally scheduled for later in the project (milestone MACE.Y5.A; M53; updated as deliverable D-PhD07-6.3), however a unique opportunity presented itself to conduct this task with the support of the organizers of the 4th International Conference on Animal Health Surveillance (ICAHS). This exercise has never been done for surveillance in a One Health context, and will have unique policy relevant impact, which will be shared with key stakeholders. Due to Covid-19, the ICAHS conference was delayed and eventually cancelled, the framework developed here was then adapted (upon a request by a WHO colleague) to support the COVID-19 response, by conducting the questionnaire within the WHO COVID-19 Stakeholder meeting in the context of investment in improving sensitivity for contact-tracing of cases in the WHO South-East Asian Region (SEAR). However, due to the surge of cases in India in early 2021, the activity could not be carried out. The current aim is to conduct the elicitation, as originally planned, with One Health experts in South America, during the summer 2021, and finalize it by M44.

A multi-host, individual based transmission model is currently being developed to, initially, simulate the dynamics of the disease between sheep and dogs (D-PhD07-6.4). This will be extended to include different control options. Coding of the model has started, but not finished (MACE.Y3.A). Simulations still need to be finished (MACE.Y3.B).

In December, the student travelled to Argentina to engage with the Argentine medical research institute under the Argentinean Health Ministry (ANLIS) in Buenos Aires and the regional unit of epidemiology and environmental health in the Andes area (URESAs), in Rio Negro. The student participated in the following activities: visiting the national institute of diagnostics for parasitology, meeting with staff to discuss about the current state of CE within the region and the state of intervention and surveillance, presentations with stake holders regarding zoonotic disease in the local area and food safety, and assisting in the vaccination programme of sheep in Rio Negro against CE.

Posters have been submitted and presented in the BSP annual conference 2021 and the Surrey Vet School Symposium. A poster presentation, participation in a 3MT competition, and organisation of a quiz for a hybrid audience for the OHEJP ASM 2021.

8.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD7-ET2.1-MACE	D-PhD07-6.1	Draft of review of surveillance and control tools for CE	M37		M37	Report completed and uploaded on Zenodo.
	D-PhD07-6.4	Final draft of publication with the model and control scenarios	M32		M44	Progress has been made with the model, delayed due to focus on elicitation.
	D-PhD07-6.2	Spatial Temporal Model of CE validated in Uruguay	M37		M49	Spatio-Temporal model completed and fitted to Historical data from Uruguay (by M37). However, concerns were raised by our local partners in Uruguay regarding the data. We are supporting planning for more data collection and want to revisit this later in the project. As this is currently delayed, we have shifted our attention on validating the method using data from Italy and Iran.
	D-PhD07-6.3	Questionnaire to Elicit WTP/WTA of One Health Surveillance Activities	M36		M52	This deliverable was moved up during the first year of the PhD due to an opportunity presented at the time. Due to Covid-19 the venue was cancelled, and an alternate venue and audience is being scoped.
	D-PhD07-6.4	Final draft of publication with the model and control scenarios	M44		M50	Progress has been made with the model.

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
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This document is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This Programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830

			Work Plan			
PhD7-ET2.1-MACE	MACE.Y3.A	Fitted model of CE to data from Uruguay	M37	Yes		First iteration of statistical model fitted to Uruguay historical data.
	MACE.Y4.B	Eastern European data	M40	No	M48	Due to COVID, engagement with stakeholders has been challenging. We plan to conduct some data analysis later in the year.
	MACE.Y5.A	Online polls with stakeholders completed	M36	Partial	M44	Poll finalised. Deployment pending.

8.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Writing A Confirmation Report	Advice on writing the confirmation report	12/Jan/2021	University of Surrey Doctoral College
GGA Spanish Stage 3	Spanish language	29/Sept/2020 – 5/May/2021	University of Surrey Global graduate award
OHEJP Summer School 2021	One Health	26th July – 6th August 2021	OHEJP

8.6. Publications and patents

Review of surveillance and control tools for CE. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4672250

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4672250>

This was published as part of the deliverable D-PhD07-6.1.

8.7. Impact and Relevance

We are engaging with colleagues in Iran and Italy. We are working on a spatial model that is using data from a survey investigating CE prevalence in dogs (Iran), sheep and goats (Italy).

We have engaged with colleagues in Rio Negro, Argentina and assisted in their most recent vaccination programme. An article about the work can be found here (in Spanish): <https://prensa.rionegro.gov.ar/articulo/39980/con-presencia-extranjera-comenzo-el-operativo-de-vacunacion-contra-hidatidosis-en-parajes-provinciales>

This project has allowed collaboration with partners within the consortium (namely between UoS and ISS), as well as supporting stakeholders in South America. The PhD student has engaged in activities

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in Brazil and Uruguay, supporting ministry of health officials through data analysis of current surveillance and control programmes.

We have been collaborating with the National Commission for Zoonoses in Uruguay and assisting them in planning a survey for 2021, sampling dogs for cystic echinococcosis. We are extending our network of collaborations and partnerships to maximize the impact of the work developed, currently engaging with partners in Italy and Iran.

8.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p><u>Non EU countries (Argentina and Peru)</u></p> <p>-The beneficiary must provide details on the material which will be imported to/exported from EU and confirm that the adequate authorisations have been obtained.</p> <p>-As low middle income countries are participating in the study, the beneficiary must confirm that fair benefit-sharing arrangements with local stakeholders are ensured during the project (cf the Global code of conduct for research in resource-poor settings – www.globalcodeofconduct.org)</p> <p>This project states that the beneficiary will collect “data” from sheep and dogs.</p> <p>Further details are needed on the researcher’s interaction and ‘use’ of a legal animals (e.g. sheep and dogs). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so please comment on any implications for the animals. Please describe how the animals’ welfare are protected and considered (e.g. if the dogs or sheep are affected when collecting data. Are any animals restricting for data collection etc).</p> <p>Please confirm if there are any impacts on the animals. Please provide a statement on the 3Rs aspects of this work</p> <p>If Ethical Approval is required please state which Research Ethics Committee this will be sent to, in the EU and non-EU countries.</p>	<p>The project is using historical data that has already been collected through the ongoing control and surveillance programme in Rio Negro, Argentina and in Uruguay. The data is collected following standard protocols that have been approved in the countries (Argentina & Uruguay). Animal welfare is managed through the guidelines approved in the country. There are no physical materials transferred to the University of Surrey/EU, we only receive the data in silico (i.e. csv/excel files).</p> <p>The lead of the group in Argentina, Prof. Edmundo Larrieu, is registered as an external supervisor, which ensures fair benefit-sharing of all the outputs. Outcomes are also communicated with the local authorities (Echinococcosis surveillance and control programme in Rio Negro). A MoU is currently being drafted with the collaborators in Uruguay.</p>

8.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
			MACE.Y4. B	M40	M48	This was delayed as collaboration with stakeholders has been challenging.		
			D-PhD07-6.3	M53	M46	The elicitation was originally moved forward, however the original venue where the elicitation was going to be conducted in was cancelled due to COVID.		

8.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	No
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	

8.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

We are collaborating with Comision Zoonosis in Uruguay and their Programa de Equinococosis quística (Programme of Cystic Echinococcosis). They are planning on initiating a national survey for cystic echinococcosis in dogs. We are preparing to assist with the planning of said programme but has been delayed. We have also worked with the Ministry of Health in Argentina (specifically with URESA) with the vaccination programme of December 2021.

In terms of OHEJP stakeholders, this project is a close collaboration between UoS and ISS, Rome. We are working closely with Dr. Adriano Casulli from the Istituto Superiore di Sanità in Italy, who leads the MEmE JRP. We are also collaborating with Professor Majid Fasihi Harandi from the Kerman University of Medical Sciences in Iran; with the studies they are conducting on cystic echinococcosis within the region's dog population. Another collaborator we are working with is Professor Laura Rinaldi from the University of Naples. They have recently conducted a survey of the prevalence of cystic echinococcosis in farms in two separate regions of Italy. We will be using this data to validate the geostatistical method developed.

8.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021. Presentation of a poster, participation in 3-minute thesis competition and quiz organisation.		
Date:	9-11th June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Yes	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	Yes

Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	BSP Annual Meeting 2021		
Date:	21-25th June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Yes	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			

	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	Surrey Vet School Symposium		
Date:	1-2nd July 2021		
Place:			
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Yes	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	No record	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0

Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

9. PhD08- DESIRE

9.1. Summary

In 2021 the PhD candidate has focused on the NGS analysis, literature review, field work, lab work and preparations for the population genetic study. The collection of monitoring data of rat populations by app continued in 2021. However, the number of reports is currently too low and too geographically clustered to be used for analyses. The monitoring app is running and will continue, but the PhD will focus on a different study: a population genetics study, assessing the genetic relatedness of rat populations across a city, and studying the influence of green and blue areas on the dispersal of wild rats. In 2021, the study has been set up and samples have been collected. These will be analysed in 2022. The PhD student has familiarised herself with the analyses of the NGS data. These results have been verified with more traditional techniques in collaboration with the partner institute WBVR. This demanded more time than anticipated but improved the final result. Also, with the WBVR, the PhD student has studied the virome of a selection of rats. Currently, the PhD student is finishing the manuscript of this study, which will be submitted in the first months of 2022 to a peer-reviewed journal.

Additional to the initial work plan, a literature review on zoonoses of wildlife has started, for which several wildlife species that are commonly found in the urban environment have been selected. This should aid in prioritising research and funds, and should give more insight in ecological mechanisms influencing the wildlife populations and/or the zoonotic pathogens

Furthermore, the PhD student has participated in multiple educational activities, both on specific topics to be used in this PhD (e.g., a Microbiome Data Analysis Workshop) and on general scientific topics, such as Scientific publishing and Scientific writing. The PhD student joined the OHEJP 'A day in the life of a PhD student' campaign with a LinkedIn blogpost, joined the NCOH (Netherlands Centre for One Health) Science café with a pitch about her research (YouTube) and she was interviewed about her research by NCOH which resulted in a written interview.

9.2. Overview of project progress

The main activities this far in 2021 have been the NGS analysis, literature review and field work. Furthermore, the PhD student has participated in multiple educational activities, both on specific topics to be used in this PhD (e.g., a Microbiome Data Analysis Workshop) and on general scientific topics, such as Scientific publishing and Scientific writing.

In 2021, a visit was initially planned to a collaborating partner (FLI) in July. This visit was rescheduled to the end of 2021, due to the extended field work, but had to be rescheduled a second time due to personnel reasons at the FLI. It will now take place March-April 2022.

9.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

In 2021, it was planned to continue the field study, which indeed is progressing as anticipated. It was decided in 2020 to collect more samples from a third city rather than initiate a new type of field study. With a combination of field work and collection from rats by pest controllers in the city, enough samples were collected for further analyses.

Also, the collection of monitoring data of rat populations by app continued in 2021. However, the number of reports is currently too low and too geographically clustered to be used for analyses. The monitoring app is running and will continue, but the PhD will focus on a different study: a population genetics study, assessing the genetic relatedness of rat populations across a city, and studying the influence of green and blue areas on the dispersal of wild rats. In 2021, the study has been set up and samples have been collected. These will be analysed in 2022.

The PhD student has familiarised herself with the analyses of the NGS data. These results have been verified with more traditional techniques in collaboration with the partner institute WBVR. This demanded more time than anticipated but improved the final result. Also, with the WBVR, the PhD student has studied the virome of a selection of rats. Currently, the PhD student is finishing the manuscript of this study, which will be submitted in the first months of 2022 to a peer-reviewed journal.

Additional to the initial work plan, a literature review on zoonoses of wildlife has started, for which several wildlife species that are commonly found in the urban environment have been selected. This should aid in prioritising research and funds and should give more insight in ecological mechanisms influencing the wildlife populations and/or the zoonotic pathogens.

9.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD08-DESIRE	D2	Comparative study between cities and neighbourhoods for rat and rat-borne diseases.	September (M45)		September (M57)	Due to the limited number of samples from the field work in 2020, field work was also performed in 2021, which causes a delay.
	D5	An international, peer reviewed publication about the effect of city greening on rat populations and related public health risks.	September (M45)		September (M57)	Due to the limited number of samples from the field work in 2020, field work was also performed in 2021, which causes a delay.

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD08-DESIRE	M3	Visit laboratories of partner institutes WBVR and FLI	M42	Partial	M51	The partner institute WBVR has been visited several times for various collaborations, of which the study of the virome is most notable. The FLI is scheduled for March 2022.

9.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Introduction to R	How to work with R	12-01-21 t/m 02-02-21	Wageningen University
Scientific publishing	Scientific publishing	09-03-21	Wageningen University
Scientific writing	Scientific writing skills	29-03-21 t/m 10-05-21	Wageningen In'to languages
Microbiome Data Analysis Workshop (MDAW)	Data analysis of microbiome data	20-04-21 t/m 23-04-21	Hasselt University
Supervising students	How to supervise BSc and MSc students	17-06-21 & 18-06-21	Wageningen University
Principles of Ecological and Evolutionary Genomics	Principles of Ecological and Evolutionary Genomics	28-09-21 & 29-09-21	Wageningen University

9.6. Publications and patents

No publications, currently finalizing manuscript regarding NGS sequencing. The PhD student joined the OHEJP 'A day in the life of a PhD student' campaign with a LinkedIn blogpost, joined the NCOH (Netherlands Centre for One Health) Science café with a pitch about her research (YouTube) and she was interviewed about her research by NCOH which resulted in a written interview.

9.7. Impact and Relevance

The PhD student has regular contact with scientists from the WBVR about different aspects of the study: virome analysis, analysis of 16S NGS results and specific pathogen testing. The supervisors involved in this PhD meet once every 3 months to discuss the progress of the research. Also, we are currently discussing potential collaborations for the genetic study with the Wageningen University and the University of Amsterdam.

9.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

9.9. Delay in Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
NGS analyses	M57	M59	D-PhD08-3	Not given	Not given	Delay due to inefficient supervision possibilities	NA	NA

9.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes, due to COVID-19
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

9.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

The PhD student and PIs are involved in a grant proposal about “Ticks and the city”, which has been submitted again and has made it to the second selection round. If this is granted, this would result in extensive collaboration between the projects. In the selection of the field sites this has already been considered.

Also, collaboration is present with our RIVM colleagues working on AMR: samples that contain MRSA or antibiotic resistant Enterobacteriaceae are further typed together with this group.

Furthermore, we share samples with a PhD student who is based at the Erasmus MC and who is part of the One Health PACT – Predicting Arboviruses Climate Tipping points project from the Netherlands Centre for One Health. This PhD student will test the samples for arboviruses that we initially had not included in our study plan, of which our PhD can also use the results. This collaboration therefore is beneficial to both PhD’s. Finally, samples from our study were shared with the Dutch Pest & Wildlife Expertise Centre to Investigate rodenticide resistance.

9.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	Poster presentation at the WIAS Annual conference		
Date:	28 & 29 April 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	Pitch at NCOH Science Café (NCOH= Netherlands Centre for One Health)
Date:	03-06-21

Place:	Utrecht University		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	10	Other	0
Policy Makers	5		

Name of the activity:	ASM OHEJP 2021 – 3-minute thesis oral presentation and poster presentation
Date:	9-11 June 2021
Place:	Online
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories	

	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	5	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	5		

10. PhD09- UDoFRIC

10.1. Summary

The student has been making progress in the project's current objectives. The nine-month Y2 report has been submitted as the first deliverable. The literature review focusing on the background and previous research conducted on fluoroquinolone (FQ) resistance (FQR) in *Campylobacter* has been completed. The project has access to six distinct datasets (poultry *Campylobacter* strains and associated metadata) over a 24-year period. *Campylobacter* strains were obtained either by sampling caecal contents of broilers at slaughter or neck skin from broiler carcasses after processing. Data analysis has been carried out on a subset of the dataset available to this project, obtained by previous UK national research and surveillance studies in poultry, analysing the trends in FQR over time and production factors associated with FQR (e.g. bird age, farming methods, date of sampling). Work has also been conducted identifying *Campylobacter* lineages and aims to determine if there is a link between MLST or whole genome sequence information and FQR. Historic isolates have been recovered from the APHA *Campylobacter* National Reference Laboratory archives, their species identification has been confirmed and DNA from these isolates has been extracted and whole genome sequencing (WGS) has been carried out on 96 isolates from 1995, 2008 and 2020. Work has been completed to characterise the MLST profiles of isolates from the selected years and from these, a representative sample have undergone analysis of phenotypic resistance profiles by determination of minimal inhibitory concentrations (MICs). The student has now relocated to ANSES in France. Using the information obtained throughout the project four FQ-susceptible *C. jejuni* isolates have been chosen for *in vivo* FQ-resistant mutant generation and competition trials at ANSES. Mutant generation has been completed and *in vivo* competition trials are currently underway.

The student has also been taking part in journal clubs, attending local presentations/seminars at the APHA and meeting with staff members who have extensive experience and knowledge on the historic use of antibiotics (ABs). The student also presented a poster at the 2021 annual EJP scientific meeting, he also entered the 3MT competition and presented a poster at the medical school post graduate conference with the University of Warwick.

10.2. Overview of project progress

Literature review

The first section of the literature review focused on *Campylobacter* within broiler production systems, its impact on industry and on human health. Also, publications on *Campylobacter* genetics, including virulence mechanisms, mutations, and gene transfer have been reviewed. The second section of the literature review has also been completed, with a distinct focus on FQs. The first subsection focusses on discovery of FQs, their chemical structure and the differences between different types of FQs, their uses, importance and mechanisms of action. Then, the review describes the historic trends in the use of FQs and how this usage has developed over time. The text mainly focusses on when literature first discovered a link between the use of antibiotics both in medicine and in agriculture and how use in these sectors selected for antibiotic resistance, including the environmental impact. This link was then recognised by government bodies and the use of fluoroquinolones as a prophylaxis to treat against *Salmonella* in poultry is now outlawed, with FQ use being reserved for treatment in diagnosed chickens. The third section focuses on the specific relationship between FQR and *Campylobacter*, and how this has developed over time. It summarised the research in the mechanisms of FQR in *Campylobacter*, the emergence, spread and persistence of this resistance and previously identified factors associated with FQR in *Campylobacter*.

Data collection and identification of data gaps

Information has been gathered and reviewed of six datasets taken from research and surveillance of broiler production systems from 1994 to 2020. These datasets include information on phenotypic resistance to antimicrobials, genomic data (including some whole genome sequence data) and epidemiological meta-data of 3052 poultry *Campylobacter* isolates. Key work has been undertaken in

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the collation of the datasets included in this project. A sample size of isolates has been collected for years (1995 (n=96), 2008 (n=96) and 2020 (96)) where WGS information was missing, and work is ongoing to process this. Isolates sampled from 1995 have been profiled using MLST and we are currently working on building a fluoroquinolone resistant snps database for *Campylobacter* to determine genotypic resistance. From 1995, 2008 and 2020 we have also determined a sample list and outlined methods for MICs to determine phenotypic resistance profile to compare with our genotypic resistance findings. Further work has been carried out in the analysis of previously characterised datasets to identify trends in resistance in several associated production variables (such as farming method, abattoir of slaughter etc). Initial observations follow that of previous studies, indicating that FQR in *Campylobacter* has increased over time and that certain clonal complexes and sequence types may be specifically associated with FQR. Similar analysis is needed on one final dataset the student has yet to acquire.

Training in WGS and bioinformatics

Training in Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) and bioinformatics has been undertaken earlier than planned, due to COVID 19 safety precautions preventing access to lab-based training. Bioinformatics training has involved the building of a database of known antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes and mutations for *Campylobacter*, and initial training to assemble genomes, to identify multi locus sequence types using SRST₂ and detecting AMR genes and mutations using the APHA SeqFinder WGS analysis pipeline. The student has now categorised the first set of WGS information (1995 dataset, n= 96 isolates) into MLST profiles, completed training in the use of APHA SeqFinder and is finalising the *Campylobacter* AMR database to determine a genotypic resistance profile. The student has also attended a week-long online course with the Antimicrobial Resistance EURL and an online training course of “Bioinformatics for Biologists: An Introduction to Linux, Bash Scripting, and R” with Wellcome Genome Campus Courses and Conferences to train in different detection methods of AMR and utilising WGS information.

***In vivo* trials**

In vivo experiments have begun at ANSES with the student relocating to conduct such experimentation.

Phase 1: Mutant generation

Four groups of specific pathogen-free (SPF) and *Campylobacter*-free chicks were inoculated with one of four FQ-susceptible *C. jejuni* strains. Two weeks post inoculation birds underwent enrofloxacin treatment, as per manufacturer’s instructions. Samples were taken at regular intervals throughout the experiment and *C. jejuni* positive samples were monitored for fluoroquinolone resistance. Four FQR isolates taken from samples at the latest point in the study were selected for use in competition trials.

Phase 2: *In vivo* Competition trials

Three groups of SPF chicks have been and will be dosed with either a susceptible wild-type strain of *C. jejuni*, its fluoroquinolone resistant counterpart (see phase 1), or a co-inoculum of both. The first competition trials have been conducted with the results currently being processed.

The remaining three strains will undergo competition trials from February to September 2022.

10.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Literature review of FQ in *Campylobacter*

The student has completed the literature review on the topic as planned. It consists of three major sections: *Campylobacter*, Fluoroquinolones and Fluoroquinolone resistant *Campylobacter*.

Description of the diversity of FQR and acquisition of resistance variants over time

Unplanned supervisor leave has affected the procurement of some datasets delaying the milestone’s progress. Work has been carried out on previously characterised datasets, from 2007-2009 (including caeca and carcass samples) and 2012-2015 (carcass samples only). Of previously characterised datasets we are currently attempting to obtain 2013-2016 caeca dataset, while also carrying out our own analysis on WGS information obtained from 1995, 2008, and 2020 caeca samples isolates.

Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype

Work has been completed on WGS from historic isolates from 1995, 2008, and 2020. Work is currently ongoing to determine genotypic FQ resistance of these isolates and a sample list of isolates has been compiled of the same years to determine phenotypic resistance by analysis of MICs. The determination of phenotypic resistance has been delayed due to COVID-19.

Identification of strains for fitness trials

Four isolates from 2008, derived from caeca samples isolated from conventional broiler farm types have been selected for fitness trials. They have been chosen based on the resistance level of their relevant MLST profile. Each isolate has an MIC value of $\leq 0.12\mu\text{g/ml}$ for CIP and without a mutation of threonine to isoleucine on position 86 of the *gyrA* gene.

Selection and characterization of isogenic resistant strains

Work is currently ongoing to select all four isogenic resistant strains. Two of four strains have been selected for competition based upon their MIC and genotypic resistant profile. Further work is currently ongoing to identify the final two resistant strains using the same methods, and to obtain WGS data from the resistant mutants.

In vitro fitness study: competition growth assays and growth kinetics

Protocols are under study and preparations to carry these experiments out are underway. Due until Mar 2022.

In vitro fitness study: comparison of survival on abiotic surfaces and on food matrices (e.g. Chicken skin model)

This work has not yet started, and it is not due until May 2022

In vitro study: comparison of colonisation using chicken skin models

This work has not yet started, and it is not due until Sep 2022

10.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD09-FBZSH3/A MR2.1-UDOFRIC	D-PhD09-1.2	Literature review of FQ in Campylobacter	M37	M38		
	D-PhD09-1.3	PhD Annual review	M38	M38		
	D-PhD09-2.1	Description of the diversity of FQ resistance and acquisition of resistance variants over time.	M41		Feb 2022	
	D-PhD09-2.2	Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype.	M42		Feb 2022	

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved : Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD09-FBZSH3 /AMR2. 1-UDOFRI C	1	Completion of literature review	M37	Yes		
	6	Annual review	M38	Yes		
	7	Completion of phenotyping and WGS	M39	No	M43	Deadline delayed due to national pipette shortage.
	8	Descriptions of genomic diversity and temporal trends in resistance	M41	No	M47	Deadline delayed due to complications in the acquisition of datasets
	9	Relationship between WGS and phenotype	M42	No	M47	Deadline delayed due to national pipette shortage.

10.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting	Virtual scientific conference	09-11/06/2021	One Health European Joint Project
Warwick University Medical school Post-graduate symposium	Virtual scientific conference	26/05/2021	Warwick University
EURL-AR online training course	Training course	26-29/04/2021	EURL

10.6. Publications and patents

No publications or patents yet.

10.7. Impact and Relevance

Fluoroquinolone resistance in *Campylobacter* is a threat, with the World Health Organisation (WHO) naming it on their list of 12 priority pathogen/AMR combinations. The information gathered during this project on drivers of resistance will help policy makers, the scientific community and the agricultural industry make decisions to prevent or reduce the continuous spread of FQR in *Campylobacter*. The study will interrogate archives of *Campylobacter* from UK research and surveillance activities in broilers from 1995 to 2020 (APHA isolates, phenotypes, MLST, WGS, production metadata), to determine the development and diversity of resistance to FQ over time (temporal trends). In addition, data from French broilers and from other potential sources of *Campylobacter* exposure to people (livestock/environment) will be interrogated wherever possible (ANSES and Public access archives and databases).

The UDoFRiC project combines the collaborative experience of the APHA, ANSES, and Warwick University. It combines the expertise of microbiologists, epidemiologists, and bioinformatics throughout various institutions in the UK and France. The project is supervised by Dr John Rodgers who leads the National reference lab for *Campylobacter* in animals, Professor Muna Anjum who leads bacterial characterisation workgroup and is the AMR research lead and Dr Manal Abu Oun who is the AMR and virulence characterisation team lead at the Animal and Plant Health agency (APHA). Professor Noel McCarthy is the lead of Evidence in Communicable Disease Epidemiology and Control at Warwick University. The project also includes a year at the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) under the supervision of Dr Isabelle Kempf who is a researcher microbiologist specialized in AMR; Leading the Mycoplasma Bacteriology Antimicrobial Resistance Unit in ANSES, Ploufragan and Dr Katell Rivoal, who works in the Hygiene and Quality of Poultry and Pork Products research unit and is leading scientific projects on zoonotic pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Listeria*, and *Campylobacter*) in poultry productions.

10.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p><u>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects</u> The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.</p> <p><u>Animals</u> This project is focusing on broiler chickens. Further details are needed on the researcher's interaction and 'use' of a legal animals (e.g. broiler chickens). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so please comment on any implications for the animals. Please describe how the animals' welfare are protected and considered (e.g. if the chickens are affected when taking samples, even if the work is dealing with faeces as these types of study can, this can still include restricting the animals or manipulating diets, etc, all which can have an impact on the animals). Please provide a statement on the 3Rs aspects of this work If Ethical Approval is required please state which Research Ethics Committee this will be sent to.</p>	<p><u>Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects</u> In the UK, the PhD will be fully trained to deliver all tasks safely and in compliance with the APHA General Health and Safety policy. This will ensure that all work is risk assessed and adequate training, supervision, facilities and equipment will be provided to protect the student and staff. As a minimum we will comply with the Health and Safety at Work etc. Act 1974 and the Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999. In France, the PhD student will be trained in hygiene and security (H&S) by the PhD supervisor, and by the agents in charge of H&S in the Anses Ploufragan Laboratory. The student will have all necessary protective equipment (laminar flow hood, masks, safety goggles, protective gloves...) and he will work in laboratory (L2 level) and animal facilities (A2 level), according to the French Labour Code, and conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation.</p> <p><u>Animals</u> All our animal facilities are under Directive on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes 2010/63/UE. When using conventional chickens, in case of breeding research, directives 98/58/CE, 1999/74/CE and 2007/43/CE must be applied. For experiments planned for the UDOFRIC thesis, we will proceed to obtain agreements from our ethic committees, and requirements of the national legislation or rules will be followed. Approval by the relevant ethics committees is required prior to the start of any animal experiment. Ethical committee on animal experiments is ANSES/ENVA/UPEC (Registered under the number 16 with the French ministry of research (Chairman: Luc Hettinger). Procedures are evaluated by this ethical committee ANSES/ENVA/UPEC and approved by the French ministry of research. Only approved experiments will be conducted. Where relevant planned experiments will also be reviewed by local Ethics Committees at APHA and the University of Warwick.</p> <p><u>Animal welfare laws:</u> The study will be carried out in compliance with National Animal Welfare Regulations i.e. Ministerial Regulation of 1st February 2013 on the protection of animals used for scientific and educational purposes, which meets the 2010/63/EC Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council regarding 'the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes'.</p> <p><u>Replacement</u> We are committed to use alternatives to animal studies wherever reasonable. The fitness of the susceptible and resistant strains will be studied <i>in vitro</i> (growth in culture</p>

	<p>medium and survival on different surfaces) but currently, the <i>in vivo</i> fitness (colonization, competition between colonizing strains) necessitates animal models. However, by regularly consulting the Federation of Laboratory Animal Science Associations (FELASA) and the European Centre for the Validation of Alternative Methods (ECVAM), we will make sure that we can actively respond to the introduction of other validated alternatives and that we can actively contribute to improved protection and respect for the welfare of animals.</p> <p><u>Reduction</u></p> <p>The <i>in vitro</i> models as outlined above will help us to generate valuable information and limit animal experiments. Our experience of the <i>Campylobacter</i> models will also be used to reduce the numbers of included chickens, based on statistical study, to obtain scientific and statistically sound results.</p> <p><u>Refinement</u></p> <p>Animals will have appropriate enrichment. <i>Campylobacter</i> does not induce suffering. The animals will be observed daily to detect any sign of discomfort. They will be offered water and conventional feed ad libitum. In case of severe injury, birds will be euthanized. Sampling of faeces will be limited according to statistical studies (number of sampling per bird).</p>
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10.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
Completion of training in bacteriology and MIC	M33	M36	M3	M33	M40	COVID-19 isolation guidelines have prevented lab-based training. The impact of COVID testing has also impacted the supply of pipette tips needed to carry out MICs.		
WGS and bioinformatics training	M36	M39	M5	M36	M39	COVID-19 has prevented face-to-face interaction and therefore negatively affected teaching. The limitations on lab-based training also prevented the acquisition of some WGS data for teaching exercises		

Comments:

None.

10.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	Yes
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	Yes*

*The main supervisor has been on extended leave since Mar 2021, however other supervisors have intervened to provide guidance and support.

10.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Not Applicable

10.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021 Poster presentation and participation in 3MT competition.		
Date:	9 - 11 th June 2021.		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	Warwick Medical School Post-Graduate Symposium poster presentation
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Date:	26 th May 2021.		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

11. PhD10- WILBR

11.1. Summary

A literature review has been written on the role of wild birds in dissemination and persistence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the farm environment. The review includes sections on identifying the current situation regarding AMR in different environments; drivers for AMR; the role of vectors and the environment in persistence and dissemination of AMR; the role of AMR surveillance; and evaluation of different methodologies for identifying AMR, both by phenotype and genotype, in bacteria.

Pig and presumptive gull faecal samples were collected over three time points in October 2017, 2018, and 2019 from a low antimicrobial usage pig farm as part of the APHA's work on the ARDIG project within the One Health European Joint Programme (<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/jrp-ardig/>). These were grown on antibiotic free and antibiotic selective agar, and 632 *E. coli* were purified from pig and gull faeces (n=342 and n=290 respectively) (see Annex 2, Table 1). 176 gull isolates (110 from T3, 66 from T5) that had not been subject to previous analyses were identified and underwent whole genome sequencing. WGS data for all isolates was run through APHA Seqfinder pipeline and Abricate to identify AMR determinants and plasmids. Seven allele MLST was carried out using SRST2 to identify the *E. coli* Sequence Type (ST) of isolates, which was used as an indicator of *E. coli* diversity in pig and gull populations. A total of 91 different sequence types were identified from the isolates included in this study, with 63 and 57 STs identified in gull and pig isolates, respectively. Considering the SNP differences is the next step to understand if the same "clone" or strain has been transferred rather than an AMR plasmid. A core genome SNP alignment was generated from WGS data of all isolates using Snippy version 4.6.0 to compare the core genes that are present in all members of the same species, and a SNP distance matrix was generated using snp-dists version 0.7.0 to estimate the SNP differences between isolates to determine the levels of genetic variation in the ST744s, allowing any transmission and persistence of clones across host species and time points, on this farm, to be identified. Preliminary analysis allowed AMR profiles to be linked to ST types that are circulating in both wild bird and pig populations.

Another outdoor pig farm, known to have wild birds persistently present on farm, had been recruited for a longitudinal study and was visited in September 2021 where over 150 environmental swabs were collected. An opportunity to examine the dissemination of AMR in wild bird populations across Great Britain for a 12-month period through the APHA's wild bird scanning surveillance programme is currently being pursued.

A poster was submitted to the OHEJP ASM 2021 meeting, and an oral presentation on the PhD was presented virtually in the 3MT competition for the OHEJP ASM 2021, as part of communicating their research. The student won the prize for the best poster presentation at the OHEJP ASM 2021. The student has also attended two virtual plasmid workshops hosted by International Society for Plasmid Biology and Other Mobile Genetic Elements to further develop their skill set for tasks later in the project.

11.2. Overview of project progress

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic in UK only desk and lab-based tasks have been recommended; currently farm visits are not permitted for research projects. A literature review has been completed on the role of wild birds in dissemination and persistence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the farm environment. The review includes sections on identifying the current situation regarding AMR in different environments; drivers for AMR; the role of vectors and the environment in persistence and dissemination of AMR; the role of AMR surveillance; and evaluation of different methodologies for identifying AMR, both by phenotype and genotype, in bacteria.

Over two hundred archived *E. coli* isolates from gull faeces that had not been subject to previous analysis have undergone whole genome sequencing, and downstream bioinformatics is now currently taking place. These isolates were collected as part of the OH-EJP ARDIG project. Work is still being

undertaken so results are not complete.

A farm visit was carried out over 150 environmental swabs were collected. The student has used antibiotic free and antibiotic containing plates to isolate over 1500 isolates from these samples. The student is currently using biochemical tests and MALDI-ToF to determine the species of isolates in order to select a subset for sequencing.

An opportunity to examine the dissemination of AMR in wild bird populations across Great Britain for a 6-month period through the APHA's wild bird scanning surveillance programme is currently being pursued. It has been agreed that the wild bird scanning surveillance will provide 0.5-1.0g of caecal/faecal contents from every wild bird submitted as part of the APHA's wild bird scanning surveillance for a 6-month period. This study would allow a unique opportunity to establish the burden of AMR in the wild bird population of Great Britain. The study will provide context to our on farm studies by allowing wider comparisons to be made, highlighting any correlation between the AMR profiles identified in the farm environment and those found in wild birds across Great Britain.

11.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Deliverable 3 (9-month report) in AWP for Y4 has been completed and deliverable 4 (12 month report) is being undertaken.

Milestone 1 in AWP was delayed as due to further Covid-19 restrictions in the UK, all fieldwork at APHA had been stopped. An outdoor pig farm was visited in September 2021 and over 150 environmental swabs were collected, which resulted in the isolation of over 1500 bacterial isolates. Only one farm visit has been able to be carried out so far due to Covid-19 delays. Milestones 2 and 3 are delayed because of the initial delay of milestone 1.

Some historical *E. coli* isolated from gull faeces, collected from an outdoor pig farm, during a longitudinal study in the OH-EJP project ARDIG are being included in this PhD project as a result of the delays caused by COVID-19. Over two hundred isolates archived from this farm have undergone whole genome sequencing, and downstream bioinformatic analysis is now being carried out in line with Milestone 2. This will result in a dataset including over 300 gull isolates and over 400 pig isolates from three time points that can be compared. AMR profiles and phylogeny are being generated from whole genome sequencing data to assess the diversity of *E. coli* strains and associated ARGs in gulls and pigs on the same farm and assess the potential for transmission of AMR bacteria between wild birds and livestock. This work is still being carried out, so the results are not yet complete.

An opportunity to examine the dissemination of AMR in wild bird populations across Great Britain for a 6-month period through the APHA's wild bird scanning surveillance programme is also being pursued. The wild bird scanning surveillance programme examines wild bird species for all disease and mortality investigations, including infectious and non-infectious disease. They receive submissions from all over Great Britain, and from many different species. It has been agreed that the wild bird scanning surveillance will provide 0.5-1.0g of caecal/intestinal contents from every wild bird submitted as part of the APHA's wild bird scanning surveillance for a 6-month period. Final logistics are being confirmed, taking in to account the risk from human and livestock pathogens that wild birds could be carrying.

11.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
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			Work Plan			
PhD10-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR	D-PhD10-1.3	Completion of 9-month review	M45	M45		
	D-PhD10-1.4	Completion of 12-month review	M48	M48		

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD10-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR	2	Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study	M48	No	M54	
	3	Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance	M48	No	M57	
	4	Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR	M48	No	M60	

11.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
EURL-AR Training Course	Working with bacterial sequence data in relation to the monitoring and reporting of antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and commensal bacteria	26-29/04/2021	Technical University of Denmark

11.6. Publications and patents

No publication or patents.

The student won the prize for the best poster presentation at the OHEJP ASM 2021.

11.7. Impact and Relevance

The supervisory team brings together leading experts in veterinary, wildlife and environmental AMR, with expertise spanning veterinary and molecular microbiology, bioinformatics, microbial ecology and evolution, as well as wildlife disease.

William Gaze is working with the United Nations Environment Project on AMR in the environment, having recently authored the UNEP Frontiers report on AMR and the environment. He is currently located within two interdisciplinary units, Exeter's Centre for Environment and Human health, and the Environmental and Sustainability Institute, which is also part of the University of Exeter

Beside his work as a researcher within SVA, Stefan Börjesson is involved in the Swedish AMR monitoring program and is also a senior lecturer in clinical microbiology with an emphasis on AMR in a One-health perspective at Linköping University at the Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine.

Muna Anjum leads the Bacterial Characterisation Workgroup and is the AMR Research Lead at the APHA working at the interface of molecular and veterinary microbiology, within the One Health remit. As lead for the AMR research, she is also involved in supporting national AMR surveillance activities and APHA's response to national outbreaks and identifying new and emerging threats. She is a member of the DEFRA Antimicrobial Resistance Coordination Group, which advises and reviews the DEFRA activities on antimicrobial usage in animals and AMR in microorganisms from feedstuffs, animals and food, the APHA lead for the Defra AMR in the Environment group and works closely with colleagues in Public Health England in various research projects and national activities.

11.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

11.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
			Milestone 2	M48	M54	COVID-19	Not yet known	Not yet known
			Milestone 3	M48	M57	COVID-19	Not yet known	Not yet known
			Milestone 4	M48	M60	COVID-19	Not yet known	Not yet known

Comments:

The project has been significantly affected by COVID-19 as the student by this point should have visited the farm recruited for longitudinal sampling four times. The original plan was to sample across four time points in one year, but that has not happened because of COVID-19. To help mitigate risks posed by Covid-19 on visiting and sampling on farms, we have already included characterization of archived isolates and are also planning to explore bird caecal samples collected from national surveillance of wild birds.

11.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	None

11.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

This PhD overlaps with the ARDIG project, where wild birds on farm have already been sampled.

11.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	ISPB Plasmids Around the Globe		
Date:	06/05/2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No

Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	60	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	ISPB Plasmids Around the Globe		
Date:	25/05/2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	60	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP ASM 2021. Poster presentation and participation in 3MT competition		
Date:	9 th - 11 th June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	Yes
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0

General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

12. PhD11- EnvDis

12.1. Summary

A major deliverable of the PhD (D-PhD11-1.3) was accomplished in March with the successful submission and defence of the Confirmation Report, which supported the feasibility of the project as well as the adequate progression towards completion. The examiners provided a useful viewpoint (e.g., define more precisely the research question, consider changing the model used as method) that will be considered to further improve the project. It also meant a good learning process towards drafting a document similar to the final thesis and the best strategy to approach it (i.e., constant reading and drafting along the process).

The updated daily human salmonellosis data was received from the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) (previously known as Public Health England) in April, completing the disease data required for performing a thorough analysis for England and Wales. Together with other gathered data (such as altitude, detailed demographics with the number of residents by age and sex, year to year), an exploratory analysis of the data was performed confirming the notably higher prevalence of salmonellosis in the younger age groups (i.e., 0-4 years old). *S. Enteritidis* was confirmed as the predominant serotype over the other serovars, accounting for 54.11% of the cases.

On top of temperature, vapour pressure and cloud cover were found to potentially have a relevant influence over the incidence of salmonellosis, according to some papers (Park, Park and Bahk, 2018), (Aguilar, Herrero and Polo, 2010), (Busse et al., 2019). At the same time, air pressure and dewpoint were identified to be related with water activity in food commodities. Water activity plays an important role in the microbial growth in food and may be more relevant than atmospheric relative humidity of the environment. A conditional incidence of the combined effect of all these variables as well as the effect of extreme climate conditions is on progress. This work will potentially lead to writing of 1-2 papers. A short set of laboratorial experiments in a chicken gut model were performed to assess the impact of environmental perturbances over two bacterial populations (*E. coli* and *Salmonella* alone and in combination) when applied in a patterned fashion. We used a 48h-cyclic pH alteration as example. The outcomes will be a chapter of the thesis.

A spatial analysis to determine the influence of the location over the cases of salmonellosis is also ongoing. Two country-level maps, each of which will display the reported incidence and the simulated incidence based on its linkage with the relevant weather variables. They can be visually compared as a proxy of the role of the weather and the influence of the climate particularities of each region in the incidence of disease.

Since animals are the source of disease for humans, we are gathering as much information as it is available to us to investigate relevant relationships, such as the proximity of animal premises to the disease events or the linkage of the peak of animal salmonellosis with human incidence. So far, we have collected yearly farm animal (cattle, pig, and poultry) numbers per county from APHA. A conditional incidence analysis investigating the likelihood of salmonellosis given the presence of livestock/poultry will follow.

Animal disease information would be ideal to be included in our investigation. However, given their sensitivity nature and the difficult of this type of data to be shared, we were not able to obtain the data.

12.2. Overview of project progress

Under the WP1, with the objective of developing a general tool to assess the risk of infectious diseases (in particular zoonoses) when we have information of relevant environmental factors:

Task 1 « Test and discuss findings of the model for salmonellosis; validate the model with data from another European country; include animal role in the model from available data; write up thesis » has

This document is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This Programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830

been completed for preliminary data, but it is a transversal task that will progress until the end of the PhD in December 2022 (60M). Preliminary results suggest that the three parameters considered so far (eggs, chicken and temperature) play a big role on the seasonality of salmonellosis. Humidity, cloudiness, vapour pressure, air pressure and dewpoint are now to be evaluated in isolation and in combination with the other in the relevance of salmonellosis incidence.

Subtask 1 « Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis » more specifically, where temperature has been seen to be a determinant seasonality factor, but more variables (e.g., humidity) will be taken into consideration applying a conditional incidence analysis to the model. This task is ongoing and has a new deadline in March 2022 (M51).

Subtask 2* « Validate the model with data from another European country; include animal role in the model from (if) available data » due in June 2022 (54M). We have contacted the RIVM as collaborator who is willing to work together in providing salmonellosis incidence data for the Netherlands and thus complementing our model. A Short-Term Mission (STM) travel grant was awarded by OHEJP to this purpose.

Subtask 3 « Write up thesis » due in December 2022 (60M).

12.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1, TASK 1 (sT-1-1.1).

Subtask 1.1 (sT-1-1.1): « Test and discuss findings of the model for salmonellosis »:

Literature review: relevance of salmonellosis and its association with climate variables.

- *Salmonella* is an important agent of disease both in developed and developing countries. The constant foodborne outbreaks linked to *Salmonella* in different countries state the relevance of the topic nowadays. A follow-up of news is needed to keep up to date with latest news.
- Empirical/experimental studies of the impact of environment on *Salmonella* identified cloudiness and vapour pressure as two variables determinant in the seasonality of salmonellosis. These will be further explored with a conditional incidence analysis.
- Water activity has a prominent role in the growth of *Salmonella* in food, as it reflects the amount of water readily available to the microbes. Air pressure and dewpoint were identified as relevant variables linked to water activity and will be explored in the conditional incidence analysis.

Improving R coding skills.

- Exploratory epidemiologic analysis was performed over the definitive UKHSA salmonellosis cases, including relative frequency of salmonellosis incidence per age group (normalized) and total of subspecies identified every year.
- Higher prevalence of salmonellosis in the younger age groups (i.e., 0-4 years old) is evident, followed by 20-24 and 25-29 years old. The average age of infected individual is 30 years old. For the rest of the categories, there is a smooth bell curve.
- *S. Enteritidis* is the clear predominant serotype (94%). There is a non-negligible number of unknown serotypes, meaning that there could be a very wide diversity of serotypes responsible for a considerable number of cases. *S. Thyphimurium* and *S. Virchow* are the following most common serotypes.
- The seasonality of all the years combined (1989-2020) shows an increase in the summer with a peak in August and September. The peak may be delayed as much as one month as compared to the analysis of weekly cases evidenced in previous outcomes for the 90's.
- Spatial analysis will follow. Using both QGIS and R, I am looking for a spatial link between the number of cases registered across the country and the geo-climatic characteristics of the location, as well as the distribution of rural/urban areas and presence of livestock.

Data management and manipulation: the format of data provided by UKHSA was explored:

- Some delay in the data coming from UKHSA was experienced given the ongoing COVID circumstances. The complete dataset was received (i.e., 32 complete years of daily salmonellosis diagnosis in humans in England and Wales from 1989 to 2020).
- The data comprises 560,842 salmonellosis records, with information on the *Salmonella* subspecies and phage type, the age of the patient, laboratory of identification and type of sample analysed.
- A surprising number of 83 records corresponded to patients of 100 years or older, with one record mistakenly aged 127. This finding is compatible with the UK Office for National Statistics, according to whom, there were 202,490 people censused to be ≥ 100 for the years 2007-2019. Yet, we will consider removing these outliers from our analysis.

Constant tailor the research question(s) and approaches to use next:

- The Wavelet analysis is a way for demonstrating seasonality of the weather parameters selected over time. It will be used to compare different models and choose the most adequate. The preliminary analysis performed over weekly cases confirms the seasonality identified year after year. It does not identify other less obvious trends separated greater spans of time.
- Perform different length duration aggregation averages (7, 14, 30 days) of weather parameters to reduce the effect of incubation delay from the weather variation to its perception in human cases detection.
- Perform a conditional incidence analysis combining more than one weather factors (e.g., temperature + humidity/vapour pressure).
- Adjust the model to fit historic prevalence data by incorporating more variables (weather, and other relevant food sources, if found).
- Explore the effect of environment on animal salmonellosis.
- Re-adapting the method from Lo Iacono et al., 2020. for campylobacteriosis to salmonellosis with additional weather variables will follow.

Subtask 1.2* (sT-1-1.2):

Following our last periodic review with the internal and external supervisory team (UKHSA and Zoetis), this subtask has been changed in the Annual Work Plan to: « Validate the model with data from another European country; include animal role in the model from (if) available data » to strengthen the relevance of the project:

- Yearly census of farm animals (cattle, pigs, chicken, duck, geese, other poultry) from 1999 to 2016 per county were provided by APHA. This will be used to find a link with the presence/proximity of animals to the cases.
- Salmonellosis data in chicken farms have been requested to APHA. This information will be very interesting to find similarities in the seasonality in animals/humans and the moment of the highest peak of incidence.
- Collaboration with a similar project at the Dutch National Institute for Health and Environment (RIVM) has been established. We will perform a data and methods exchange to improve our model and validate it with the Netherlands.

12.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast	Comments

			Work Plan		achievement date	
PhD11-FBZ4/5-EnvDis	D- PhD11-2.1	Presentation of findings (e.g., conferences, internal school seminars) Y2	M42	M42		Poster presentation at the OHEJP ASM, OHEJP ASM 3-minute thesis competition Participation on a 3-minute thesis competition of the Doctoral College of the University of Surrey, Organization committee member and participation on the Vet School Research Symposium.
	D- PhD11-2.2	End of Year Progress Review Y2	M48	M48		

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD11-FBZ4/5-EnvDis	M-PhD11-1	Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis	M48	No	M51	Ongoing. We are close to get results from the conditional incidence of humidity and temperature. Other relevant climate variables will be compared to get a clearer understanding of the effect of weather. This milestone will be a summary of a main chapter of the thesis.

12.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
French language classes (weekly)	Languages	07/11/20 - 28/04/21	Global Graduate Award - UoS
German language classes (weekly)	Languages	04/10/21- 04/05/22	Global Graduate Award - UoS
Writing retreat	Writing skills	04/12/20	Research and Development skills - UoS
International Student One Health Association (ISOHA) mentorship program	Networking	11/12/20 - 31/05/21	One Health Commission

Managing your supervisor	Interpersonal skills/ Managerial skills	15/12/20	Doctoral college - UoS
Genomics & Bioinformatics workshop	Interdisciplinary skills	15/12/20	Arnoud van Vliet - UoS
Research Data Management and Open Data	Research skills	19/01/21	Library and Learning Support Services - UoS
OHEJP CPD Workshop – Digital innovation for One Health practitioners	Research skills	25/02/21	OHEJP - Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) & Norwegian Veterinary Institute
Building your professional network workshop	Networking	19/03/21	Research and Development skills - UoS
1 to 1 Career support	Research skills	24/03/21	Doctoral college - UoS
International Women in STEM workshop	Interdisciplinary skills/ Networking	25/03/21	Queen Mary University -QMUL
Performing Data analysis in R studio	Interdisciplinary skills	26/03/21	Academic Skills and Development - UoS
3MT competition practice	Presentation skills	29/03/21	Doctoral college - UoS
The Conversation media training	Presentation skills/ Research skills	20/04/21	Doctoral college - UoS
Demonstration: heart dissection	Teaching skills	22/04/21	University of Surrey
Demonstration Herp practical	Teaching skills	05/05/21 06/05/21	University of Surrey
Storytelling for researchers	Presentation skills/ Research skills	10/05/21	University of Surrey - ESRC Impact Acceleration Account
Communication with impact workshop	Presentation skills/ Research skills	12/05/21	University of Surrey - ESRC Impact Acceleration Account
Vet School Research symposium participation and member of the organising committee	Research skills/ Presentation skills/ Networking/ Managerial skills	18/03/21-02/07/21	School of Veterinary Medicine - University of Surrey
23 Things International participant & Pod chair	Networking/ Managerial skills	08/03/21-07/06/21	Research and Development skills - UoS
OHEJP Summer School	Networking/ Research skills	26/07/21 – 06/08/21	OHEJP – Italian Higher Institute of Health (ISS) & CERSAG
Organisation & participation on News and updates meeting with the NTD group	Research skills/ Managerial skills	Biweekly	University of Surrey
Member of a programme promoting physical activity at the university	Managerial skills/ Transversal skills	Annual	SurreyMoves+ - University of Surrey
Co-author of papers (1)	Writing skills/ Research skills	24/09/2021	University of Surrey
Progress analysis reviews	Writing skills/	Quarterly	OHEJP - UoS

	Project Management skills		
Demonstration: ante-mortem & post-mortem inspection	Teaching skills	09/12/21	University of Surrey

12.6. Publications and patents

No publications

12.7. Impact and Relevance

The project involves the University of Surrey, UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) and Zoetis. EnvDis project builds on current work being done at UKHSA by Dr Gillingham, Prof Nichols and Dr Lo Iacono. Laura's work combines phenomenology of *Salmonella* in England and Wales with mechanistic models. The project fits also very well with research interests of Dr Kanellos in Zoetis in understanding better the disease and how to prevent it; and the activities led by Prof Cook in vHive (<https://vhive.buzz/>). By collaborating with the Dutch National Institute for Health and Environment (RIVM), we are validating the versatility of the model in understanding and measuring the impact of the environment on infectious diseases in different geographic scenarios.

12.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

12.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay
sT-1-1.1	M48	M51	M- PhD11-1	M48	M52	Delayed data on origin Changed the scope. STM collaborator found	NA	NA
sT-1-1.2	NA	NA	M- PhD11-2	M44	M54	Delayed data on origin Changed the scope. STM collaborator found	NA	NA

Comments:

M- PhD11-1 The data were received in April 2021, which was the deadline foreseen for the result of the

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analysis.

M- PhD11-2 As a result of the 2021 OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Laura contacted a PhD student working on a similar OHEJP project (ADONIS) and convened with the supervisory team to apply for a short visit (STM). This will take place early next year, following OHEJP's bases, and will serve as a validation approach for when the model is ready (planned for the first half of the year 2022).

12.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes*
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional Comments: *Due to COVID we have received the salmonellosis data 16 months after the start of the PhD. In the meantime, I focused on learning how to code maps in R and explore spatial distribution as well as proceeding with further literature review. Even though parallel work has been done in the meantime, it has irremediably delayed the progression on analysis of the outcomes.

12.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

A short-term mission was applied to work together with the OHEJP ADONIS project (<https://onehealth.ejrp.eu/jrp-adonis/>) at the RIVM (<https://www.rivm.nl/en>).

ADONIS and EnvDis are two OHEJP projects with a similar research scope, yet with different approaches, where human salmonellosis is studied with the aim of better understanding the epidemiology of the disease:

ADONIS focuses on explaining the trends in the time-series of salmonellosis' incidence. Their approach is based on the variations of explanatory factors, such as national surveillance systems in humans and poultry, following a longitudinal approach. EnvDis aims to estimate the incidence of salmonellosis conditional to certain environmental exposures. It assumes that this conditional incidence is, in general, not depending on time. In addition, it aims to incorporate mechanistic processes, such as bacterial growth in the food source of human transmission. A key benefit of working closely together is to bring the temporal dimension, typical of timeseries analysis, into the conditional incidence approach. Vice-versa, by applying the conditional incidence approach to different settings we would be able to assess whether or not the relationship between salmonellosis and exposure is universal. This collaboration will enhance the robustness of our findings and it will help in overcoming the intrinsic limitations of the different approaches.

12.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	3 rd One Health European Joint Project (OHEJP) Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Presentation of poster and participation in 3-minute Thesis competition.		
Date:	09-11/06/2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	International Day of Women in Science post
Date:	11/02/2021

Place:	Virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	No
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	Yes	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	0	<i>Media</i>	1,935
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Cogwheel workshop – Versatile Emerging Infectious Disease Observatory (VEO)		
Date:	25/02/21		
Place:	Virtual/ Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) & Norwegian Veterinary Institute		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	55	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	Vet School Research Symposium		
Date:	01/07/2021 - 02/07/2021		
Place:	Virtual/ Vet School University of Surrey		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	75	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	Modelling in Animal Health conference (ModAH2)		
Date:	16/09/2021		
Place:	Virtual/ INRAe		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	40	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	EnvDis Deliverables Y1		
Date:	20/12/2020		
Place:	https://zenodo.org/record/4516634#.YD0qWU5xeUk		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Yes	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	0	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

13. PhD12- AptaTrich

13.1. Summary

1) Whole Larvae SELEX

Selection of single stranded DNA-based aptamers specific for *T. spiralis* whole muscle larvae (ML) is ongoing. Using a highly variable and randomized ssDNA library, a whole-larvae SELEX method (Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Enrichment) is undergoing continuous improvement. As of now, 8 rounds of SELEX have been completed using 2 different protocols. Additionally, further selection is ongoing using an alternative protocol.

As is demonstrated in prior research literature, optimization of sequence amplification by PCR, as well as the generation of single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) from double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) is of absolute importance for a successful selection procedure. Considering this, two different methodologies were optimized and compared to determine the best method. Using biotinylated reverse primers, a Streptavidin magnetic bead method used the denaturing abilities of NaOH to liberate unlabeled ssDNA from the magnetic bead surface. Additionally, a lambda exonuclease enzyme was used to digest sequences amplified with phosphorylated reverse primers.

A collaborative partnership has been established and several samples from various rounds of SELEX have been subjected to High-throughput sequencing (HTS) and subsequent bioinformatics analysis to determine possible sequence enrichment. From this, several sequences containing consensus motifs have been selected for synthesis and eventual binding affinity and specificity testing. By incorporating a 5'Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) onto each sequence, binding affinity and specificity for the *T. spiralis* whole ML will be measured using confocal microscopy.

2) *Trichinella spiralis* Excretory/Secretory Proteins

Following the production of *T. spiralis* muscle larvae Excretory/Secretory proteins, the student visited the Montreal partner laboratory at the Research Institute of the McGill University Health Centre (RI-MUHC) to analyze the samples by Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS). During the mission however, several problems were encountered with the equipment, ultimately resulting in a failure to analyze the samples without impact on the samples themselves. During the mission in Montreal, a review article surrounding the use of aptamers in parasitology-based diagnostics was completed. The protein samples are currently awaiting analysis by the partner institute.

13.2. Overview of project progress

- A whole-larvae SELEX method has been established against *Trichinella spiralis* muscle larvae. The current protocol is continuously being improved to produce the highest quality aptamers possible. This includes making frequent alterations in the parameters and conditions of target-aptamer incubation.
- While results of qPCR suggest low sequence enrichment with minimal evolution, HTS and bioinformatics results using PATTERNITY.seq software demonstrate an interesting shift towards a certain consensus sequence present in the variable region. In addition, several sequences illustrating higher than average evolution possess a defined consensus motif of interest.
- *Trichinella spiralis* ES proteins are currently awaiting proteomic analysis by LC-MS/MS for potential biomarkers and aptamer targets of interest.

13.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

1) **Generation of single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) during SELEX**

- A Streptavidin magnetic beads method (A) and Lambda exonuclease method (B) were tested for their ability to generate high quality ssDNA products for future applications in aptamer selection protocols.

A) Streptavidin Beads Method

Gel Loading Sequence

- 1 – 50bp ladder
- 2 – 14 cycle PCR (dsDNA) product before bead treatment
- 3 – Post bead incubation supernatant
- 4 – 100mM NaOH elution #1
- 5 – 100mM NaOH elution #2
- 6 – 100mM NaOH elution #3

Fig 1: Electrophoretic profile of Round 2 SELEX PCR products before and after Streptavidin magnetic beads treatment.

B) Lambda Exonuclease Method

Gel Loading Sequence

- 1 – 50bp ladder
- 2 – 15 cycle PCR (dsDNA) product before digestion
- 3 – No template control (NTC)
- 4 – 15 cycle PCR (dsDNA) product purified
- 5 – Lambda digest product (ssDNA)

Fig 2: Electrophoretic profile of Round 2 SELEX PCR products before and after Lambda Exonuclease treatment

Results: The gel image of the products of method A (Fig 1) display the non-specific generation of double-stranded product at 80bp and single-stranded product (40bp) following 100mM NaOH treatment (lane 4). In contrast, the gel image of the products of method B (Fig 2) illustrate the highly specific generation of ssDNA following lambda exonuclease digestion (lane 5).

2) SELEX monitoring by qPCR Melting Curve Analysis

- The Lambda Exonuclease method of ssDNA generation was adopted for use in two independent trials of aptamer selection against *T. spiralis* ML entitled Rx(5) and Rx(6), where the “x” signifies the round of selection whereas 5 and 6 signify the trial of SELEX. Muscle larvae-bound sequences were subjected to amplification by qPCR and their melting curve profiles examined to qualitatively evaluate whether sequence enrichment had occurred.

- In theory, iterative rounds of aptamer selection should result in sequence “evolution” and a convergence towards specific sequences and motifs that favour aptamer-target interaction. Knowing that imperfectly hybridized double-stranded DNA sequences (heteroduplexes), dominant in populations with high sequence diversity, dissociate at lower temperatures, diversity can be estimated by evaluating melting peaks produced following qPCR.

Fig 3: qPCR Melting curve profiles of Rounds 2 to 7 of Aptamer selection Trial 5

Result: The melting curve data above (Fig 3) suggests slight sequence enrichment from round 2 of selection (Blue) to round 7 of selection (Yellow). Additionally, the sequences of rounds 2 to 7 of selection produced two primary melting peaks at 65°C and 77°C. The increased drop in fluorescence at 77°C from Round 2 to 7 suggests a gradual decrease in sequence diversity with a resulting increase in sequence homogeneity. Finally, the drop in fluorescence at 65°C of the round 7 products is less intense, further illustrating the potential drop in sequence heterogeneity.

Fig 4: qPCR Melting curve profiles of Rounds 2 to 8 of Aptamer selection Trial 6

Result: The qPCR melting curve profiles of SELEX Trial 6 (Fig 4) are a near mirror image of Trial 5 (Fig 3). As with Trial 5 of SELEX, a shift from low melting temperatures to high melting temperatures can be seen. Interestingly, in this trial of SELEX, the shift appears to be more gradual than the more sudden “jump” that is apparent in the yellow curve of Fig 3.

Conclusion: The melting curve profiles of both SELEX Trials suggest that, even after 7 rounds of selection, the sequence pools remain largely heterogeneous, signifying only slight evolution. To more specifically evaluate the SELEX process of each trial, samples were sent for High-throughput sequencing and subsequent bioinformatics analysis.

3) High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) and PATTERNITY.seq Analysis

- Following HTS of SELEX Trial 5 and Trial 6 PCR products, bioinformatics analysis by PATTERNITY.seq concluded an overall weak evolution of sequences.
- After 7 rounds of selection however, some observable sequence enrichment had occurred in both SELEX Trials 5 and 6, with several sequence families having enriched up to 0.1% of the total number of sequences
- While families enriched in Trial 5 and Trial 6 of SELEX were different, 99 families belonging to each SELEX trial shared a common 13-mer consensus sequence of **TTCAATTACCA** present in the 40-mer variable region.
- Additionally, within this consensus sequence, a specific 11-mer hairpin loop motif composed of the following sequence **TTCAATTTACC** was identified in 65 families.

Fig 5: Sequences containing the consensus hairpin loop motif of SELEX Trial 5

Fig 6: Sequences containing the consensus hairpin loop motif of SELEX Trial 6

Conclusion/Perspectives: HTS and bioinformatics data revealed an overall weak sequence evolution throughout the rounds of selection for both Trial 5 and 6. Upon further analysis of the PATTERNITY.seq software results however, the presence of a conserved sequence and structural motif, present in both independent SELEX Trials, demands further investigating. Sequences of interest will therefore be synthesized and labelled with Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) to be used in binding studies using confocal microscopy. Using this method, the binding affinities, as well as the specific binding sites in or on the *T. spiralis* muscle larva can be quantitatively estimated with fluorescence measurements. Alternatively, biotin-conjugated sequences will also be synthesized, fixed to streptavidin-coated magnetic beads, and used to capture their cognate targets for subsequent identification. Finally, an Enzyme-linked oligonucleotide assay (ELONA) could be employed against whole larvae lysate, Excretory/Secretory antigens, and/or muscle larvae surface protein preparations.

13.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD12-FBZSH9-AptaTrich	D-PhD12-2	Aptamers set on whole larvae is selected	M29	10/12/2021		Aptamers have been sequenced

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD12-FBZSH9-AptaTrich	M-3	The aptamers bind to <i>Trichinella spiralis</i> ML	M36	No		

13.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

No details provided

13.6. Publications and patents

No publications produced during this period.

13.7. Impact and Relevance

The partners involved in the project offer various elements of expertise to optimally support a PhD student in the development of a new method. The partners come from institutes with a wide interdisciplinary background.

ANSES laboratories conduct their activities in three major areas: animal health and well-being, food safety (chemical and biological) and plant health. The French NRL is also an OIE Collaborating Centre, it is part of the Animal Health Laboratory of Anses, which is internationally renowned and carries out critical missions for France, Europe and World in the field of animal health and public health, food safety, epidemiology. Researchers of the NRL work in close collaboration with medical doctors, veterinarians and give their expertise when outbreaks occur.

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) is the German national scientific institution in the area of consumer health protection, food safety, authenticity and risk assessment/ risk communication. The NRL for *Trichinella* mainly operates in the field of diagnostics, food safety and risk assessment, but also provide consultant support in human diagnostics.

The Canadian National Reference Centre for Parasitology (NRCP) is located within the Research Institute of the McGill University Health Centre (RI-MUHC) and provides reference serological and molecular diagnostics for parasitic diseases. Investigators at the Centre are active in several areas, including clinical parasitology, parasite diagnostics, parasite epidemiology, vaccine immunology, as well as cold climate parasitoses and circumpolar health.

The existing close collaboration between the partners, which operate between the medical, veterinary and food science fields, will facilitate the success of the proposed PhD project under a One Health approach.

13.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p><u>Human biological samples</u> The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate authorizations will be sought to collect the Human samples.</p> <p><u>Non-EU countries (Canada)</u> The beneficiary must provide details on the material which will be imported to/exported from EU and confirm that the adequate authorisations have been obtained.</p> <p>This project is focusing on laying hens. Further details are needed on the researcher's interaction and 'use' of a legal animals (e.g., the layers hens). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so please comment on any implications for the animals. Please describe how the animals' welfare are protected and considered (e.g., if the chickens are affected when taking samples, even if the work is dealing with faeces as these types of study can, this can still include restricting the animals or manipulating diets, etc, all which can have an impact on the animals). Please provide a statement on the 3Rs aspects of this work If Ethical Approval is required please state which Research Ethics Committee this will be sent to.</p>	<p><u>Human biological samples</u> All serums have already been sampled with the authorizations that must be obtained in accordance with Canadian laws, and within the framework of the NRC in place at the McGill Institute.</p> <p><u>Non-EU countries (Canada)</u> Both the French and German NRLs have defined <i>Trichinella</i> positive and negative pig sera already available in their respective repository and the Canadian reference center has defined some <i>Trichinella</i> positive Human sera in its repository. Each project participant will test the effectiveness of the test on its own samples. Therefore, no shipment is planned. If, however, the evolution of the project leads to shipments, the Nagoya protocol will be respected.</p> <p>This project will not focus on laying hens. On the other hand, we will have to use mice to obtain larvae. Their number will be very limited since each mouse contains thousands of larvae. The experiments on mice were approved by an ethical review committee (C2EA-16 Comité d'éthique ComEth ANSES/ENVA/UPEC, under the approval number: saisine 12-0048, ComEth 13/11/12-4).</p>

13.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

None detailed.

13.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

13.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Not Applicable

13.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	Science Happy Hour		
Date:	December 3rd, 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	Yes
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes

Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	20	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

14. PhD13- VIMOGUT

14.1. Summary

The VIMOGUT project consists of *in vivo* analysis of the microbiome in the caecum of healthy broilers and the set-up of an *in vitro* model to study the transmission dynamics of antimicrobial resistance in caecal microbial communities. In the first period of 2021, the PhD student has worked on both aspects of the project.

Further data analysis was performed for the *in vivo* component to complete the first manuscript titled “Succession in the caecal microbiota of developing broilers colonised by Extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli*”, which was submitted in September 2021. The collection of additional broiler caecal samples at farms was postponed due to COVID-19. Preparations were arranged with the hope to perform the sampling at the end of 2021. However, due to the Avian influenza outbreaks in the Netherlands, the sampling at the broiler farms had to be postponed once more until further notice, hopefully, the first quarter of 2022.

The *in vitro* chicken caecum model was first tested in 2020, after which further optimisation was necessary. Challenges with the oxygen sensors were under investigation and solved. The initial tests in the semi-automated *in vitro* chicken have been run for ~8 days. Analyses of data collected (real-time process monitoring and 16S rRNA gene analysis) have shown reproducibility and reliability of the system between experiments. Inoculation and intervention experiments have been delayed due to a hardware failure in the *in vitro* system secondary to a power failure at WBVR in October 2021. Applikon engineers are currently working on this issue.

14.2. Overview of project progress

In WP 1, the data analysis from the first experiment has been finalised. The student has written the results into a manuscript submitted to a peer-reviewed journal.

For WP2, the *in vitro* chicken caecum model was adjusted and optimised to minimise the presence of oxygen in the culture media, underlined by the high presence of anaerobic bacteria in the microbiome. Tests to monitor the presence of oxygen in the system were performed with a different set of sensors. The first experiments used two feed additive phytochemicals as an intervention strategy to test the system. 16S rRNA genes sequencing and microbiome analyses were performed for different test runs.

In preparation for the planned experiments, an approach of fluorescent labelling of plasmids has been selected, which was previously carried out at the University of Copenhagen. A short-term mission proposal was submitted for the student to visit this research group to create her own fluorescently labelled plasmids efficiently. The PhD student was granted the STM and will start her work in May 2022.

14.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Before the start of VIMOGUT, a number of broiler caecal samples was collected, on which 16S rRNA gene sequencing was performed. For WP1, additional samples of this collection were sequenced for VIMOGUT to allow proper statistical analysis of the data set. Challenges in the analysis arose due to a difference in 16S rRNA genes amplification between these datasets. It was impractical to analyse both datasets together due to the nature of the research question and the possible bias influencing the results of the microbiome downstream analysis. Precautions have been made to prevent this problem from occurring in any other datasets generated during VIMOGUT.

From the data generated in VIMOGUT, a manuscript has been prepared and submitted and is currently under peer review. In this study we describe the ESBL-*E. coli* prevalence and successional dynamics of the caecal microbiome of developing broilers in a commercial flock during their production life (age 0 to 35). Broilers were discriminated as ESBL-*E. coli* colonised or not by selective culturing. Using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, we compared the richness, evenness and composition of the caecal microbiota of both broiler groups and assessed the combined role of age and ESBL status on the microbiota.

We have observed a significant linear trend in the proportions of ESBL-*E. coli* throughout the broilers' production round; $X^2(1, N = 12) = 28.4, p < .001$ (Fig 1). Over time, the microbial richness was consistently higher in non colonised broilers, but significant differences between both groups were found exclusively on day three; Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $p = .016$ (Fig 2). Multivariate analysis showed no explanatory power of ESBL status, while age explained 14% of the compositional variation of the caecal microbiome, $F(2, 66) = 6.47, p = .001$ (Fig. 3).

Figure 1. ESBL-*E. coli* prevalence throughout the broiler production round.

Figure 2. Comparison of microbial richness between ESBL-*E. coli* colonised and non-colonised broilers.

Figure 3. Principal coordinate analyses based on Bray Curtis dissimilarity metrics (BC-PCoA). Changes in the caecal microbial community composition over time (day 0-35).

In conclusion, we have assessed the role of ESBL-producing *E. coli* in the successional dynamics of the cecal microbiome in developing broilers and showed that the presence of ESBL-producing *E. coli* is associated with mild but consistent reductions in alpha diversity and transient microbial compositional differences. We also reported the clonal spread of ESBL-*E. coli* and point to the farm environment as a likely source for ESBLs.

For WP2, an *in vitro* chicken caecum model was set up. The model was challenged by difficulties using the oxygen sensors for which the calibration to a completely anaerobic environment appears to be inaccurate. Replacement with new sensors did not help overcome this problem, and tests with different sensors (e.g. redox) were performed.

Additional optimisation of the system included the addition of a second gas inlet that creates an overlay of nitrogen on top of the culture media in the bioreactor to prevent any oxygen from dissolving into the culture. Two experiments were performed in which phytochemical feed additives were added to the culture at 3 days after the start of the experiment. After DNA isolation, 16S rRNA genes amplicon sequencing was performed, and the data was analysed. In both experiments, the relative abundance of

phyla of the *in vitro* microbiome was relatively stable and consisted primarily of anaerobic bacteria, confirming that the *in vitro* system can maintain the main broilers caecal microbial communities (Fig. 4). The control bioreactors in which no intervention was added showed similar stabilisation of the microbiome after 3 days, suggesting that any interventions can be started from the time point.

Figure 4. Relative abundance of different phyla measured in the *in vitro* caecal microbiome. The numbers below the bar indicate the experiment timeline (when the sample was acquired). The two upper plots represent the experiment 1, the lower plots are for experiment 2. The left panels represent the control reactors, while the right panels show the effects of two phytochemicals which are added to the bioreactors from day 3.

The chicken caecal *in vitro* system is in continuous optimisation. In the previous months, an experiment was performed to evaluate the effect of gassing type on the *in vitro* caecal microbiome composition. Maintaining adequate anaerobic conditions is essential to simulate the chicken caecal microbiome. In this experiment, both bioreactors were supplied with nitrogen (N₂) for eight days to create an anaerobic environment; one bioreactor was supplied with N₂ continuously via sparger (into the media) and the other bioreactor via an overlay (on the top of the media).

Preliminary results showed that the type of gassing could influence the relative abundance of the *in vitro* chicken caecal composition (Fig. 5). However, no significant differences in microbiome composition were found between the two types of gassing. Additional analyses are currently being performed.

Figure 5. Differences in phyla relative abundance observed between overlay and sparger gassing. N2 delivery via sparger stimulated the grow of specific taxa of the phylum *Proteobacteria* compared to overlay.

14.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD13-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR	D-PhD13-1.1	Manuscript on preliminary findings for the relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation.	M36		M45	Challenges in data analysis delayed the preparation of the manuscript.
	D-PhD13-1.2	Manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome	M48		M56	Farm visits could not be planned in the first half of 2021 due to COVID-19.

		maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.				
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PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD13-FBZ8/AMR 2-VIMOGUT-AMR	M6	Perform initial test runs on <i>in vitro</i> gut model to determine CFU for reliable ESBL colonisation.	M36		M48	Delayed due to closure of lab facilities in 2020.
	M7	Write manuscript on initial results relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL gut colonisation.	M36		M45	Delayed due to closure of lab facilities in 2020.
	M8	Perform 16S sequencing and analysis of caecal samples from OH-EJP VIMOGUT.	M42		M52	Samples were not collected yet due to the inability to visit broiler farms during an outbreak of avian influenza in the Netherlands.
	M9	Write manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.	M48		M56	Samples were not collected yet due to the inability to visit broiler farms during an outbreak of avian influenza in the Netherlands.

14.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Peer review discussion meeting	Communication	12/01/21	GSS-WUR
Metagenomics webinar (DADA2)	Data analysis	21/01/21	Loop Genomics
Scicom IG meeting	Communication	16/02/21	WUR

Imposter syndrome	Personal development	24/02/21	
7 th OHEJP cogwheel workshop	Science	25/02/21	CACTUS
Global Tricycle Surveillance ESBL <i>E.coli</i>	Science	03/03/21	WHO
Applications of -omics technologies in poultry health and productivity : where are we now ?	Science	22/04/21	<i>IHSIG</i>
Designing and attractive and effective poster	Communication	17/05/21	PE&RC - WSG
Effective and efficient verbal communication in academia and beyond	Communication	26/05/21	PE&RC - WSG
Mindful productivity for PhD Candidates	Personal development	28/05/21	PE&RC - WSG
Multivariate analysis course	Statistical analysis	23 – 25, 28 – 29 June 2021	PE&RC – WSG
RMarkdown	Data analysis	5-6 July 2021	VLAG - WSG

14.6. Publications and patents

One manuscript has been submitted for publication. A preprint is available at <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-929974/v1>.

14.7. Impact and Relevance

The initial *in vivo* 16s data set analysis has been performed with Dr. Stephanie Jurgburg at iDiv Germany. The positive collaboration in the VIMOGUT project has led to the preparation of a new collaborative project which started in 2021.

The *in vitro* gut model experiment to compare the effects of phytochemicals described above has been conducted collaborating with Dr. Adam Roberts at Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine. The PhD student of Dr. Roberts, Mr. William Hutton visited WBVR at the end of 2020 for one month to perform this experiment. The collaboration has boosted the implementation of the *in vitro* model. Furthermore, a consortium led by Dr. Roberts has submitted a pre-proposal and is now preparing a full proposal for the JPI-AMR call in which the *in vitro* gut model at WBVR is an important component.

As part of the work for VIMOGUT, the PhD has engaged with the research group of Prof. Luca Guardabassi at the University of Copenhagen to receive technical assistance in constructing fluorescently labelled plasmids, as the group previously mentioned described it in the literature. As such, she has been granted a short-term mission to visit Prof. Guardabassi's group for nine weeks in 2022. The fluorescently labelled plasmids will be utilised in the *in vitro* model to study the host range of ESBL-encoding plasmids.

14.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
<p>This project is using broiler chickens at conventional farms. Further details are needed on the researcher's interaction and 'use' of a legal animals (e.g., the broiler chickens). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so please comment on any implications for the the broiler chickens from sampling etc.</p> <p>Please describe how the animals' welfare are protected and considered (e.g., if the chickens are affected when taking samples, even if the work is dealing with faeces as these types of study can, this can still include restricting the animals or manipulating diets, etc, all which can have an impact on the animals).</p> <p>Please provide a statement on the 3Rs aspects of this work</p> <p>If Ethical Approval is required please state which Research Ethics Committee this will be sent to.</p>	<p>During the VIMOGUT project, sampling at conventional broiler farms and possibly slaughterhouses will be carried out.</p> <p>If samples are taken at slaughterhouses, the intestinal tract of animals will be collected after slaughter and evisceration are carried out. No changes are made to the standard procedures of the site and no additional animals are slaughtered for the benefit of the research.</p> <p>For the sampling at farms, only conventional broilers will be used with no restrictions or manipulation of the animals' diets.</p> <p>Animals will not be sacrificed for the research carried out for VIMOGUT unless approval has been given by the local animal welfare committee (IvD) at WUR and the national board on animal experiments (CCD), as per local guidelines. Sampling at conventional broiler farms will include the collection of fresh droppings for which animals may be briefly isolated to relieve themselves. Handling of the animals will only be performed after careful instruction and under the constant supervision of a trained veterinarian.</p> <p>As per local law in the Netherlands, the 3Rs are always considered when animal experiments or on-site sampling is performed. The <i>in vitro</i> model that is set up during VIMOGUT is part of the strategy to replace the need for animal experiments in microbiota research. To refine the experiments and reduce the number of animals that are sacrificed, fresh droppings will be used for this study instead of caecal content of the animals, unless there is there is a clear need for the use of caecal content. As mentioned above, permission will be sought from the local animal welfare committee IvD and the national board on animal experiments CCD.</p>

14.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay

			D2	M48	M56	No planned farm visits as early 2021 COVID-19 & late 2021 Avian influenza outbreak Sampling planned 05-09/22		
			D3	M60	M68	Lab closure during 2020		
			M6	M36	M48	Lab closure during 2020		
			M8	M42	M50	No planned farm visits as early 2021 COVID-19		
			M9	M48	M56	No planned farm visits as early 2021 COVID-19 & late 2021 Avian influenza outbreak Sampling planned 05-09/22		

Comments:

The COVID-19 crisis has affected the feasibility of meeting the deadlines of the milestones. The work on the *in vitro* model has had significant delays in Y3 due to the temporary closure of the laboratory facilities and the postponement of an essential course to commence this part of the work properly, but progress has since been made and most of the work will be delivered by the end of the project.

For the *in vivo* work, sampling at farms has been delayed until the PhD student has been vaccinated against COVID-19. Preparations are made to start this work in Q3/Q4 of 2021.

14.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

As described above, the COVID-19 crisis has had effects on the planning of the work in this PHD project.

14.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Currently not applicable

14.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Presentation of poster and participation in 3-minute Thesis competition.		
Date:	9 - 11 June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g., Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

15. PhD14- ToxSauQMRA

15.1. Summary

The present research project aims to answer to the scientific question: “What is the attribution of the traditional raw pork products in the human *Toxoplasma* infection? “ based on three main areas of study consisting of (i) a thorough investigation of *T.gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst) (WP1); (ii) evaluate the impact of the manufacturing process (including different incorporation rates of nitrites and NaCl) and the conservation of dry sausage on the viability of *T. gondii* (WP2); (iii) a quantitative microbiological risk assessment analysis to be conducted for the various raw pork products (dry sausage, dry ham, etc) (WP3). The 3-year project spans over four Annual Periods (Y2-Y5). The key activities, results and achievements for the reporting period of January to December 2021 are the following:

Key scientific results:

1. Complete artificial digestion of meat samples from “tissue cysts” pig group
2. Complete MC-PCR analysis of tissue samples and dry sausages
3. Complete data analysis of *T. gondii* tissue distribution and resistance in dry sausages

Challenges:

1. Delay in PCR reagents (Taq polymerase, primers, etc) delivery (manufacture, synthesis, etc) due to internationally high demand of PCR Covid19 testing
2. Optimisation of MC-PCR protocol with a new UV-light lamp according to the latest published protocol (Algaba et al., 2017)
3. Work overcharge of several partners involved in the analysis of *T.gondii* prevalence in relevant meat products

Adaptations:

1. Involvement of under-graduate students for helping us with the digestions and PCR
2. Selecting the MC-PCR protocol that gave us the best results in terms of reproducibility (Opsteegh, et al., 2010)
3. Prolonging the Milestone (M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-02) and Deliverable (D-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-WP3.1) to year 5

15.2. Overview of project progress

Concerning the project progress in various tasks and work packages for the last 12 months, we are clearly within our objectives and goals since for:

WP1 - Investigation of *T.gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst)

WP1-T1: Experimental infection of pigs: – successfully completed in 2020

WP1-T2: Predilection sites of *T.gondii* in pigs: – successfully completed in 2021

WP2 - Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* during the production and storage of dry sausages and dry ham

WP2-T1: Manufacture of dry sausages and dry ham: – successfully completed in 2020

WP2-T2: Assessment of the persistence of viable *T. gondii* in pork delicatessen: – successfully completed in 2021

WP3 - Quantitative microbiological risk assessment

WP3-T1 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* in pigs and pork products: – underway/ to be completed by June

WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections: – started/ to be completed by the end of 2021

15.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Within the WP1 (Investigation of *T.gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst)), we have finished the work of WP1-T2: Predilection sites of *T.gondii* in pigs, which had been delayed due to covid 1st and 2nd confinement. Within the WP2 - Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* during the production and storage of dry sausages and dry ham we have worked mainly on Task 2: WP2-T2: Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* since Task 1: WP2-T1: Manufacture of dry sausages and dry ham was already completed. However, a short summary of WP1-T1 and WP2-T1 is mentioned for a better understanding of the workflow over the last 3 years. All the work has been completed with the help of external partners: Institut du Porc (IFIP) and Université de Champagne-Ardennes (URCA).

For WP1-T1, the focus was to be able to collect meat massively contaminated with *Toxoplasma gondii*. Therefore, an infection with a high dose (1000) of parasites was carried out (strain ME49) in pigs (WP1-T1). These tests were carried out with 2 parasitic forms that may be at the origin of contamination in pigs: the oocyst (ingestion from the environment) and the tissue cyst (ingestion from infested meat). Three pigs were inoculated with oocysts and 3 others with tissue cysts. Serological monitoring of the serum of these pigs was carried out by Modified Agglutination Test (MAT) on a weekly basis until D30, then every 15 days until the end of the protocol (3-4 months/80-90 kg). After euthanasia of the MAT positive pigs, 4 tissues /pig were collected for analysis: heart, breast, shoulder and ham, as tissues used in the manufacture of dry sausage. For each of the anatomical regions studied, the different muscles (4 for breast, 7 for shoulder and 13 for ham) were pooled. Some 40 supplementary muscles per carcass were individually collected, representing the most important anatomical regions. One hind leg was collected for each pig for dry ham production.

Concerning the WP1-T2, the main focus was to identify the predilection sites of *T.gondii* presence in pig tissues. Therefore, mouse bioassays and quantitative PCR were performed on a part (200g) of the pooled sample per region. The remaining parts of the pools were used for industrial (salting, smoking, etc) processing (WP2). The analysis of tissue samples ([breast, shoulder, ham, heart + 40 supplementary muscles] x 6 pigs) by MC-PCR, delayed by the 1st and the 2nd confinement due to COVID19 sanitary crisis in France, has now been completed for both parasitic stages (oocysts and tissue cysts). This involved the digestion, DNA extraction and PCR for each individual tissue sample.

Within the WP2-T1 the manufacture of dry sausages was carried out on a pilot scale by IFIP, according to a protocol representative of those used by a commercial factory. Briefly, after mincing, the muscle pool was divided into seven portions (corresponding to the 7 combinations of nitrites (as sodium NaNO₂ nitrites) and NaCl concentrations that was to be compared: 120 (maximum dose of nitrites mentioned in the Code of Practice), 60 and 0 ppm of nitrites combined with the usual dose of 26 g/kg NaCl or a reduced dose of 20 g/kg NaCl or 0 g/kg NaCl. For each of the tested formulations, 3 dry sausages were collected at different dates (D0, D2, D10, D20, D30 and D50). On each analysis date, IFIP has carried out a physico-chemical monitoring (pH, Aw, weight loss) and a count of the lactic flora from a dry sausage per formulation, in particular to check that the process is running properly. A total of 168 dry sausages was required for this study (3 dry sausages x 7 recipes x 6 analysis dates for *T. gondii* monitoring as well as 1 dry sausage x 7 recipes x 6 analysis dates for physico-chemical and bacteriological analyses). The dry hams were meant to be sent and manufactured by INRAe Corte (Corsica), using two traditional salting techniques (a long one: 2.5 days/kg and a short one: 1 day/kg). However due to a local strike in the harbour of Marseille, the hams arrived with 10 days of delay, causing the sanitary quality of meat to be questionable in terms of manufacturing. Therefore, a long salting technique has been applied only, with 300g of product that was taken at D30 and D90 due to Covid19 shutdown.

For WP2-T2 the main focus was the analysis of the dry sausages and ham for the presence of viable *T. gondii* by bioassay in mice that has been performed in the animal facility of URCA. In total 90 mouse bioassays were performed (1 dry sausage x 7 recipes x 6 analysis dates x 2 mice + 2 dry hams x 3

analysis dates) with the last data being collected 6 weeks after the last bioassay was performed. During this time, the presence of *T. gondii* DNA in the inocula, resulting from the dry sausage digestion, was quantified by URCA using a (conventional) qPCR and by ANSES by MC-qPCR developed by Opsteegh et al., (2010).

Within the WP3 - Quantitative microbiological risk assessment, we focused on the WP3-T1 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* in pigs and pork products and WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections. During Y4, the review of the prevalence data of *T. gondii* in pigs and pork products was conducted. Data from various studies involving long-last processing pork delicatessen (Jambon de Parme; Jambon Serrano, etc) started to be collated, building on the systematic reviews performed for EFSA and EJP Toxosources. In addition, we initiated the first steps in WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections by providing the animal *T. gondii* prevalence for the QMRA model that needs to be built.

Key scientific results:

1. Complete artificial digestion of meat samples from “tissue cysts” pig group
2. Complete MC-PCR analysis of tissue samples and dry sausages
3. Complete data analysis of *T. gondii* tissue distribution and resistance in dry sausages

Challenges:

1. Delay in PCR reagents (Taq polymerase, primers, etc) delivery (manufacture, synthesis, etc) due to internationally high demand of PCR Covid19 testing
2. Optimisation of MC-PCR protocol with a new UV-light lamp according to the latest published protocol (Algaba et al., 2017)
3. Work overcharge of several partners involved in the analysis of *T. gondii* prevalence in relevant meat products

Adaptations:

1. Involvement of under-graduate students for helping with the digestions and PCR techniques
2. Selecting the MC-PCR protocol that gave the best results in terms of reproducibility (Opsteegh, et al., 2010)
3. Prolonging the Milestone (M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-02) and Deliverable (D-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-WP3.1) to year 5

15.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD14-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA	D-PhD14-1 WP2.2	Final report on the <i>T. gondii</i> detection in collected tissues after processing	M46		M46	On time

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD14-FBZ4-ToxSauQ MRA	M-PhD14-01 WP3.1	Report on prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> in various dry pork delicatessen	M46		M54	It's a very fastidious task, involving intensive-labour and precise definitions and details with several other partners involved. The work that is demanded is overpassing our optimistic expectations. We are expecting a 6-month delay since the other partners involved in this task are currently overwhelmed.
	M-PhD14-02 M-PhD14- 01	Data on quantitative PCR, Magnetic-capture PCR and mouse bioassay on tested tissues after processing to be collected	M46	Yes		Being helped by under-graduate students we advanced quicker than initially planned.
	M-PhD14-03 M-PhD14-02	Prevalence of <i>T.gondii</i> in relevant meat products to be collected	M46	No	M54	It's a very fastidious task, involving intensive-labour and precise definitions and details with several other partners involved. The work that is demanded is overpassing our optimistic expectations. We are expecting a 6-month delay since the other partners involved in this task are currently overwhelmed.

	M-PhD14-05 M-PhD14-03	Prevalence of <i>T.gondii</i> in relevant meat products is provided as input to QMRA	M51	No	M55	A delay is expected due to the adjournment of the previous task.
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15.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
French as a foreign language course elementary level	Language	18/01/21 - 15/04/21	Université Paris-Est Créteil
The challenges of the bioeconomy	Bio-economics	19/04/21 -22/04/21	Agreenium, AgroParisTech
Scientific integrity and research ethics	Ethics	06/05/21 – 21/05/21	Université Paris-Est Créteil
DataCamp – courses on R programming	Programming	10/07/21 – 10/06/22	Online courses provided by DataCamp

15.6. Publications and patents

For this period Filip DAMEK, presented his PhD project with the results up to date and the results from Toxosources concerning *T.gondii* animal prevalence review as a poster, at the 3rd Annual Scientific Meeting of EJPs (09.-11.06., Copenhagen, Denmark) (n=2). During this time, these results were presented at the 28th International Conference of the World Association for the Advancement of Veterinary Parasitology (19.-22.07., Dublin, Ireland) as posters (n=2). Results were also published as oral presentations at the 13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology (12.-16.10., Belgrade, Serbia) (n=2) and at the annual symposium of the French Society of Medical Mycology and Parasitology (28.-29.10., Lyon, France) (n=1). Furthermore, his results will be submitted for publication in a Special Issue "**Advances in the Diagnosis, Detection, Epidemiology, and Control of *Toxoplasma gondii***", in collaboration with /Microorganisms/ (ISSN 2076-2607, ImpactFactor 4.152)

15.7. Impact and Relevance

From the beginning, the PhD project was built as an interdisciplinary project involving partners from the Vet (Anses, RIVM), Med (URCA, RIVM) and industrial (IFIP) area. The topic itself touches all three domains, fitting perfectly into the OneHealth approach. Therefore, the PhD student is working in an interdisciplinary environment, gathering vets, researchers, doctors, pharmacists, engineers, technicians with a broad spectrum of activities such as parasitology, food-product manufacture, risk assessment analysis, statistics, epidemiology. Precisely, the experimental infection of pigs has been performed by JRU BIPAR, the sausages were manufactured by Institut du Porc (IFIP), and tested both by JRU BIPAR and URCA. Later the results will be interpreted with the help of statisticians (ANSES) and the QMRA model will be run and performed in RIVM. The PhD project and the PhD student are playing perfectly the role of a pivot within this interdisciplinary environment. Without them this part of the research would not have been possible.

15.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.	All new personnel working in the ANSES laboratories must undergo a ½ day training/visit of the laboratories with the local Health and Safety correspondent. During this visit, the personnel are highlighted the specific dangers and critical points for each section of the lab and are informed about the relevant local and national guidelines that needs to be followed. The visit ends with the signature of a training sheet summarizing all this points. One copy being kept by the personnel.
This project is focusing on pigs. Further details are needed on the researcher's interaction and 'use' of a legal animals (e.g., the pigs). If these are not experimental animals as defined in Directive 2010/63/EU they are still legal animals through national animal welfare laws so please comment on any implications for the animals. Please describe how the animals' welfare are protected and considered (e.g., if the pigs are affected when taking samples, even if the work is dealing with faeces as these types of study can, this can still include restricting the animals or manipulating diets, etc, all which can have an impact on the animals). Please provide a statement on the 3Rs aspects of this work If Ethical Approval is required please state which Research Ethics Committee this will be sent to.	The entire experimental infection has been already approved by the local Ethical Committee (ANSES – ENVA –UPEC) and the Ministry of Research under the number 18-035 (n° APAFIS: 2018032908554996) where all these aspects (3R, welfare, etc) has been detailed.

15.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

No specific delay for specific activities just a general delay in PCR reagents delivery. Due to an important internationally demand for PCR reagents to be used in the COVID19 testing (diagnostic), the R&D activities are not on the priority list for the biochemical companies generating delays in work plan execution, duties, tasks or reporting.

15.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No

Other risks (please describe)	Yes (see below)
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Additional information:

Filip DAMEK is an excellent PhD student, dynamic and pro-active. From the beginning of the PhD project, we had to deal with several unexpected problems, but this has not discouraged him, demonstrating he can adapt and is well suited to finalise this project successfully. The challenges included:

- Delay in PCR reagents delivery. Due to an important international demand for PCR reagents to be used in the COVID19 testing (diagnostic), the R&D activities are not on the priority list for the biochemical companies generating delays in work plan execution, duties, tasks or reporting.
- The collaboration with RIVM is excellent with monthly meetings and ad-hoc discussions to proceed with the PhD project. However, a 3-month internship of Filip in RIVM was discussed at the beginning of his PhD. This internship has been postponed due to COVID19 safety protocols since and has been fulfilled only in October-November 2021. However, a second internship of Filip in RIVM will take place in April-May 2022.

15.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Filip DAMEK has been involved in the EJP JRP Toxosources, as part of the Anses team, participating at the kick-off meeting (3-4.02, Copenhagen, Denmark) and since then participating at all the videoconferences of the various WPs, where Anses is involved in. He took a very active role in the activities of WP2 (human/animal prevalence review, questionnaires, etc), as well as in activities of WP3 (T.gondii detection in RTE salads).

Similarly, part of the Anses team, Filip DAMEK is involved in the national research project n° 0917003490 financed by the French Ministry of Agriculture through the France Agri Mer agency with the title: Study of the tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage, gathering the above-mentioned partners (Ifip, URCA, Inrae Corte), representing at the same time the fundament/basis of his PhD programme.

15.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	28 th International Conference of the World Association for the Advancement of Veterinary Parasitology. Presentation of poster online		
Date:	19-22 July 2021		
Place:	Dublin, Ireland		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No

<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	No report	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	3rd OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Presentation of poster and participation in 3-minute Thesis competition.		
Date:	9-11 June 2021		
Place:	Copenhagen, Denmark and online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No

Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

16. PhD15- TRACE

16.1. Summary

Due to the COVID-19 crisis (which started just a few months after the start this PhD project) the PhD project is delayed by approximately 6 months. The PhD candidate worked on COVID19 in minks and published multiple papers on this topic. Regarding TRACE, previous year some progress was made on establishing optimisation of sample (pre)processing (enrichment) to make whole genome sequencing possible (WP1). The producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change in his product. For this reason, we had to start with another method (multi-primer enrichment), however we didn't succeed. In the second part of 2021 we started setting up a new enrichment method, based on probe capture enrichment. Because of the delay of WP1, we were not able to start in WP2 (phylogenetics) with the analyses of newly produced sequences. However, we started setting up a method for HEV analyses for timed phylogeny of known sequences from the NCBI. This should enable us to later apply this method for sequences we generated ourselves

16.2. Overview of project progress

WP1. During the first year of the project work was done to establish a sample (pre)processing (enrichment) to make whole genome sequencing possible. Different methods were used, and DNA depletion treatments were explored. mRNA of 18S (host) and 16S (bacterial) origin was successfully removed. HEV whole genome sequences were successfully generated using above enrichment methods and specific probes. The producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change in his product. By this reason we had to start with another method. We decided to develop a test based on multi primer sequencing method for HEV. Probably the genome structure of HEV is a little bit complicated therefore we didn't succeed with this method. In the second part of 2021, we started setting up a new enrichment method. This method is based on the principle of the first original procedure called probe capture enrichment. For this we had develop a completely new probe set before we could start to optimise the enrichment procedure. The first result look promising, whole genomes could be generated from our control sample and a positive faecal sample with a Ct of 24. The procedure now needs to be optimised to generate whole genomes from samples with a Ct value up to Ct30.

WP2. This work was planned to start in the beginning of 2021, due to the delay of WP1 we were not able to start in WP2 with the analyse of new produced sequences. However, we started setting up a method for HEV analyse for timed phylogeny of known sequences from the NCBI. With the idea that we can later apply the method for our own generated sequences.

WP3. Not planned to start yet.

Wp4. Not planned to start yet.

16.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Work Package 1 Whole genome sequencing.

During the first year of the project work was done to establish a sample (pre)processing (enrichment) to make whole genome sequencing possible. Different methods were used and DNA depletion treatments were explored. mRNA of 18S (host) and 16S (bacterial) origin was successfully removed. HEV whole genome sequences were successfully generated using above enrichment methods and specific primers. Currently work is done to analyse sensitivity.

The producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change in his product. For this reason we had to start with another method. We had a successful method for sequencing SARS-CoV-2, based on a multi primer sequencing method. We decided to develop a test based on the same principle for HEV. Probably the genome structure of HEV is a little bit complicated therefore we didn't succeed with this method.

In the second part of 2021, we started setting up a new enrichment method. This method is based on the principle of the first original procedure called probe capture enrichment. For this we had develop a completely new probe set before we could start to optimise the enrichment procedure. The first result look promising, whole genomes could be generated from our control sample and a positive faecal sample with a Ct of 24. The procedure now needs to be optimised to generate whole genomes from samples with a Ct value up to Ct30. HEV culture preceding sequencing may be considered to increase the amount of HEV virus (work on a culture method is part of BIOPIGEE project).

Work Package 2 HEV phylodynamics.

Using HEV whole genome sequences data generated in WP1, we will construct a timed phylogeny of HEV based on core-genome SNP analysis. From this analysis we can infer time-points of evolutionary divergence of different HEV types. Coupled to geographic location data of the isolates we will also include a spatial dimension to the phylogeny which will inform us on the geographical origin and spread of HEV types over time. Comparison of sequences over time will also be used to identify sequences that differ between time periods in which we observed a different epidemiology of HEV, giving indications of probable increased colonization success in pigs, increased environmental survival and/or increased virulence. This work was planned to start in the beginning of 2021, due to the delay of WP1 we were not able to start in WP2 with the analysis of newly produced sequences. However, we started setting up a method for HEV analysis for timed phylogeny of known sequences from the NCBI. With the idea that we will later be able to apply this method for sequences we (will) have generated ourselves.

Work Package 3 Identification of HEV virulence genes and HEV quasispecies.

Work on this work package is planned to start in month 54

Work Package 4 Data analyses and data evaluation

Work on this work package is planned to start in month 54

16.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD15-FBZ5-TRACE	D-PhD15-1.1	Sample processing protocol for HEV RNA positive target samples of different origin and associated deep sequencing procedure for HEV from such samples	M48		M54	Due to the producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change in his product. And a first attempt to develop a new method was unsuccessful. We were not able to make the delivery date.

	D-PhD15-2.2	Report/publication on HEV dynamics including information about the geographical origin of predominant virulent strains and identification of genetic traits changed over time.	M48		Not given	WP2 is dependent on WP1.
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PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD15-FBZ5-TRACE	M-PhD15-01	Detailed outline of PhD plan	M24		Yes	

16.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Digital innovations for One Health practitioners	Communications	15- 19 /021/2021	BfR

16.6. Publications and patents

No publications have been produced yet.

16.7. Impact and Relevance

OHEJP Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) Updated List and Descriptions of Priority Research and Integrative topics: "risk factors and infection dynamics".

Development and harmonisation of deep sequencing-based methods for detection and tracing of foodborne zoonotic agents and emerging threats have been identified as a main research item within the updated EJP One Health SRA. Data from this project will lead to improved surveillance and more harmonized data analyses on the foodborne zoonosis HEV. This will contribute to broader and flexible actions to detect actual hazards, main reservoirs, trends and routes of transmission as well as common approach and timely analysis and data sharing which will be needed more and more with ongoing globalization.

16.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate authorizations will be sought to collect the Human samples. Please reconfirm that this work is not using or interacting with animals directly, please reconfirm this.	In this case the appropriate authorization regarding the collection of human HEV sequences is RIVM itself. In addition, we confirm that this research is not using animals directly.

16.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

In 2020 there was much impact of COVID-19 on this project, and we extended the delivery month. Although there is still some impact of COVID-19, we do not expect a lot of extra extension.

16.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

16.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

This PhD project relates to the OHEJP project BIOPIGEE: HEV viability screening method developed In BIOPIGEE may be used In TRACE as applicable.

16.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	3 rd OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Participation in 3-minute Thesis competition.		
Date:	10 th June 2021		
Place:	Copenhagen, Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No

Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

17. PhD16- Codes4Strains

17.1. Summary

Aim

Whole genome sequencing allows the tracking of pathogenic strains and informs infection control, diagnostic and sometimes treatment strategies. To track strains globally, and as they spread between the environment, food, animals and humans, universal strain nomenclatures are necessary. The core genome Multilocus Sequence Typing (cgMLST) approach is an accurate, reproducible and portable strain genotyping method that underlies widely used strain nomenclatures, in which groups are generally determined by single-linkage clustering. However, cgMLST groups are unstable due to the possibility of group fusion upon subsequent sampling. Recently, a new coding approach named LIN (Life Identification Number) was introduced by Marakeby et al. (1). It provides a numerical code for each genome based on its similarity (estimated using the Average Nucleotide Identity, ANI) to the closest genome already encoded. As LIN codes are attributed to genome rather than groups, they are stable. A common feature of both approaches is that single linkage groups and LINcodes can be defined using several similarity cutoffs, in which case they inherently convey phylogenetic proximity information. cgMLST additionally provides, through the number of allelic mismatches among cgMLST profiles, intuitive human-understandable metrics of differences among strains involved in epidemiological events (e.g., '5 cgMLST allele differences').

The aim of the PhD project is to develop a novel genome-based genotyping approach taking the best of the two above classification approaches, i.e., combining the advantages of cgMLST (discrimination, standardization) with those of the LIN code approach (complete stability). That is, we aim to develop and explore the strain classification utility of cgMLST-based LIN code (cgLINcodes) systems, where the pairwise distance is based on the number of allelic mismatches, rather than ANI. We also aim to compare the cgLINcodes approach with other existing classification approaches: the SNP address and multi-level single-linkage classifications (Multilevel Single Linkage, MLSL). We use *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp) and *Escherichia coli* (Ec) as two important pathogens to develop and evaluate our approach.

Report on the period of January to December 2021

Before the reporting period, we had selected our pilot genome dataset for the pathogen Kp (December 2019, D-PhD16-2.1).

We developed procedures (bioinformatics, algorithmic) to follow our goal of a cgMLST-based LIN code systems. First, we generated cgMLST profiles from genomes, using defined schemes. To this aim, the choice and the evaluation of the cgMLST schemes was finalized, for Kp and Ec (D-PhD16-3.1).

As a second task, the development of the cgMLST-based LIN code algorithm has been defined and a bioinformatics implementation was developed in Python (D-PhD16-3.2).

During this reporting period, we have consolidated our analyses of LINcodes and their comparison with MLSL. We have developed a novel way to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust; we have optimized our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with previous nomenclature identifiers from 7-gene MLST; we have defined the optimal input order for LIN encoding; we have compared the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric; we devised a method to identify recombination in cgMLST data; we have incorporated the MLSL identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available; and have submitted for publication a manuscript on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications (D-PhD16-4.1).

References:

1. Marakeby, H. et al. A System to Automatically Classify and Name Any Individual Genome-Sequenced Organism Independently of Current Biological Classification and Nomenclature. *PLOS ONE* 9, e89142 (2014).

17.2. Overview of project progress

The initial objectives proposed for the PhD project are the following:

- To define a collection of pilot dataset of genomes including published outbreak sets
- To develop the cgLINcode approach and compare with MLSL and SNPaddress approaches on large genomic datasets
- To simulate genomic evolution and use the three approaches to encode resulting evolved genomes; compare resulting codes with expectations
- To write publications on the cgLINcodes concept and implementation with comparison with MLSL and SNPaddress approaches
- To disseminate the cgLINcodes approach towards collaborating partner institutes and to evaluate this approach in one Health and Global Health contexts
- To write-up the PhD dissertation

The first two objectives have been achieved over the period September 2019 – December 2020. The second objective was divided into 4 subtasks: define the cgMLST schemes to be used for the two pathogens; collect a full dataset of public genomic sequences and scan them to define their cgMLST allelic profiles; development of the cgLINcodes algorithm; and create and/or analyze the SNPaddress database and compare cgLINcodes with MLST and SNPaddress approaches.

We have decided to leave the simulation out of the scope of the PhD work, as the data analysis of the real dataset is thorough enough for us to conclude that LIN codes and MLSL provide fully congruent results. Therefore, there is no point in simulating datasets to evaluate the differential performance of one against the other method. This is an unexpected outcome of our evaluation of a large dataset of 7060 Kp genomes.

The scheduled work that is not complete yet is the development and analysis of the SNPaddress approach for Kp. We are first finalizing the manuscript on cgLINcodes for Kp, as this is the most innovative development, and the manuscript is already complex and long. We thus reserve the comparison with SNP address for the next period, or possibly for an ulterior project outside of the PhD work.

During this period, we have submitted for publication the manuscript on the cgLINcodes approach and posted it on bioRxiv.

The remaining objectives for the next period are (i) to disseminate this approach towards our partners and explore its practical implementation in a One Health context; and (ii) We also intend to apply the LIN code approach and the tools we developed (MSTclust and inheritance to nomenclature identifiers) to other pathogens, even though this was not initially planned.

17.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

D4.1. Simulated dataset analysed

We have decided to leave the simulation out of the scope of the PhD work, as the data analysis of the real dataset is thorough enough for us to conclude that LIN codes and MLSL provide fully congruent results. Therefore, there is no point in simulating datasets to evaluate the differential performance of one against the other method. This abandoned DL is largely compensated by our additional DLs outlined below.

D4.2. Publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications

The publication is posted on bioRxiv and under review in a journal; The current version of the abstract of the publication is the following:

Sublineages within microbial species can differ widely in their ecology and pathogenicity, and their precise definition is important in basic research and industrial or public health applications. Whereas the classification and naming of prokaryotes is unified at the species level and higher taxonomic ranks, universally accepted definitions of sublineages within species are largely missing, which introduces confusion in population biology and epidemiological surveillance.

Here we propose a broadly applicable genomic classification and nomenclature approach for bacterial strains, using the prominent public health threat *Klebsiella pneumoniae* as a model. Based on a 629-gene core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST) scheme, we devised a dual barcoding system that combines multilevel single linkage (MLSL) clustering and life identification numbers (LIN). Phylogenetic and clustering analyses of >7,000 genome sequences captured population structure discontinuities, which were used to guide the definition of 10 infra-specific genetic dissimilarity thresholds. The widely used 7-gene multilocus sequence typing (MLST) nomenclature was mapped onto MLSL sublineages (threshold: 190 allelic mismatches) and clonal group (threshold: 43) identifiers for backwards nomenclature compatibility. The taxonomy is publicly accessible through a community-curated platform (<https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>), which also enables external users' genomic sequences identification.

The proposed strain taxonomy combines two phylogenetically informative barcodes systems that provide full stability (LIN codes) and nomenclatural continuity with previous nomenclature (MLSL). This species-specific dual barcoding strategy for the genomic taxonomy of microbial strains is broadly applicable and should contribute to unify global and cross-sector collaborative knowledge on the emergence and microevolution of bacterial pathogens.

D4.3. (NEW) A novel tool to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust

To profile the population structure, we developed MSTclust (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/MSTclust>) and used this tool to perform single linkage (SL) clustering of allelic profiles into partitions, at all possible thresholds t (from 0 to 629 allelic differences). SL clustering was applied on the pairwise distances among allelic profiles, defined as the number of allele mismatches normalized by the number of loci with alleles called in both profiles (therefore accounting for missing data). For each threshold t , the degree of clustering (goodness-of-fit of the clustering to the population) of the corresponding allelic profile partitioning was assessed by three different measures: (i) The overall average silhouette width St (2), which estimates the overall clustering quality based on maximizing inter-group distances and minimizing intra-group distances; (ii) the clustering robustness index in face of data subsampling, estimated by the Wallace index Wt (3) ; and (iii) The adjusted Rand index Rt (4,5) to assess the global concordance between the SL partitioning and those induced by any external classifications. For the application on *Kp*, we used as external classifications the 7-gene MLST sequence types, subspecies and species classifications.

D4.4. (NEW) Optimization of our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with 7-gene MLST

In order to attribute to each sublineage (SL) and clonal group (CG), an identifier that would maximally reflect the widely adopted 7-gene ST identifier of the corresponding isolates, we developed a set of naming rules that prioritize the most abundant ST observed among isolates of each group.

We briefly describe the process for the clonal groups (CG) level, and it would also apply in the same way for sublineages (SL). The data (e.g., a list of CG-ST pairs) can be formalized as a bipartite graph, in which each CG or ST are nodes, and each CG-ST pair is an edge. The weight of each edge is equal to the number of isolates sharing the corresponding CG and ST identifiers. Based on this representation, the algorithm will consist in following all edges in the input graph, in the order of decreasing weight. The approach prioritizes the most frequent ST/CG pairs of isolates, i.e., those that are epidemiologically predominant, and thus naturally transfers to the CG nomenclature, the identifiers of the epidemiologically major STs. Rules were implemented to treat the cases of equality of representation of two or more STs

connected to the same CG. Once all edges were removed from the graph, it may happen that some CGs were not yet named (for example, because the identifier of their unique corresponding ST was already attributed to another CG). For these orphan CGs, iteratively, the attributed identifier corresponds to the maximal CG identifier already attributed, plus one. Finally, to highlight identifiers that were attributed with no reference to 7-gene MLST identifiers, their numbering was initiated at 10000.

D4.5. (NEW) Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric

We compared ANI-based distances with the number of mismatches between cgMLST profiles (Figure 1). While the ANI-based distances varied from 92.8% to 100%, the cgMLST distances varied from 0 to 100% (i.e., 629 allele mismatches). Although both distributions had four to five modes, the first two modes of the ANI distance distribution, composed of inter-phylogroup strain comparisons, were at 93.5% to 95.5% ANI, whereas in the cgMLST distribution these distance pairs were centered around 2%, corresponding to the first mode of this distribution. In turn, whereas intra-species cgMLST distances varied from 5% to 100%, the range was only 98% to 100% for ANI values.

Figure 1. The distribution of pairwise distances of 7060 genomes of Kp based on Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) and cgMLST. (A) Each point represents a pair of distances between two strains, the X-axis the distance cgMLST and the Y-axis the distance ANI, the distributions are shown on the outside of the graph. We have colored the points corresponding to intergroup and intragroup distance. (B) Distribution of cgMLST pairwise distance. (C) Distribution of ANI pairwise distance.

The ANI metric was not designed to define the similarity of closely related genomes, such as those of strains within species; for example, high similarity values (e.g., 99.9990% and 99.9991%) are not intuitive to compare. In addition, the ANI metric is non-reciprocal, is highly dependent on comparison parameters, and is sensitive to sequencing or assembly artifacts. These shortfalls of the ANI metric lead to imprecision and non-reproducibility that are particularly impactful for comparisons between very similar genomes.

In contrast, the metric based on a cgMLST scheme, comprising 629 highly conserved and syntenic genes, was appropriate to reveal discontinuities that are relevant for strain nomenclature purposes.

D4.6. (NEW) Designed a method to identify recombination in cgMLST profiles

Horizontal transfer of large portions of the genome can occur among isolates belonging to distinct KpSC phylogroups (6). Additionally, MLST or cgMLST alleles may have been transferred horizontally from non-KpSC members, for example *E. coli*. For the purpose of phylogeny-based classification, we excluded such hybrid genomes. To define genomes that result from large inter-phylogroup recombination events, we leveraged our gene-by-gene approach to define an original strategy, outlined briefly here: we first attempted to determine for each allele of each locus, its KpSC phylogroup of origin; we then quantified a phylogroup homogeneity index of each genome by simply summing phylogroup origins of individual loci over the 629 scgMLSTv2 loci. The index was defined as the number of loci in the predominant phylogroup, divided by the number of alleles called in the profile. We then established a distribution of the phylogroup homogeneity indices to define genomes as having a hybrid origin.

D4.7. (NEW) Integration of MLST identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available

The MLST nomenclature was incorporated into the Institut Pasteur *K. pneumoniae* MLST and whole genome MLST database (<https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>). For this purpose, classification schemes and attached information fields were implemented as a novel BIGSdb functionality in BIGSdb version 1.21.0. The cgMLST profile of all isolates with less than 30 missing cgMLST-629 alleles were assigned to a core genome sequence type (cgST), and these were grouped into single-linkage partitions at the 10 defined mismatch levels. For SL and CG levels, a custom classification group field (named SL or CG within the system) was populated with 7-gene MLST inherited identifiers. All cgMLST profiles and their corresponding classification identifiers were made available for public use.

To allow users to easily identify *K. pneumoniae* isolates, a profile matching functionality was developed, allowing them to search for cgMLST profiles related to a query genome sequence. This was implemented and is available from the website sequence query page (<https://bigsdb.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration.html#scheme-profile-clustering-setting-up-classification-schemes>). This functionality returns the classification identifiers (including MLST-inherited clonal group and sublineage identifiers) of the cgMLST profile that is most closely related to the query genomic sequence, along with its number of mismatches compared to the closest profile.

References:

1. Marakeby, H. et al. A System to Automatically Classify and Name Any Individual Genome-Sequenced Organism Independently of Current Biological Classification and Nomenclature. *PLOS ONE* 9, e89142 (2014).
2. Rousseeuw, P. J. Silhouettes: A graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 20, 53–65 (1987).
3. Wallace, D. L. A Method for Comparing Two Hierarchical Clusterings: Comment. *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* 78, 569–576 (1983).
4. Hubert, L. & Arabie, P. Comparing partitions. *J. Classif.* 2, 193–218 (1985).
5. Carriço, J. A. et al. Illustration of a Common Framework for Relating Multiple Typing Methods by Application to Macrolide-Resistant *Streptococcus pyogenes*. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 44, 2524–2532 (2006).
6. Holt, K. E. et al. Genomic analysis of diversity, population structure, virulence, and antimicrobial resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, an urgent threat to public health. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 112, E3574-81 (2015).

17.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD16-FBZ2/AMR6.1-Codes4strains	D-PhD16-3.4	SNapperDB Kp implemented for full dataset	M36		M48	We did not create SNapperDB for the pathogen Kp yet. We are finalizing the manuscript on cgLINcodes for Kp first.
	D-PhD16-4.1	Simulated dataset analysed	M42		M48	Priority to writing the publication on the cgLINcodes approach
	D-PhD16-4.2	Publication on LINcode approach and comparison with cgMLST and SNP address approaches	M48		M48	
	D-PhD16-4.3	A novel tool to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust		M40		We did not create SNapperDB for the pathogen Kp yet. We are finalizing the manuscript on cgLINcodes for Kp first.
	D-PhD16-4.4	Optimization of our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with 7-gene MLST		M42		
	D-PhD16-4.5	Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric		M42		
	D-PhD16-4.6	Designed a method to identify recombination in cgMLST		M40		

	D-PhD16-4.7	Integration of MLSL identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available		M42		
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PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
PhD16-FBZ2/AMR6.1-Codes4strains	M-PhD16-3.3	SNapperDB databases set-up for both pathogens	M36	Yes/no		Yes, for Ec; not yet for Kp
	M-PhD16-4.1	Simulations completed	M42	No		Priority to writing the publication on the cgLINcodes approach
	M-PhD16-4.2	Publication submitted	M48	Yes/no		Submitted and under Review
	D-PhD16-4.4	Optimization of our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with 7-gene MLST	M42	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.5	Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric	M42	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.6	Designed a method to identify recombination in cgMLST	M40	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.7	Integration of MLSL identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available	M42	Yes		

17.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

None in this reporting period.

17.6. Publications and patents

In addition to the main project, I also contributed to side projects. The PhD host lab comprises the National Reference Center for *Corynebacteria* of the *diphtheriae* complex (i.e., *C. diphtheriae*, *C. ulcerans* and phylogenetically related species; <https://www.pasteur.fr/fr/sante-publique/CNR/les-cnr/corynebacteries-du-complexe-diphtheriae>). It thereby collects and characterizes all potentially toxigenic strains identified in French metropolitan area and overseas territories for 11 years. This unique collection of isolates and the associated clinical and epidemiological data has been an essential resource for various related projects.

I have been interested in and contributed to a few of these projects, including the study of the diversity and evolution of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* and the computational research of antimicrobial resistance. Below is a list of articles where I have made contributions:

Hennart, M., Guglielmini, J., Maiden, M.C., Jolley, K.A., Criscuolo, A. and Brisse, S., 2021. A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains. bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>

Guglielmini J., Hennart M., Badell E., Toubiana J., Criscuolo A., Brisse S., 2021. Genomic epidemiology and strain taxonomy of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. 0(ja): JCM.01581-21.

Badell, E., Alharazi, A., Criscuolo, A., Almoayed, K.A.A., Lefrancq, N., Bouchez, V., Guglielmini, J., Hennart, M., Carmi-Leroy, A., Zidane, N., Pascal-Perrigault, M., Lebreton, M., Martini, H., Salje, H., Toubiana, J., Dureab, F., Dhabaan, G., Brisse, S., Rawah, A.A., Aldawla, M.A., Al-Awdi, E.M., Al-Moalmy, N.M., Al-Shami, H.Z., Al-Somainy, A.A., 2021. Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study. *Lancet Microbe* 0. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(21\)00094-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(21)00094-X)

Badell, E., Hennart, M., Rodrigues, C., Passet, V., Dazas, M., Panunzi, L., Bouchez, V., Carmi-Leroy, A., Toubiana, J., Brisse, S., 2020. *Corynebacterium rouxii* sp. nov., a novel member of the diphtheriae species complex. *Res. Microbiol.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2020.02.003> PMID: 32119905.

Hennart, M., Panunzi, L.G., Rodrigues, C., Gaday, Q., Baines, S.L., Barros-Pinkelnic, M., Carmi-Leroy, A., Dazas, M., Wehenkel, A.M., Didelot, X., Toubiana, J., Badell, E., Brisse, S., 2020. Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. *Genome Med.* 12, 107. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-020-00805-7> PMID: 33246485; PMCID: PMC7694903.

17.7. Impact and Relevance

The project will define, implement and evaluate a novel bioinformatics strategy to classify and name strains within pathogenic bacteria, from the level of deep subspecific lineages down to shallower levels of diversity that differentiate epidemiological related strains from non-related ones. It will be first tested on *Ec* and *Kp*, two important ubiquitous 'One Health' pathogens. However, the general applicability of the approach means that in the future, the classification and nomenclature of strains of other pathogens could benefit from the PhD project outcomes.

By facilitating in the future, communication on bacterial strains across sectors and countries, the project is highly relevant to multiple topics and objectives of One Health EJP: antibiotic resistance clonal dissemination, emerging pathogens, cross-sector transmission, public health and basic microbiology integration.

This document is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This Programme has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830

The project will deliver a novel nomenclature system of bacterial pathogens genomes that will be stable by design, unlike existing systems based on SNPs and cgMLST single linkage groupings. This has a far-reaching impact on possibilities to integrate efforts of agencies (e.g., at the international levels, ECDC, EFSA, PulseNet international) to detect, monitor, understand and control the spread of pathogens.

17.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

No requirements from Ethics Advisors

17.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

No impact, as our bioinformatics work was not affected.

17.10. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	No
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	None

17.11. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

The novel method developed in the PhD project will find natural dissemination ways via the existing networks of collaborations in which the main investigators are involved: MedVetKlebs (just finished JRP), KlebNET, SpARK, kleb-GAP and Nor-Kleb-Net for Kp (see MedVetKlebs final report); and Ec surveillance networks and national and international levels (e.g., French NRC & NRL @Pasteur and ANSES; ECDC; PulseNet international).

The novel nomenclature system will be compared with existing nomenclatures (dictionaries of nomenclature correspondence between LIN codes and current SNP/cgMLST nomenclatures for wider communication and backwards-compatibility) and will need in the future to be integrated in existing platforms that serve nomenclatures of bacterial strains (e.g., SnapperDB, EnteroBase, BIGSdb-Oxford and PulseNet international for *E. coli*; BIGSdb-Pasteur for *K. pneumoniae*). Future interactions with 'dev-op' specialists (application developers) will be established with free software such as EnteroBase, BIGSdb and Innuendo; or commercial software such as BioNumerics or SeqSphere.

Following the writing of the first draft of our publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications, Martin M.C. Maiden and Keith A. Jolley became aware of it and were interested in applying our methods on other pathogens

of interest to the One Health perspective (Campylobacter) or Clinical/Antimicrobial resistance (N. gonorrhoeae)

17.12. List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	“Journées Boris Ephrussi” 2021 Poster: A new approach for naming bacterial strains, combining cgMLST and LIN codes		
Date:	27 - 28th May 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	3rd One Health European Joint Project (OHEJP) Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Presentation of poster.		
Date:	9-11 June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		0

18. PhD17- SUSTAIN

Fieldwork:

From the 3rd to the 17th of October, I conducted fieldwork in Italy, interviewing experts from the veterinary institutes of different regions (in Brescia, Padova, Bologna and Teramo).

Research work:

The start of 2021 was used to finalise the manuscript “Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”. I transcribed interviews that were conducted with public health and environmental experts from Italian institutes in autumn 2020. Additionally, I supported the NOVA project by analysing interviews. A survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. Data gathering was completed in June 2021 and followed by analysis.

An edited book will be published by Oxford University Press, and I was invited to write a chapter with Chris Degeling (University of Wollongong in Australia) on One Health and AMR in the European Union. This chapter is under construction. An author workshop was held in September. The chapter will be finalised in December.

In March 2021, the “One Health governance” online survey was launched. From July 2021, data was analysed and based on the data, I am working on writing an article.

After the fieldwork in Italy, the process of transcribing interviews was initiated.

Scientific output:

Two articles were published in 2021:

“Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”. *Medicina* journal by MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>

“One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination”. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>

Teaching:

In spring 2021, I taught a Bachelor class on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health” in the course “International Institutions and Global Governance”.

Conferences:

I participated at the:

OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 by engaging in the three-minute competition and presenting my research at the conference (Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy). Additionally, I supported the organizing team in creating and presenting kahoot quizzes, which were held in the breaks of the conference, accessible for both the online and on-site participants.

14th European Public Health Conference via a poster presentation and a participation in a workshop called “The contribution of Environmental Impact Assessments to better health”

GRASP festival, which was a conference (including some arts and performances), where I presented on-site some of my findings of the survey data.

18.1. Summary

The SUSTAIN PhD project is connected to WP7 of the OHEJP but it is not connected to specific tasks, deliverables or milestones.

Nevertheless, there has been progress. In 2021, data analysis was conducted as planned for the PhD project. This included transcribing interviews with experts from public health and environmental agencies and Italy. Data gathering for the interviews has been slowed down due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Due to travel restrictions, the remaining interviews were conducted in October 2021 with Italian veterinary experts. Subsequently, they were transcribed the analysis will start in 2022.

Data analysis was also conducted for the NOVA project “Surveillance barriers and opportunities as perceived by med-vet-food experts”.

Further, a survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. The survey is addressed to ministries, EU institutions, international organisations and high-level members of staff from public health, veterinary, environment and food agencies. The analysis of the survey data started after the end of the survey in July 2021 and an article is being prepared.

Within the PhD project, several articles must be produced. In March and June 2021, two articles were published (<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>) and (<https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>).

All teaching obligations (defined by Roskilde University) were completed after the spring semester 2020. However, I did teach a Bachelor class on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health.”

18.2. Overview of project progress

The SUSTAIN PhD project is connected to WP7 of the OHEJP but it is not connected to specific tasks, deliverables or milestones.

Nevertheless, there has been progress. In 2021, data analysis was conducted as planned for the PhD project. This included transcribing interviews with experts from public health and environmental agencies and Italy. Data gathering for the interviews has been slowed down due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Due to travel restrictions, the remaining interviews were conducted in October 2021 with Italian veterinary experts. Subsequently, they were transcribed the analysis will start in 2022.

Data analysis was also conducted for the NOVA project “Surveillance barriers and opportunities as perceived by med-vet-food experts”.

Further, a survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. The survey is addressed to ministries, EU institutions, international organisations and high-level members of staff from public health, veterinary, environment and food agencies. The analysis of the survey data started after the end of the survey in July 2021 and an article is being prepared.

Within the PhD project, a number of articles must be produced. In March and June 2021, two articles were published (<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>) and (<https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>).

All teaching obligations (defined by Roskilde University) were completed after the spring semester 2020. However, I did teach a Bachelor class on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health”.

18.3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

The SUSTAIN PhD project is connected to WP7 of the OHEJP but it is not connected to specific tasks, deliverables or milestones.

The start of 2021 was used to finalise the manuscript “Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”, which is a co-authored article with Alberto Mantovani. The article was published in March 2021.

Another focus was put on transcribing interviews that were conducted with public and environmental experts in Italy at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità; the Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale; and the Istituti Zooprofilattici in October 2020 and 2021. The first round of transcriptions was concluded in April and the second round in December. The interviews will be analysed in 2022.

Additionally, I supported the NOVA project “Surveillance barriers and opportunities as perceived by med-vet-food experts”. After having conducted the interviews and started transcription and coding in 2020, we (Maria-Eleni Filippitzi & I) analysed the data in 2021.

A survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. The survey was addressed to ministries, EU institutions, international organisations and high-level members of staff from public health, veterinary, environment and food agencies. The online survey examined policy networks for One Health by understanding policy- and decision-making processes of One Health. The survey investigated political constrains for turning One Health topics into policy (science to policy) to shed light on opportunities for One health policy integration. Data gathering was completed in June July 2021 and followed by analysis. Based on this data, an article is being developed.

An edited book by Olivier Rubin, Erik Bækkeskov and Louise Munkholm (tentative title: Steering against Superbugs – The Global Governance of Antimicrobial Resistance) will be published by Oxford University Press and I was invited to write a chapter with Chris Degeling (University of Wollongong in Australia). The chapter will be about One Health and AMR in the European Union. This chapter is under construction and will be finalised by the end of this year. It will use a literature review as well as data from the survey (described above).

Within the PhD project, a minimum of three articles must be produced, of which at least two have to be self-authored. In 2020, two co-authored articles were published (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146> & <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-021-00277-y>). In 2021, one a co-authored and a self-authored article was published (<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240> & <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>). One singled-authored article is accepted and in the process of being published.

All teaching obligations (defined by Roskilde University) were completed after the spring semester 2020. However, I did teach a Bachelor class in April 2021 on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health”.

Dissemination of the research was done by presenting at the OHEJP ASM 2021. At the conference in June, my PhD project was presented online at the 3MT competition. Additionally, the abstract I submitted was accepted for an oral presentation, where I had the opportunity to present my research titled “Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy” on-site at the ASM.

I also presented my research at the 14th European Public Health Conference with one poster and by participating in a workshop titled “The contribution of Environmental Impact Assessments to better health” where my focus was to discuss the benefits of the One Health approach within Environmental Impact Assessments. The event was online.

At the GRASP festival/conference, I presented some of my research based on the online survey titled “Challenges of policy actors to integrate the One Health approach into health emergency policy initiatives”. The event was on-site in Roskilde, Denmark.

18.4. Progress of the research project: Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverables of Roskilde University's PhD School:

Every 6 months, the status of the PhD progress is assessed by the half-yearly evaluation, which entails detailed description of the past 6 months in terms of status, changes in the time schedule or budget plan, the nature of supervision, research stays at other institutes, the assessment of all attended events (courses, conferences) as well as teaching hours.

Teaching: 250 hours for the whole period of the PhD
All teaching hours are completed

Total of 30 acts for whole period of PhD

From January to December 2021:

Attendance and presentation at conference

- OHEJP ASM (Copenhagen, Denmark)
- European Public Health Conference (online)
- GRASP conference (Roskilde, Denmark)

Courses

- 2 courses: Get your Article Published in a Social Science or Business Journal
- Work in Progress seminars (research group at Roskilde University)
- OHEJP Summer School
- Workshop on research communication
- Seminar on writing a Kappe (article-based dissertation)
- Quantitative research method workshop

Minimum requirement of 30 acts is reached

Fieldwork and change of research environment stay, 3- 6 months
All fieldwork and research stays are completed

Publications (Mandatory: three articles of which at least two are self-authored articles)

- Three co-authored articles published
- One single-authored article accepted and in the publishing process
- Remaining articles to be done in 2021 & 2022

Milestones:

None reached

18.5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Teaching at bachelor level: International Institutions and Global Governance	Global governance Policy Area IV: Health	19.04.21	Roskilde University
OHEJP Summer School 2021	Environmental Issues in One Health: from risk assessment to surveillance	26.07.-06.08.21	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
Course: Get your Article Published in a Social Science or Business Journal (1/3)	Getting started (writing an abstract and an introduction)	18.05.21	Roskilde University
Virtual PhD Career Seminar	Understanding the job market, how do employers view PhDs as candidates for a position?, Competences and career paths as a PhD	12.04.21	Roskilde University

PhD Workshop on Research Communication	How to disseminate research to news outlets	09.09.21	Roskilde University
PhD Seminar on Writing a Kappe/Frame	Understanding the process of writing an article-based PhD dissertation	14.-15.09.21	Roskilde University
PhD Quantitative research method workshop	Sectional simple and multivariate regressions	16.09.21	Roskilde University
Course: Get your Article Published in a Social Science or Business Journal (2/3)	Writing a first draft of an article	26.10.21	Roskilde University

18.6. Publications and patents

Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach

<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>

gold open access (no fees)

Uploaded to Zenodo

Abstract for the OHEJP ASM 2021 - Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy

One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination

<https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>

gold open access (no fees)

Uploaded to Zenodo

18.7. Impact and Relevance

The PhD project has a unique angle on One Health. The project investigates One Health integration, implementation and how One Health is put into practice within public health, veterinary, food and environment institutes. The results of this research can be used by all partners to evaluate and consider their coordination and collaboration efforts. It can be used to enhance disease surveillance nationally and internationally. It produces useful knowledge and examples for institutes on challenges and opportunities for collaboration and for institutionalising One Health activities. On a political level, it will provide insight into sharing and translating knowledge between scientists and politicians.

18.8. Follow-up of recommendations and comments in previous reviews by Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers' comments have been accepted and this is closed.

18.9. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on project

The Covid-19 pandemic has affected my PhD project, as there were changes in terms of fieldwork, conferences and courses. Conferences were postponed or rescheduled to online events, which impedes the ability to network.

My fieldwork was postponed or cancelled and cut short. In spring 2020, a research stay in Sweden at the Swedish Veterinary Agency was planned to conduct my fieldwork. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, I remained in Denmark and conducted my interviews online via Microsoft Teams and Skype instead of conducting face-to-face interviews.

A three-month fieldwork stay in Italy at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità and the veterinary institutes in the autumn semester 2020 was shortened to a one month stay in October 2020 and another month stay in October 2021.

17.10 List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

17.11 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Roskilde University has a small “AMR Social Science” research group which I am part of. One project is the development of an edited book with the title “Steering against Superbugs – The Global Governance of Antimicrobial Resistance”.

17.12 List of Dissemination activities

Name of the activity:	3 rd One Health European Joint Project (OHEJP) Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Presentation of poster, participation in 3-minute thesis competition, organisation of team for Kahoot quizzes.		
Date:	9-11/06/2021		
Place:	Copenhagen, Denmark and Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	20
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	14th European Public Health Conference – Poster presentation and workshop/oral presentation		
Date:	10-13/11/2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	GRASP – A FESTIVAL OF NEW IDEAS – Conference – Oral presentation		
Date:	18/11/2021		
Place:	Roskilde, Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	5	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

